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Appendix A

Search Strategy

Eight databases, one book, and three papers were searched in three phases (see Table A1).

Table A1

Data Source and Retrieval Time

Databases/Papers/Book	Search engines / Platforms	Phases and span of retrieved papers		
		Nov 2020–Feb 2021	Jan 2022	Aug 2023
PubMed	PubMed search engine			
MEDLINE	Ovid	Before 01 Jan 2021	01 Jan 2021–01 Jan 2022	01 Jan 2022–01 Aug 2023
Embase	Embase.com			
Cochrane Library	Cochrane platform			
Web of Science	Web of Science platform			
PsycINFO	EBSCOhost	/	/	Before 01 Aug 2023
PsycARTICLES	EBSCOhost			
CINAHL	EBSCOhost			
Glanz et al. (2008)		Covering health behavior theories between 1986 and 2005.	/	/

Kwasnicka et al. (2016)	Covering theories related to behavior maintenance / before March 1, 2014.		/
Michie et al. (2005)	/	/	Before July 2004
Davis et al. (2014)	/	/	01 Jan 1960–11 Sep 2012

Full search strategy was informed by a systematic review of behavior theories (Kwasnicka et al., 2016). The strategy replicated the search (sets 1-4) adding other terms related to behavior change theory (set 5). The search terms and structure remained uniform across the eight databases and the search string for the original electronic search was run as follows:

Set 1: Behavior change theory terms: “behavior change theories” OR “behavior change theory” OR “behavior theories” OR “behaviour change theories” OR “behaviour change theory” OR “behaviour theories” OR “diffusion of innovations” OR “elaboration likelihood model” OR “goal theory” OR “information motivation behavioral skills model” OR “information motivation behavioural skills model” OR “rational addiction model” OR “social cognition models” OR “behavior change models” OR “behavior change model”

Set 2: Behavior theory terms: “acculturation theory” OR “AIDS risk reduction model” OR “behavior economic theories” OR “behaviour economic theories” OR “communication theory” OR “community organisation theory” OR “community organization theory” OR “consumer information processing model” OR “control theory” OR “critical consciousness” OR “decisional balance theory” OR “ecological model” OR “ecological perspective” OR “empowerment theory” OR “enculturation theory” OR “exchange theory” OR “fear

arousal theory” OR “goal setting theory” OR “goal theory” OR “habit theory” OR “health belief model” OR “health promotion theories”
OR “health promotion theory” OR “health behaviour theory” OR “health behavior theory” OR “innovation-decision process” OR
“interactionist model” OR “intrapersonal theory” OR “intrinsic motivation theories” OR “multicomponent stage model” OR “natural
recovery” OR “operant learning theory” OR “operant theory” OR “organisational change theory” OR “organizational change theory” OR
“personality theory” OR “precaution adoption process” OR “protection motivation theory” OR “reciprocal causality” OR “reciprocal
determinism” OR "risk behaviour theory" OR "risk behavior theory" OR “self regulation theory” OR “self-regulation theory” OR “self-
determination theory” OR “self-efficacy theory” OR “self-perception theory” OR “social capital” OR “social cognitive theory” OR “social
comparison theory” OR “social determinism” OR “social influence” OR “social learning theories” OR “social learning theory” OR “social
marketing theory” OR “social structural theory” OR “social support” OR “stage of change model” OR “stages of change model” OR
“systems theory” OR “theories of planned behavior” OR “theories of planned behaviour” OR “theory of planned behavior” OR “theory of
planned behaviour” OR “theory of reasoned action” OR “transtheoretical model” OR “value-expectancy theory”

Set 3: Change terms: “behaviour change” OR “behavior change” OR “behaviour modification” OR “behavior modification” OR
“mediation effects on behaviour” OR “mediation effects on behavior” OR “normative change” OR “normative changes” OR “cultural

change” OR “cultural changes” OR “social change” OR “social changes” OR “group level effect” OR “group level effects” OR “social development” or “social developments” OR “behavioural interventions” OR “behavioral interventions” OR “behavioural intervention” OR “behavioral intervention”

Set 4: Maintenance relevant terms: “maintenance” OR “behaviour maintenance” OR “behavior maintenance” OR “maintain” OR “sustain” OR “sustained behaviour” OR “sustained behavior” OR “sustained change” OR “habit” OR “habitual behaviour” OR “habitual behavior” OR “maintenance stage”

Set 5: Other related to behavior change theory terms: “behavior change model” OR “behavior change models” OR “behaviour change model” OR “behaviour change models” OR “behavior change framework” OR “behaviour change framework”

The search result was limited to articles written in English, and other restriction were applied in accordance with the exclusion criteria: (a) studies about non-human, non-health-related behaviors, or non-specific theories, such as animal behavior, solely psychological mechanisms, pharmacologic actions, or relational ethics; (b) strategies, technologies, treatments, and approaches for a specific program or scene, as well as design guidelines and evaluation systems for interventions; (c) immature or variant theories, such as theories that have not been fully verified, simple variations, integration, or reinterpretation of other theories.

Appendix B

Theories Assessed in the Review

Table B1

Theories From the Review and Multiple Databases

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Affect infusion model (AIM; Forgas, 1995, 2001)	“A comprehensive account of the role of affective states in social judgments” (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Mood
AIDS Risk Reduction Model (ARRM; Catania et al., 1990)	“A model of AIDS Risk Reduction Process” (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Knowledge (e.g., HIV Transmission, health utility, and enjoyability) Perceived susceptibility Social networks Social norms Costs and benefits: response efficacy (It refers to perceived instrumentality, which is a belief that one’s actions will be effective and will have desired consequences.) and enjoyment. Self-efficacy Skills Social support Aversive emotional states Help seeking

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
		External motivators (cues) Labeling, commitment, enactment (three phases: information-seeking, obtaining remedies, enacting solutions).
Alcohol expectancy theory (Christiansen et al., 1982; Davis et al., 2013; Jones et al., 2001)	The expectancies can determine the actual behavioral effects of alcohol (Christiansen et al., 1982, p. 336).	Expectancy
Alcohol myopia theory (Steele & Josephs, 1990)	“The theories are based on alcohol’s impairment of perception and thought—the myopia it causes—rather than on the ability of alcohol’s pharmacology to directly cause specific reactions or on expectations associated with alcohol’s use” (Steele & Josephs, 1990, p. 921).	Cognitive impairments
Angelo (Swinburn et al., 1999)	A conceptual model for understanding the obesogenic of environments and a practical tool for prioritizing environmental elements for research and intervention (Swinburn et al., 1999, p. 563).	Physical Economic Political Sociocultural Microenvironmental settings Macroenvironmental sectors
Associative-cybernetic model (de Wit & Dickinson, 2009)	A theory encapsulates two routes of action (outcome-response and response-outcome) to describe the action selection.	Outcome-Response (O-R) Response-Outcome (R-O)
Attitude-social influence- efficacy model / Integrated	Integrated Change Model (the I-Change Model), derived from the attitude-social influence-self-	Motivation factors Attitude: pros & cons and rational &

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)	efficacy model that can be considered as an integration of ideas of Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behaviour, Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, Prochaska's Transtheoretical Model, the Health Belief Model, and Implementation and Goal setting theories (De Vries et al., 2005, p. 155).	<p>emotional.</p> <p>Social influences: norms, modelling, and pressure.</p> <p>Self-efficacy: social-, stress-, skills-, and routine self-efficacy.</p> <p>Predisposing factors: social and cultural factors, behavioural factors (e.g., life styles), psychological factors, and biological factors.</p> <p>Information factors: message, channel, and source.</p> <p>Awareness factors: knowledge, cues to action, and risk perceptions.</p> <p>Ability factors: implementation plans and performance skills.</p> <p>Barriers</p> <p>Intention state: precontemplation, contemplation, and preparation.</p> <p>Behavioural state: trial and maintenance.</p>
Attribution theory (Jones, 1976; Rubenstein & Thoron, 2017)	"Attribution theory is defined as the way that individuals envision the success or failure of their own behavior or the behavior of others" (Rubenstein & Thoron, 2017, p. 1).	Behavioral attribution
BASNEF model (Heather, 2005; Momeni et al., 2020)	BASNEF is the acronym for belief, attitude, subjective norm, and enabling factor. "The BASNEF model is based on Fishbein's theory regarding attitude	<p>Beliefs</p> <p>Attitudes</p> <p>Subjective norm</p>

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
	structures, behavioral intention, subjective norms, and enabling factors such as the skill of performing a behavior, time, and expenditure” (Momeni et al., 2020, p. 2).	Behavior intention Enabling factors (e.g., skill, time, expenditure, and information) Behavior change
Behavior setting theory (Popov & Chompalov, 2012)	“Behavior setting theory was developed by Roger Barker to explain small-scale social systems, as well as the study of behavior in its natural environment” (Popov & Chompalov, 2012, p. 18).	Small-scale social systems
Behavioral choice theory (Epstein, 1998; Lacey & Rachlin, 1978; Vlek, 1991)	This is “a theoretical approach that attempts to understand decision making and how time and responses are allocated given the options available” (Epstein, 1998, p. 258).	Behavioral cost Available alternatives Reinforcer Delay between choosing and receiving the alternatives Choice
Behaviour Centred Design (BCD; Aunger & Curtis, 2016; White et al., 2016)	“Behaviour Centred Design (BCD) is a new approach to behaviour change which focuses, not on improving knowledge, but on identifying and employing behavioural levers which enable or inhibit change” (White et al., 2016, p. 349).	Brain (process related) Body Environment Behaviour Behaviour setting State-of-the-world
Behavioural ecological model (BEM; Dresler-Hawke & Veer, 2006; Hovell et al., 2002)	“The BEM is an extension of social cognitive theories and is multifaceted in nature. The model is concerned with behaviour, environmental change and public policy that help individuals make healthy choices. The BEM recognizes that any behaviour is	Individual level Local level Community level Socio-cultural level

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
	affected through multiple levels of influence” (Dresler-Hawke & Veer, 2006, p. 319).	
Behavioural reasoning theory (Westaby, 2005)	“The theory proposes that reasons serve as important linkages between beliefs, global motives (e.g., attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived control), intentions, and behavior” (Westaby, 2005, p. 97).	Reason
Belief systems theory (Grube et al., 1994)	“Belief system theory is a theory of organization that attempts to explain and understand how beliefs and behaviors are interrelated and the conditions under which belief systems remain stable or undergo change” (Grube et al., 1994, p. 154).	Values (cognitive representations of individual needs and desire) Belief Attitudes Self-conceptions
Broaden-and-build theory of positive emotions (Fredrickson, 1998)	This theory proposes that positive emotions, such as joy and gratitude, broaden individuals’ cognitive and behavioral repertoires, leading to increased creativity, resilience, and personal growth. This theory suggests that positive emotions play a role beyond momentary pleasure, facilitating exploration and the development of valuable psychological resources over time (Fredrickson, 1998).	Emotions
Change theory (Lewin, 1943)	Lewin’s Change Theory, also known as the “Unfreeze-Change-Refreeze” model, is a conceptual framework for understanding and managing organizational and social change. It suggests that successful change involves three stages: unfreezing the existing state, implementing the desired change, and then	Unfreeze Change Refreeze

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
	refreezing the new state to make it the new norm (Lewin, 1943).	
Classical conditioning (Skinner, 2014)	A kind of learning in which the stimulus or experience occurs before the behavior and then gets paired or associated with the behavior.	Classical conditioning Conditioned stimulus Response
Cognitive evaluation theory (CET; Hoss, 1985)	Cognitive Evaluation Theory (CET) focuses on the effects of external consequences on internal motivation, especially on autonomy and competence.	Intrinsic motivation Rewards
Cognitive-Social Health Information-Processing Model (C-SHIP model; Mille et al., 1996; Shaw et al., 2008)	The C-SHIP model focuses on how individuals cognitively and affectively process information about their health behavior and how it translates into health-enhancing or health-defeating behaviors.	Information processing
COM-B system (Michie et al., 2011)	A “behavior system” involves three essential conditions: capability, opportunity, and motivation (Michie et al., 2011, p. 1), which is the theoretical foundation of behavior change wheel.	Motivation: basic drives, automatic processes, and reflective processes. Capability: psychological capability and physical capability. Opportunity: social opportunity and physical opportunity.
Common-sense model of self-regulation (CSM; Leventhal et al., 2003; Leventhal et al., 2016)	“The Common-Sense Model of Self-Regulation (CSM) provides a conceptual framework for examining the perceptual, behavioral and cognitive processes involved in individuals’ self-management of ongoing and future health threats” (Leventhal et al., 2016, p. 935).	Situational stimuli (inner and outer) Representation of danger Representation of fear Coping procedures Action plans Appraisal

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Conceptual model of psychosocial risk and protective factors for excessive gestational weight gain (Hill et al., 2013)	This model outlines the psychosocial determinants of gestational weight gain, including the role of motivation and self-efficacy toward healthy behaviors (Hill et al., 2013, p. 110).	Feedback loop Maternal psychological factors Knowledge/Understanding of weight gain during pregnancy Familial/Social-contextual factors Coping skills Body image during pregnancy Self-efficacy Motivation Physical activity and eating behaviors Gestational weight gain
Conservation of resources theory (COR; Hobfoll, 1989)	“This resource-oriented model is based on the supposition that people strive to retain, protect, and build resources and that what is threatening to them is the potential or actual loss of these valued resources” (Hobfoll, 1989, p. 513).	Resource (e.g., things, personality traits, conditions, and resources of energy)
Context-dependent repetition (Lally & Gardner, 2013; Lally et al., 2010; Lally et al., 2011)	“As behaviours are repeated in consistent settings they then begin to proceed more efficiently and with less thought as control of the behaviour transfers to cues in the environment that activate an automatic response: a habit” (Lally et al., 2010).	Context Habit
Context, executive, and operational systems theory (CEOS Theory; Borland, 2016)	The CEOS theory proposes that behavior results from the interaction between an individual’s internal needs and motivations (operational processes) and their environmental context, which is modulated by	Executive System (ES) Operational System (OS) Self-regulation

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Control theory (Carver & Scheier, 1982)	goal-directed cognitive processes (executive systems; Borland, 2016). “A theory explains how people perceive the environment they live in and how they react to the environmental changes” (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Reference value Goal Comparator Input function (perception) Output function (behavior) Impact on environment Disturbance Feedback loop
Coping planning (Sniehotta et al., 2005)	“A distinction is made between action planning and coping planning” (Sniehotta et al., 2005, p. 565).	Action planning Coping planning
Cross-cultural psychology (Triandis, 1999)	Cross-cultural psychology studies how cultural factors influence people think, feel, and behavior.	Cultural factors
Dietary restraint theory (Polivy & Herman, 1985)	This theory establish the association between binge eating and dieting and present sequence data indicating that dieting usually precedes bingeing, chronologically (Polivy & Herman, 1985, p. 193).	Physiological factors Cognitions factors
Dual process model of self-control (Friese et al., 2008; Hofmann et al., 2008)	“A model of impulsive and reflective influences on health behaviour” (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Automatic affective reactions (implicit attitude) Automatic approach-avoidance reactions Reasoned attitudes Restraint standards Habitualness Cognitive load Ego depletion

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
		Alcohol consumption (influence consciousness process) Trait self-control Working memory capacity Mood Health-related behavior
Dual-Process Theory (Kahneman, 1973)	This theory suggests that human thinking operates through two cognitive systems: System 1, which is intuitive and automatic, and System 2, which is deliberate and analytical. In terms of behavior, this theory highlights how individuals' decision-making and actions are influenced by the interplay between these two cognitive systems, impacting responses to various situations (Kahneman, 1973).	System 1: intuitive and automatic. System 2: deliberate and analytical.
Dynamic social systems model (DSSM; Latkin et al., 2010)	A model for HIV-related behaviors emphasizes the dynamic and social nature of the structural factors that influencing HIV prevention and detection (Latkin et al., 2010, p. 222).	Resources: material resources and allocations, science & technology. Influence & control factors (informal or formal) Contextual interconnectedness factors: social interconnectedness. Transfer of resources: material, information, and technology. Social influence & control processes Prevention skills Perceived norms Motivations

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Empowerment theory (Zimmerman, 1995)	Psychological empowerment integrates perceptions of personal control, a proactive approach to life, and a critical understanding of one's sociopolitical environment (Zimmerman, 1995).	Beliefs Mental health status Biological factors Social constructs (e.g., gender, race/ethnicity, and sexual orientation) Access HIV-related behaviors
Environmental research framework for weight gain prevention (Kremers et al., 2006)	“In the framework, behavior is postulated to be the result of a simultaneous influence of conscious and unconscious processes. Environmental influences are hypothesized to influence behavior both indirectly and directly” (Kremers et al., 2006, p. 1).	Physical environment Political environment Economic environment Sociocultural environment Cognitive mediators: attitude, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control, and intention. Energy balance-related behavior

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
		Person: demographic, personality, awareness, and involvement. Habit strength Clustering (co-occurrence of behaviors)
Episodic future thinking (Schacter et al., 2017)	“Episodic future thinking refers to the capacity to imagine or simulate experiences that might occur in one’s personal future” (Schacter et al., 2017, p. 41).	Episodic future thinking Episodic memory
Extended information processing model (Flay et al., 1980)	The extended information-processing model proposes a 12-step process of how communication influences belief, attitude, and intention, from initial exposure to final behavior (Flay et al., 1980).	Exposure Awareness Knowledge Memory Opinion/Belief Retention Attitude (affective) Persistence Intentions Resistance Behavior Maintenance
Evo-Eco approach (Aunger & Curtis, 2014a)	The Evo-Eco model is a theory rooted in evolutionary biology and ecological psychology to understand behavioral changes (Aunger & Curtis, 2014a).	Brain: reactive brain (for reactions to environmental stimuli), motivated brain (motivational system), and executive brain (executive control of behavior). Body Environment: physical environment, biological environment, and social

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Evolved structure of human motivation (Aunger & Curtis, 2013)	From the perspective of this study, motives can be considered psychological mechanisms to produce behavior that solves evolutionarily important tasks in the human niche (Aunger & Curtis, 2013, p. 49).	environment. Setting Behavior Motivation
Extended parallel process model (EPPM; Witte, 1992)	The Extended Parallel Processing Model, also known as Threat Management or Fear Management, studies how rational considerations (efficacy beliefs) and emotional reactions (fear of a health threat) combine to determine behavioral decisions.	Message components Perceived efficacy Perceived threat: severity/susceptibility. Protection motivation Defensive motivation Adaptive changes Maladaptive changes Individual difference Fear
Family process theory (Broderick, 1993)	This theory focuses on the dynamics and interactions within family units, emphasizing how family members' behaviors, roles, and communication patterns influence the overall functioning of the family system (Broderick, 1993).	Family
Family systems theory (Bowen, 1966; Johnson & Ray, 2016)	“Family systems theory places primary focus on exchanges of behavior that take place in a given moment of interaction between members of the family” (Johnson & Ray, 2016, p. 782).	Family

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Feedback intervention theory (FIT; Kluger & DeNisi, 1996)	The central assumption of FIT is that FIs change the locus of attention among three general and hierarchically organized levels of control, which suggest that FI effectiveness decreases as attention moves up the hierarchy closer to the self and away from the task (Kluger & DeNisi, 1996).	Feedback Locus of attention
Fisher's social influence theory (Fisher, 1988)	Social influence involves direct and indirect ways in which people can affect each other, an approach to behavior change that has long captured the attention of social psychologists (Fisher, 1988, p. 914).	Social network Social influence
Focus theory of normative conduct (Cialdini et al., 1990)	This theory posits that norms guide behavior most strongly when attention is focused on them, such that norms must be prominent in order for people to act in accordance with them (Cialdini et al., 1990).	Descriptive norms Injunctive norms Personal norms Focus of attention
Fogg Behavior Model (FBM; Fogg et al., 2003; Fogg, 2009a, 2009b)	The Fogg Behavior Model shows that three elements must converge at the same moment for a behavior to occur: motivation, ability, and a prompt.	Motivation Ability Prompt
Ford's motivational system theory (MST; Van Dellen, 2012)	"Ford sees motivation as a process bringing together emotions, beliefs about one's own capabilities and the context, and personal goals" (Van Dellen, 2012, p. 40).	Personal goal Competence Competence beliefs Context Context beliefs Emotions
Goal conflict model (Stroebe et al., 2007)	"A theory of eating regulation" (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Goal conflict

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Goal content theory (GCT; Deci & Ryan, 2000; Gunnell et al., 2014; Gill et al., 2021)	GCT was developed to understand how the content of a goal can lead to differential outcomes affecting well-being and behavior (Deci & Ryan, 2000).	Goal contents
Goal setting theory (Locke & Latham, 2002)	A theory based on Ryan's (1970) premise that conscious goals affect action (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Goal core Goal mechanisms: choice/direction, effort, persistence, and strategies. Performance Satisfaction with performance and rewards Moderators: goal commitment, goal importance, self-efficacy, feedback, and task complexity. Willingness to commit to new challenges
Goal theory (Bagozzi, 1992)	“A theory explains the processes that occur between intentions and goal-directed behaviours” (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Self-efficacies Instrumental beliefs Affect toward means Choice among means Intention to perform means Planning Monitoring activities Guidance & control Psychological commitment Effort Goal achievement Facilitating/Inhibiting conditions

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Groningen Active Living Model (GALM; Kwasnicka et al., 2016; Stevens et al., 1999)	The Groningen Active Living Model (GALM) is a behavioral change strategy for stimulating leisure-time physical activity participation (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Treatment (3 phases) Subjective fitness (before program) Subjective fitness (after program) Social support Self-efficacy Enjoy/Pleasure Outcome Participants (related to demographic variables) Implementing organization Delivery mode Microcontext
Habit and intention theory (Ouellette & Wood, 1998)	Past behavior guides future responses through two processes: habit and intentions.	Past behavior Decision making Intention
Habit formation theory (HFT; Gardner et al., 2012)	This theory suggests forming habits by repeating an action consistently in the same context.	Habit
Habit theory (Verplanken, 2006; Verplanken & Aarts, 1999; Verplanken & Orbell, 2003; Verplanken et al., 2008)	“A theory of habit; habit is defined as a psychological construct, rather than simply past behavioural frequency; refers to ‘habitual mindsets’” (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Habit
Health action model (HAM; Mazaheri & Heidarnia, 2015; Seaman, 2010; Tones, 1987; Vahedian-Shahroodi et al., 2019)	The integration of the Health Belief Model and the Theory of Reasoned Action.	Normative system Attitude system Belief system Self concept

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Health Action Process Approach (HAPA; Schwarzer, 1992, 2008, 2016b; Sniehotta et al., 2005)	The health action process approach (HAPA) is a hybrid model with a continuum layer as well as a stage layer.	Adapting to healthy behavior or reverting to previous practice Facilitators: skills, knowledge, access to resource, communication, and supporting environment. Behavioral intention Healthy behavior
Health behavior goal model (HBG model; Maes & Gebhardt, 2000)	“The HBG model integrates aspects of expectancy-value, stage, and goal theories. ... The model has been developed to describe and predict the process of health behavior change” (Maes & Gebhardt, 2000, p. 357).	Action self-efficacy Outcome expectancies Risk perception Intention Coping self-efficacy Action planning Coping planning Recovery self-efficacy Action initiation & maintenance Self-monitoring (action control) Environmental characteristics Social influence Health costs & benefits Emotional costs & benefits Personal characteristics Perceived competence Lower/Higher order personal goals Actual health behaviour Target health behaviour

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Health behavior internalization model (HBIM; Bellg, 2003)	HBIM is proposed to describe motivational factors associated with internalization processes and hypothesizes that integrated internalization may be associated with long-term health behavior maintenance (Bellg, 2003, p. 103).	Precontemplation stage, contemplation stage, initial behaviour change stage, and maintenance stage. Self needs: identity (ownership), self-determination, security, and support. Behavior-related needs: preference, context, competence, and coping. Internalization and self-regulation of new health behavior Health behavior maintenance
Health promotion model (HPM; Heydari & Khorashadizadeh, 2014; Khoshnood et al., 2018)	The model focuses on the following three areas: individual characteristics and experiences, behavior-specific cognitions and affect, and immediate behavioral contingencies (Heydari & Khorashadizadeh, 2014, p. 1067).	Prior-related behavior Personal factor: biological, psychological, and sociocultural. Perceived benefits of action Perceived barriers to action Perceived self-efficacy Activity-related affect Interpersonal influences Situational influences Commitment to a plan of action Immediate competing demands and preferences Health promoting behavior
Health-related model of behaviour change (Hunt & Martin, 1988)	“It seems reasonable to assume that change growing out of some ‘natural’ cognitive reorganisation on the part of the subject will be longer-lasting than that	“Natural” cognitive reorganisation

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
	which is, as it were, imposed artificially from without” (Hunt & Martin, 1988, p. 227).	
Heuristic model for teachable moments (TM; McBride et al., 2003)	This model is a theoretical framework that suggests individuals are more receptive to health-related information and behavior change interventions during critical life events or “teachable moments,” such as medical diagnoses or significant life transitions. The theory proposes that these moments create a heightened state of readiness for change, making individuals more open to adopting healthier behaviors and seeking relevant information (McBride et al., 2003).	Emotion Perceived risk Outcome expectancies Self-concept Social role Motivation Acquisition of skills Self-efficacy Behavior (eg. smoking cessation)
Information-Motivation-Behavioural Skills Model (IMB model; Fisher & Fisher, 2003; Fisher et al., 2003; Hodges et al., 2020)	The model focuses on information, motivation, and behavioral skills that affect health behavior change.	Health behavior motivation Health behavior information (e.g., specific facts, heuristics, and implicit theories) Health behavior skills: perceived abilities. Health behavior skills: objective ability. Health behavior
Implementation intentions (Gollwitzer, 1999; Lachman et al., 2018)	Implementation intentions focus on forming an “if-then plan” in advance that can lead to effective behavior change by increasing self-efficacy (confidence in one’s ability to exercise) and control (beliefs about self-control).	Implementation intentions
Implicit theories (Dweck, 1996, 2012; Dweck et al., 1995)	This research found that one type of belief about human nature—the belief that fundamental human attributes are fixed traits or that they are malleable	Beliefs (about the nature of human attributes) Intelligence or personality

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Integrated behavior change model (Hagger & Chatzisarantis, 2014)	<p>qualities that can be developed—has profound consequences on how people function, how they relate to others, and what they achieve (Dweck, 2012, p. 1).</p> <p>“The model integrates hypotheses from social-cognitive, motivational, dual-phase, dual-systems theories” (Hagger & Chatzisarantis, 2014, p. 62).</p>	<p>Autonomous motivation</p> <p>Implicit motivation</p> <p>Attitude (from the Theory of Planned Behavior)</p> <p>Subjective norm</p> <p>Perceived behavioral control</p> <p>Intention</p> <p>Implicit attitudes</p> <p>Action planning</p> <p>Behavior</p>
Integrated Theory of Health Behavior Change (ITHBC; Ryan, 2009)	<p>“The Integrated Theory of Health Behavior Change suggests that health behavior change can be enhanced by fostering knowledge and beliefs, increasing self-regulation skills and abilities, and enhancing social facilitation” (Ryan, 2009, p. 161).</p>	<p>Knowledge & beliefs</p> <p>Condition specific knowledge</p> <p>Personal perceptions: self-efficacy, outcome expectancy, and goal congruence.</p> <p>Self-regulation skill and ability</p> <p>Goal setting</p> <p>Self-monitoring & Reflective thinking</p> <p>Decision making</p> <p>Planning and plan enactment</p> <p>Self-evaluation</p> <p>Management of emotional response</p> <p>Social facilitation</p>

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
		Social influence Social support: emotional, instrumental, and informational. Engagement in self-management behavior Health status
Integrative conceptual model of spiritual mechanisms underlying substance abuse behaviour change (Neff & MacMaster, 2005)	“A framework for viewing substance abuse treatment and change in substance abuse behaviours during treatment” (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Individual attributes: initial level of spirituality and initial treatment readiness. Program elements: empathy, acceptance, forgiveness, discipline (related lifestyles), norms, and support. Social learning process: role modeling and social reinforcement. Spiritual transformation process Readiness: enhanced behavioral intention and movement through stages of change. Behavior change
Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)	This model is a comprehensive model combined with McGuire’s information-processing model, health-belief model, Rogers’ model of communication effects, theory of reasoned action, social learning theory, and other theories. In order to help in the design of better programs and in the identification of mediating variables to be assessed during evaluation.	Beliefs (The formation process includes exposure, awareness and knowledge, and affects the formation of attitude.) Information Attention Comprehension Acceptance Other information Attitudes: evaluations × expectancies. General values

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Internet intervention model (Ritterband et al., 2009)	The model is proposed to help guide Internet intervention development and predict and explain behavior changes and symptom improvement produced by Internet intervention (Ritterband et al., 2009, p. 18).	Consistency Social normative beliefs (i.e., social norms, influences, or pressures) Available materials Available behavioral alternatives Self-efficacy Reinforcements Intentions Trial behavior Repeated behavior Self-image/Personality Family influences Peer influences Physiological reaction User characteristics: disease, demographics, traits, cognitive factors, beliefs and attitudes, physiological factors, and skills. Environment Website Website use Support Mechanisms of change Behavior change Symptom improvement Treatment maintenance

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Janis and Mann's theory of conflict (Janis & Mann, 1968)	This theory views the decision-making process as a sequence of stages that start with attitude changes induced by challenging information that motivates and constitutes the current policy (Janis & Mann, 1968, p. 328).	Decision-making process
Kelman's social influence theory (Kelman, 1958, 1974)	This theory proposes that others influence an individual's attitudes, beliefs, and subsequent behaviors through three processes: compliance, identification, and internalization.	Social influence
Life crises and the process of reinvention theory (Epiphanou & Ogden, 2010; Ogden & Hills, 2008)	This theory focuses on the sustained behavior change triggered by a significant life crisis relating to health, relationships, or salient milestones (Ogden & Hills, 2008, p. 419).	Life crises Sustaining conditions Identity
Life-span theory (Heckhausen & Schulz, 1995; Schulz & Heckhausen, 1996)	Behaviors undergoes systematic shifts across the life course in response to the opportunities and constraints encountered, targeting at external environment or internal processes (Heckhausen & Schulz, 1995).	Motivation Emotion Primary control Secondary control
Maintain IT (identity transformation) model (Caldwell et al., 2018)	The Maintain IT model posits that a centered identity transformation is one path leading to less effortful processing and facilitating successful recruitment of EF(executive function) when necessary over the long term, increasing the sustainability of health behavior change (Caldwell et al., 2018, p. 231).	Centered identity: role-based identity, group-based identity, behavior-based identity, and personal values. Executive function: working memory, inhibition, and shifting. Perceptual lens (It refers to attributional or explanatory style, implicit theory)

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
		surrounding behaviour and identity change.) Psychological well-being Health behaviors
McGuire's information processing model (Flay et al., 1980)	The model suggested a "persuasion matrix" as a way of conceptualizing the change process and understanding the complexities of the relationships between outcomes (changes in knowledge, attitudes, and behavior) and inputs (the persuasive communication and its properties; Flay et al., 1980, p. 129).	Information processing
Model of behaviour maintenance (Rothman, 2000, 2004; Rothman et al., 2011)	The model proposed that the decision to maintain a behavior depends on people's perceived satisfaction with received outcomes (Rothman, 2000).	Perceived satisfaction
Model of human occupation (Kielhofner, 2002)	A model of human volition, habituation, and performance capacity.	Person: human volition, habituation, and performance capacity. Environment Occupation (related to identity)
Multiple domain model (MDM; Zimmerman et al., 2007)	A comprehensive multiple domain model (MDM) to understand condom use in adolescents (Zimmerman et al., 2007, p. 380).	Social structural/Demographic variables Personality/Individual difference Social environmental Attitudes Norms Self-efficacy Intentions Situational/Contextual

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Multi-theory model (MTM; Dokun-Mowete et al., 2019; Sharma, 2015; Sharma et al., 2016)	Multi-theory model is a theoretical and conceptual framework derived from existing theories such as the health belief model, the transtheoretical model, the PRECEDE-PROCEED model, and the ecological models (Dokun-Mowete et al., 2019, p. 246).	Preparatory behaviors Behavior Participatory dialogue Behavioral confidence Changes in physical environment Emotional transformation Practice for change Changes in social environment Initiation/One-time behavior change Sustenance/Long term behavior change
Network-Individual-Resource (NIR) model (Johnson et al., 2010)	A model for HIV prevention that recognizes how exchanges of resources between individuals and their networks underlie and sustain HIV-risk behaviors (Johnson et al., 2010, p. 204).	Network Individual Resource: mental resource and tangible resource.
Optimistic bias (Weinstein, 1980)	Optimistic bias is a cognitive bias where individuals tend to believe that they are less likely to experience negative events and more likely to experience positive events compared to others. This bias leads people to underestimate their personal risk of adverse outcomes, such as health risks or negative life events, while overestimating the likelihood of positive outcomes (Weinstein, 1980).	Optimistic bias
Peplau's theory of interpersonal relations (Hagerty et al., 2017)	"In the theory of interpersonal relations in nursing, Peplau emphasized patients' experiences and the effect that nurse-patient relationships have on those experiences" (Hagerty et al., 2017, p. 161).	Nurse-patient relationships

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Perceptual Control Theory (PCT; Powers et al., 2011)	“Perceptual Control Theory (PCT) provides a general theory of functioning for organisms. At the conceptual core of the theory is the observation that living things control the perceived environment by means of their behavior” (Powers et al., 2011, p. 18).	Controlling system: input function, comparator, output function, perceptual signal, reference signal, and error signal. Environment: feedback function, output quantity, input quantity, and disturbance.
Personality theory (Secord & Backman, 1961)	This theory emphasizes how personality traits and dynamics interact with social and environmental factors, influencing how individuals behave and respond in various situations. The theory explores how personal characteristics and social interactions shape behavior, highlighting the interplay between individual attributes and external contexts (Secord & Backman, 1961).	Interpersonal matrix: self-concept, interpretation of own behavior, and perception of other's behavior. Interpersonal processes
Possible selves theory (Markus & Nurius, 1986)	The theory of possible selves proposes that we are motivated in our present life by mental images of possible future selves.	Possible selves
PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)	“The system as a whole is captured by the acronym PRIME, which stands for plans, responses, impulses, motives and evaluations” (West & Brown, 2013, p. 195).	External environment Stimuli (from our senses and our memory) Information (from our senses and our memory) Internal environment percepts Identity (frame of mine) Arousal Emotional states: generalized and targeted. Drives (e.g., hunger) Plans (intentions)

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
		Evaluations (beliefs) Motives (wants) Impulses (urges)/Inhibitions Responses Past experience influence: habituation/sensitisation, explicit memory, associative learning, and imitation learning. Personal rules
Problem Behaviour Theory (PBT; Jessor, 2014; Lerner et al., 2013; Mckellar & Sillence, 2020; Tremblay & Frigon, 2004)	“Problem behavior theory (PBT) is a social-psychological framework that helps to explain the development and nature of problem behaviors, for example, risky sex or alcohol use” (Mckellar & Sillence, 2020, p. 9).	Personality system Perceived environment system Demography-social structure Socialization Behaviour system
Process model for lifestyle behavior change (PMLBC; Greaves et al., 2010; Gillison et al., 2015)	A modified version of the Health Action Process Approach (Gillison et al., 2015, p. 2).	Stage: motivation, action, maintenance. Understand the process Explore & Enhance the motivation Engage social support Decision to act Plan action Action self-monitor progress Review progress and motivation Manage setbacks Habit
Prototype willingness model (Gerrard et al., 2008)	“The prototype willingness model is a modified dual-processing model that was created in an attempt to	Previous behavior Attitudes

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
	improve the predictive value of existing (analytic) health behavior theories, specifically with regard to adolescent health behaviors, by combining elements of existing health behavior theories with heuristic approaches to decision making” (Gerrard et al, 2008, p. 35).	Subjective norms Risk images Behavioral intention Behavioral willingness Risk behavior Context Media Temperament Self-control Heuristic
Reactance theory (Miron & Brehm, 2006)	“Reactance is a motivational state, it possesses energizing properties that drive individuals to engage in freedom-restoration behaviors” (Miron & Brehm, 2006, p.10).	Motivation (e.g., autonomy and freedom)
Reflective-impulsive model (Strack & Deutsch, 2004)	“A dual process model including a reflective system and an impulsive system” (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Perception Imagination Pointing & referring Propositional categorization Reasoning 1 Noetic decision (e.g., factual and evaluative) Reasoning 2 Behavioral decision Intending Associative store Behavioral schemata Behavior

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Regulatory fit/focus theory (Higgins, 1997, 2005; Veazie & Qian, 2011)	Two unique systems of self-regulation underpin human behavior and motivation: promotion focus and prevention focus.	Promotion focus Prevention focus
Relapse prevention model (Hendershot et al., 2011; Marlatt & Donovan, 2005; Marlatt & George, 1984)	“Relapse Prevention (RP) is a self-control programme designed to teach individuals who are trying to change their behaviour how to anticipate and cope with the problem of relapse” (Marlatt & George, 1984, p. 261).	High-risk situation Coping response Self-efficacy Probability of relapse Positive expectancies Self-control strategies: skill-training, cognitive reframing, and lifestyle intervention. Abstinence violation effect (a psychological response)
Revision and persistence (Vancouver & Kendall, 2006; Vancouver et al., 2002)	The efforts to directly influence self-efficacy beliefs may alter the calibration of those beliefs and, thus, the ability of the individual to properly self-regulate preparatory activities (Vancouver & Kendall, 2006, p. 1152).	Self-efficacy
Risk as feelings model (Loewenstein et al., 2001)	The risk-as-feelings hypothesis highlights the role of affect experienced at the moment of decision making and behavior (Loewenstein et al., 2001).	Anticipated outcomes (including anticipated emotions) Subjective probabilities Other factors: vividness, immediacy, and background mood. Cognitive evaluation Feelings Behavior

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Risk, attitude, norm, ability, and self-regulation model (RANAS; Mosler, 2012)	The RANAS model was developed by integrating key factors from established psychological theories. It aims to provide a comprehensive framework for systematically identifying, measuring and changing relevant behavioral factors in order to design effective behavior change interventions, especially in the water, sanitation and hygiene sectors in developing countries (Mosler, 2012).	<p>Outcomes (include emotions)</p> <p>Risk factors: perceived vulnerability, perceived severity, and factual knowledge.</p> <p>Attitude factors: instrumental beliefs and affective beliefs.</p> <p>Norm factors: descriptive norm, injunctive norm, and personal norm.</p> <p>Ability factors: action knowledge, self-efficacy, maintenance self-efficacy, and recovery self-efficacy.</p> <p>Self-regulation factors: Action control/planning, coping planning, remembering, and commitment.</p> <p>Intention</p> <p>Habit</p> <p>Behavior</p>
Rotter's social learning theory (Rotter, 1982)	The theory's main idea is that personality represents an interaction of the individual with his or her environment. To understand behavior, one must take both the individual and the environment into account.	<p>Behavior potential</p> <p>Expectancy</p> <p>Reinforcement value</p> <p>Psychological situation</p> <p>Locus of control</p>
Rubicon model of action phases (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2007, 2008; Heckhausen, 2007)	"The model describes successful goal pursuit as solving four consecutive tasks: choosing between potential goals, planning the implementation of a chosen goal, acting on the chosen goal, and assessing what has been achieved by acting on the	<p>Motivation</p> <p>Intention</p> <p>Volition</p> <p>Predecisional phase (deliberation)</p> <p>Postdecisional phase (planning)</p>

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
	goal and what still needs to be achieved by further acting on the goal” (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2007, p. 769).	Actional phase (action) Postactional phase (evaluation)
Salutogenic model (Antonovsky, 1996)	A model of a salutogenic orientation as the basis for health promotion (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Sense of coherence
Self-affirmation theory (Steele, 1988)	Self-affirmation theory proposes that people are motivated to protect their overall self-integrity, and will respond to threats to the self through affirming valued aspects of the self in order to restore self-worth. This theory views self-affirmation as a process that enables adaptive responses to threats by bolstering one’s global sense of self-integrity (Steele, 1988).	Self-integrity Self-affirmation
Self-concept theory (Bracken, 1996)	“A theory of self-perception” (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Self-concept
Self-determination theory (SDT; Deci & Ryan, 2002, 2010; Gaggioli et al., 2017; Ryan & Deci, 2000)	“The main focus of self-determination theory is on the investigation of innate psychological needs and inherent growth tendencies that form the basis of self-motivation and integration of personality” (Gaggioli et al., 2017, p. 485).	Autonomy Competence Relatedness Self-regulation of extrinsic motivation
Self-efficacy theory (Bandura, 1977a)	“This theory states that psychological procedures, whatever their form, alter the level and strength of self-efficacy” (Bandura, 1977a, p. 191).	Self-efficacy

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Self-perception theory (Bem, 1967, 1972)	“A theory of self-attitudes” (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Motivation Attitude Emotion Self-perception
Self-regulation theory (Kanfer & Gaelick-Buys, 1991; Kanfer & Kanfer, 1991; Parvin, 2013)	“Self-regulation refers to the intrapersonal processes by which an individual exercises control over the direction, persistence, and intensity of thinking, affect, and behavior for the purpose of goal attainment” (Kanfer & Kanfer, 1991, p. 291).	Self-regulation
Self-schemata theory (Markus, 1977)	This theory puts forward the concept of self-schemata, which can be considered cognitive generalizations about the self, and can be used to organize, summarize, and explain behavior along a particular dimension (Markus, 1977, p. 75).	Self-schemata
Situating learning theory (Besar, 2018; O’Brien & Battista 2020)	“Situating learning theory holds that effective education requires learning that is embedded in authentic contexts of practice” (Besar, 2018, p. 49).	Contexts
Social action theory (Ewart, 1991)	“Social action theory offers an integrative action schema for defining public health goals and identifying modifiable personal and social-contextual influences that can be activated to encourage self-protective activities” (Ewart, 1991, p. 942).	Motivational appraisal: outcome expectancies, self-efficacy, and goal structures. Problem solving (making plan or strategies) Generative capabilities Settings: physical, task (routinely performed), and social. Relationship systems Organizational systems

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
		Mood/Arousal Temperament Biological conditions Social interaction processes (social capabilities) Social interdependence Health protective action Outcomes
Social action theory (Weber, 2009)	This theory proposes that social behavior is guided by subjective motives and meanings, with four types of action: two rational (instrumentally and value rational) and two social (affectual and traditional; Weber, 2009).	Four types of social action
Social change theory (Anderson et al., 2002)	“A theory for changing community norms about health related behaviour” (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Community
Social comparison and social identity (Turner, 1975)	This study presents an explanation of intergroup discrimination “in terms of the operation of social comparison processes between groups based on the need for a positive ingroup identity” (Turner, 1975, p. 5).	Social comparison Social identity
Social comparison theory (Festinger, 1954)	This theory posits that individuals assess themselves by comparing with others, influencing behavior and self-perception. It highlights the role of social context and comparisons in shaping actions and choices (Festinger, 1954).	Comparison Unidirectional drive upward

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Social consensus model of health education (Romer & Hornik, 1992)	“A model of social consensus in behaviour change for HIV prevention” (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Social consensus
Social constructivist perspective (Burr, 2015)	It is a theoretical orientation that asserts that humans make and remake the world through social interactions and relationships (Burr, 2015).	Social interactions
Social contextual model of health behavior change (SCM; Sorensen et al., 2003)	This model is a theory that emphasizes the influence of social factors on health behaviors, particularly in working-class and multiethnic populations. This model suggests that interventions targeting health behaviors should consider the broader social context and its impact on individual choices, aiming to improve health outcomes within diverse and socioeconomically challenged communities (Sorensen et al., 2003).	<p>Socio-demographic characteristics</p> <p>Modifying conditions: individual level, interpersonal level, organizational level, neighborhood/community level, and societal level.</p> <p>Mediating mechanisms societal context: social norms, social support, and organizational environment.</p> <p>Mediating mechanisms individual factors: self-efficacy, attitudes/beliefs, intentions to perform behavior, and skills.</p> <p>Health behaviors</p> <p>Policy</p> <p>Cancer morbidity and cancer mortality</p> <p>Culture</p>
Social determinants of health and environmental health promotion model (Schulz & Northridge, 2004)	A conceptual framework for environmental health promotion that considers dynamic social processes through which social and environmental inequalities—and associated health disparities—are	<p>Natural environment</p> <p>Macrosocial factors</p> <p>Inequalities</p> <p>Built environment</p> <p>Social context</p>

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
	produced, reproduced, and potentially transformed (Schulz & Northridge, 2004, p. 455).	Stressors Health behaviors Social integration Social support Health outcomes Well-being
Social ecology model of behaviour change (Panter-Brick et al., 2006)	This theory views behaviors as being influenced by multiple levels of social and environmental factors, with interventions needing to target the interactions between individuals and their social and physical environments in order to effectively promote behavior change (Panter-Brick et al., 2006).	Social contexts
Social identity theory (Leaper, 2011; Tajfel & Turner, 1979)	“Social identity theory addresses the ways that social identities affect people’s attitudes and behaviors regarding their ingroup and the outgroup” (Leaper, 2011, p. 362).	Social identity
Social impact theory (Latané, 1981)	“Any of the great variety of changes in physiological states and subjective feelings, motives and emotions, cognitions and beliefs, values and behavior, that occur in an individual, human, or animal, as a result of the real, implied or imagined presence or actions of other individuals” (Latané, 1981, p. 343).	Other individuals
Social norms theory (Berkowitz, 2004)	“It states that our behavior is influenced by incorrect perceptions of how other members of our social groups think and act” (Berkowitz, 2004, p. 4).	Social norms

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Socioemotional selectivity theory (SST; Carstensen et al., 1999)	Socioemotional selectivity theory claims that the perception of time plays a fundamental role in the selection and pursuit of social goals, including knowledge acquisition and emotion regulation (Carstensen et al., 1999).	Social motives Perception of time
Strength model of self-control (Baumeister et al., 1998; Baumeister et al., 2000; Muraven & Baumeister, 2000)	“A theory of self-regulation as a limited cognitive resource” (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, Appendix 3).	Self-regulation Resource
Supportive accountability model (Mohr et al., 2011)	This theory is proposed to understand how human support enhances adherence to eHealth interventions.	Motivation Human support Adherence Communications medium
Temporal self-regulation theory (Hall & Fong, 2007)	A theory based on the intention-behavior model focus on self-regulatory capacity, behavioral prepotency, temporal valuations, and ambient temporal contingencies.	Connectedness beliefs (outcome expectancies) Temporal valuations Behavioral prepotency Self-regulatory capacity Observed behavior Emotion Physical environment Social environment Intentions

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)	“The Theoretical Domains Framework (TDF) provides a broad list of the key determinants of health behaviour” (Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021, p. 6).	<p>Social/Professional role and identity: professional identity, professional role, social identity, identity, professional boundaries, professional confidence, group identity, leadership, and organisational commitment.</p> <p>Beliefs about capabilities: self-confidence, perceived competence, self-efficacy, perceived behavioural control, beliefs, self-esteem, empowerment, and professional confidence.</p> <p>Optimism: optimism, pessimism, unrealistic optimism, and identity.</p> <p>Beliefs about consequences: beliefs, outcome expectancies, characteristics of outcome expectancies, anticipated regret, and consequents.</p> <p>Reinforcement: rewards, incentives, punishment, consequents (related reinforcement), reinforcement, contingencies, and sanctions.</p> <p>Goals: goals (distal/proximal), goal priority, goal/target setting, goals (autonomous/controlled), action planning, and implementation intention.</p>

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
		<p>Memory, attention and decision processes: memory, attention, attention control, decision making, and cognitive overload/tiredness.</p> <p>Social influences: social pressure, social norms, group conformity, social comparisons, group norms, social support, power, intergroup conflict, alienation, group identity, and modelling.</p> <p>Environmental context and resources</p> <p>Knowledge</p> <p>Skills</p> <p>Emotion</p> <p>Intentions</p> <p>Behavioural regulation: self-monitoring, breaking habit, and action planning.</p>
Theory of Action control (Kuhl, 1984)	The Theory of Action Control is presented as a systems-oriented model that specifies the interactions between processes underlying motivation, volition/action control, and performance control (Kuhl, 1984).	<p>Motivation: choice motivation and control motivation.</p> <p>Volitional control</p> <p>Action control: selective attention, encoding control, emotion control, motivation control, environment control, and parsimonious information processing.</p> <p>Performance control</p>
Theory of gender and power (Connell, 2013)	The Theory of gender and power analyzes how social structures of gender inequality in division of labor,	<p>Gender</p> <p>Social structures</p>

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
	division of power, and cathexis interact to produce sexual inequality and gender and power imbalance (Wingood & DiClemente, 2000)	
Theory of interpersonal behaviour (TIB; Cheng et al., 2011; Moody & Siponen, 2013; Triandis, 1979)	<p>“The TIB includes the theory of reasoned action (TRA) and theory of planned behavior (TPB) concepts (i.e., attitudes, social influence, and intentions)” (Moody & Siponen, 2013, p. 322).</p> <p>“New factors are also included in this context, namely, emotional factors, habits, and different sources of social influence” (Moody & Siponen, 2013, p. 322).</p>	<p>Attitude: beliefs about outcomes and evaluation of outcomes.</p> <p>Social factors: norms, roles (sets of actions deemed appropriate for individuals occupying a given position within the group), and self-concept.</p> <p>Affect: emotions.</p> <p>Habits: frequency of past behaviour.</p> <p>Environment factors: facilitating conditions.</p> <p>Intention</p> <p>Behaviour</p>
Theory of normative social behavior (Rimal & Real, 2005)	The theory of normative social behavior includes three mechanisms (injunctive norms, outcome expectations, and group identity), which are hypothesized to moderate the influence of descriptive norms on behavior (Rimal & Real, 2005).	<p>Descriptive norms</p> <p>Injunctive norms</p> <p>Outcome expectations</p> <p>Group identity</p>
Theory of physical activity maintenance (Nigg et al., 2008)	This theory incorporates individual psychosocial variables (goal-setting, motivation, and self-efficacy) and contextual variables of the environment and life stress (triggers of relapse) to explain how and why people do and do not maintain	<p>Motivation</p> <p>Self-efficacy</p> <p>Goal-setting</p> <p>Life stress (triggers of relapse)</p> <p>Physical activity environment</p> <p>Physical activity maintenance</p>

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Theory of rational addiction (Becker & Murphy, 1988; Rogeberg, 2020)	physical activity long term (Nigg et al., 2008, p. 544). “At the heart of the theory is an assumption that rational individuals consider the delayed effects of addictive behaviors as well as their immediate rewards and risks” (Rogeberg, 2020, p. 184).	Rational choice
Two-factor theory of avoidance learning (Mowrer 1939; Michaella, 2010; Stasiewicz & Maisto, 1993)	This theory focuses on the interplay of classical and operational contingencies and, on this basis, explains avoidance conditioning (Michaella, 2010, p. 334).	Classical conditioning Operant conditioning Emotion
2 × 2 behaviour change matrix (Rothman et al., 2009)	“Decomposing action control and behavior change into a 2 (reflective, automatic) × 2 (initiation, maintenance) matrix offers a useful way of conceptualizing the various determinants of eating behavior and suggests that different intervention strategies will be needed to target particular processes during respective phases of behavior change” (Rothman et al., 2009, p. S4).	Reflective Automatic Initiation Maintenance
Utility theory (Fishburn, 1968)	“Utility theory is interested in people's preferences or values and with assumptions about a person's preferences that enable them to be represented in numerically useful ways” (Fishburn, 1968, p. 335).	Utility Preferences
Vested interest theory (Crano & Prislin, 1995; Sivacek & Crano, 1982)	This theory proposes that individuals' attitudes and behaviors are influenced by their perception of having a personal stake or vested interest in a particular issue or outcome (Crano & Prislin, 1995;	Vested interest Attitude

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
	Sivacek & Crano, 1982).	
Watson's model of caring (Lukose, 2011)	"Watson's theory of human caring focuses on holistic care and the authentic relationship between caregivers and patients" (Lukose, 2011, p. 27).	Relationship between caregivers and patients
Web of group-affiliations (Chayko, 2015)	"It outlines how group affiliations and social interactions develop and impact both the individual and the society" (Chayko, 2015, p. 1421).	Group-affiliations Social interactions

Note. The review mentioned in the table title is "Theoretical Explanations for Maintenance of Behavior Change: A Systematic Review of Behavior Theories" (Kwasnicka et al., 2016). The multiple databases mentioned in the table title include PubMed, MEDLINE, Embase, Cochrane Library, Web of Science, PsycINFO, PsycARTICLES, and CINAHL. To facilitate readers in searching and reading relevant literature, some different spellings (e.g., "behavior" and "behaviour," "organization" and "organisation") are consistent with the original references.

Table B2

Theories From the Glanz et al. (2008)

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Cognitive consistency theory (Harmon-Jones & Mills,	"Cognitive dissonance theory postulates that an underlying psychological tension is created when an	Attitudes Beliefs Behaviors

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
2019; Miller et al., 2015; Thompson et al., 2012)	individual's behavior is inconsistent with his or her thoughts and beliefs" (Thompson et al., 2012, p. 503).	Dissonance
Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM)	A theory of persuasion.	Central route Peripheral route
Health Belief Model (HBM; Kagee & Freeman, 2008)	"The Health Belief Model (HBM) hypothesizes that health-related behavior depends on the combination of several factors, namely, perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefits, perceived barriers, cues to action, and self-efficacy" (Kagee & Freeman, 2008, p. 363).	Demographics variables: age, gender, ethnicity, personality, socioeconomics, and knowledge. Perceived threat: perceived susceptibility and perceived severity. Perceived benefits Perceived barriers self-efficacy behaviors Cues to action
Heuristic Systematic Model	A theory of persuasion.	Heuristic processing Systematic processing
Integrated Behavior Model (IBM)	"Fishbein and colleagues have further expanded TRA [Theory of Reasoned Action] and TPB [Theory of Planned Behavior] to include components from other major behavioral theories and have proposed use of an Integrated Behavioral Model" (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 68).	Experiential attitude: feelings about behavior. Instrumental attitude: behavioral belief × evaluation. Subjective/Injunctive norm: normative belief (others' expectations) × motivation to comply. Descriptive norm: normative belief (other's behavior).

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
		Perceived behavioral control: control belief \times perceived power. Self-efficacy: self-efficacy belief. Intention to perform the behavior Environmental constraints Salience of the behavior Knowledge and skills to perform the behavior Habit Behavior Personality Attitudes towards targets Other individual difference variables Demographic variables
Multiattribute Utility Theory	“Multi-attribute utility theory is an extension of Utility theory developed to help decision-makers assign utility values, taking into consideration the decision-maker’s preferences, to outcomes by evaluating these in terms of multiple attributes and combining these individual assignments to obtain overall utility measures” (Mateo, 2012, p. 63).	Multi-attribute utility values
Operant learning theory (Skinner, 2014)	It’s a kind of learning theory. Voluntary behaviors are strengthened or weakened by the consequences that follow them.	Reinforcement
Precaution Adoption Process Model (PAPM)	“The Precaution Adoption Process Model (PAPM) seeks to identify all the stages involved when people	Unaware of issue Unengaged by issue

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
	commence health-protective behaviors and to determine the factors that lead people to move from one stage to the next” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 124).	Undecided about acting Decided to act Acting Maintenance Decided not to act
Prospect theory (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979; Latimer et al., 2007)	“Prospect Theory contributed to understanding message framing of the positive or negative consequences of a behavior” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 160).	Gain Loss
Protection motivation theory (PMT)	This theory explains the effect of fear appeal in communications on the audience’s attitude change.	Verbal persuasion Observational learning Personality variables Prior experience Threat appraisal: perceived severity, perceived vulnerability, intrinsic rewards, and extrinsic rewards. Coping appraisal: response efficacy, response costs, and self-efficacy. Adaptive response Maladaptive response Fear Protection motivation Action or inhibition of action
Social learning theory Social cognitive theory (SCT)	“Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) was first known as social learning theory. ... It was renamed Social Cognitive Theory when concepts from cognitive psychology were integrated to accommodate the	Behavioral factors: outcome expectations. Personal factors: knowledge, goal, and self-efficacy.

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
	growing understanding of human information processing capacities and biases that influence learning from experience, observation, and symbolic communication. ... SCT emphasizes reciprocal determinism in the interaction between people and their environments” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 170).	Environment factors: incentive motivation and facilitation. Reciprocal determinism Self-regulation Negative feedback system Anticipatory proactive system Moral disengagement Observational learning Reinforcement Vicarious experiences
Subjective expected utility theory (SEU; Shanteau et al., 2009)	“Subjective Expected Utility (SEU) is an approach to decision making under risk that allows for subjective evaluation of both the variables under consideration and the probabilities associated with them” (Shanteau et al., 2009, p. 1084).	Decision making under risk Value (loss and gain) Probability (related to outcome)
Transtheoretical Model (TTM) / Stages of Change	“The Transtheoretical Model (TTM) uses stages of change to integrate processes and principles of change across major theories of intervention, hence the name Transtheoretical” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 97).	Stages: precontemplation, contemplation, preparation, action, maintenance, and termination. Consciousness raising Dramatic relief Self-reevaluation Environmental reevaluation Self-liberation Helping relationships Counterconditioning Reinforcement management

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)	“TPB is an extension of the TRA and includes an additional construct: perceived control over performance of the behavior” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 68).	<p>Stimulus control</p> <p>Social liberation</p> <p>Decisional balance: pros and cons.</p> <p>Self-efficacy: confidence and temptation.</p> <hr/> <p>Demographic variables</p> <p>Attitudes towards targets (Targets are considered to be the negative health outcomes of the behavior.)</p> <p>Personality traits</p> <p>Other individual difference variables</p> <p>Attitude: behavioral beliefs × evaluations of behavioral outcomes.</p> <p>Subjective norm: normative beliefs × motivation to comply.</p> <p>Intention to perform the behavior</p> <p>Perceived control: control beliefs and perceived power.</p> <p>Behavior</p>
Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)	“The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) focus on theoretical constructs concerned with individual motivational factors as determinants of the likelihood of performing a specific behavior” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 68).	<p>Demographic variables</p> <p>Attitudes towards targets (Targets are considered to be the negative health outcomes of the behavior.)</p> <p>Personality traits</p> <p>Other individual difference variables</p> <p>Attitude: behavioral beliefs × evaluations of behavioral outcomes.</p>

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
		Subjective norm: normative beliefs × motivation to comply. Intention to perform the behavior Behavior
Transactional model of stress and coping	“The Transactional Model of Stress and Coping is a framework for evaluating processes of coping with stressful events” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 213).	Stressor Primary appraisal: perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, motivational relevance, and causal focus. Secondary appraisal: perceived control over outcomes, perceived control over emotions, and self-efficacy. Coping efforts: problem management (strategies) and emotional regulation. Meaning-based coping (an intervention technique not classified in Appendix C): positive reappraisal, revised goals, spiritual beliefs, and positive events. Moderators: dispositional coping styles and social support. Outcomes of coping (adaptation): emotional well-being, functional status, and health behaviors. Optimism
Unimodel	A theory of persuasion.	Information processing
Community and group models (theory set)	Four types of theories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • diffusion of innovations model 	Community and group

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • examples of community organization theories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Rothman’s typology ✓ models of collaborative empowerment and community-building practice <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ feminist and “women-centered” models • examples of media communication theories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ theories at the micro level <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ expectancy-value theories ▪ information processing theories ▪ integrated behavior model ▪ message effect theories and persuasion (such as sensation seeking and framing) ▪ social cognitive theory ✓ theories at the macro level • examples of organizational change theories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ interorganizational relations theory (IOR) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ community coalition action theory (CCAT; a specific type of interorganizational relationship) ✓ organizational development theory ✓ stage theory of organizational change 	
Ecological models of health behavior (theory set)	To avoid repeated assessing, the social cognitive theory and operant learning theory related to this set were not listed again.	
Daniel Stokols’ social ecology model for health	This model researches behavior from the perspective of the interaction between humans and the	Physical environments Social environments

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
promotion (Stokols et al., 1996)	multidimensional environment (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 469).	Personal attributes
Deborah Cohen and others' structural-ecological model	The model proposes four categories of structural influences on behavior: "(1) availability of protective or harmful consumer products, (2) physical structures (or physical characteristics of products), (3) social structures and policies, and (4) media and cultural messages" (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 469).	Availability of protective or harmful consumer products Physical structures Social structures Policies Media and cultural messages
Edwin Fisher and others' resources and skills for self-management model	This model is "based on integration of individuals' skills and choices with support they receive from the social environment, as well as physical and policy environments of communities" (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 469).	Skills Choices Physical environment Social environment Policy environment
Karen Glanz and others' model of community food environment	This model "proposes key constructs that affect eating behaviors: availability, price, placement, and promotion of foods, as well as nutrition information. Applies to restaurants and food stores" (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 469).	Food availability, price, placement, promotion of foods, and nutrition information.
Kenneth McLeroy and others' ecological model of health behavior	This model proposes "five sources of influence on health behaviors: intrapersonal factors, interpersonal processes and primary groups, institutional factors, community factors, and public policy" (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 469).	Intrapersonal factors Interpersonal process and primary groups Institutional factors Community factors Public policy

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Kurt Lewin's ecological psychology	"Ecological psychology' is the study of the influence of the outside environment on the person" (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 468).	Environment
Roger Barker's environmental psychology	"Behaviors could be predicted more accurately from the situations people are in than from their individual characteristics" (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 468).	Behavior settings
Rudolph Moos's social ecology	Four categories of environmental factors: physical setting, organizational setting, the "human aggregate," and "social climate" (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 468).	Physical settings Organizational settings Human aggregate Social climate: supportiveness of a social setting for a particular behavior.
Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)	"Triadic influence theory includes seven 'tiers' of 'causes' of behavior that range from very proximal to distal to ultimate, and three 'streams of influence' that flow through the seven 'tiers'" (Flay & Petraitis, 1994, p. 19).	Social situation Social bonding Others' behavior & attitude Motivation to comply Perceived norms Social normative beliefs Cultural environment Knowledge Values Expectancies Evaluations Attitudes Biology Personality Sense of self (self-concept)

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
Thomas Glass and Matthew McAtee's ecosocial model	The model "conceptualizes hierarchies of influences on behavior within biology and society, which has social and physical environment dimensions. Structural contingencies provide opportunities and constraints, and biological processes regulate expression of behavior" (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 468).	Social competence Self-determination Social skills Self-efficacy Decisions/Intentions Trial behavior Experiences Repeated behavior Closely-related behavior
Urie Bronfenbrenner's systems theory	Three levels of environmental influences: microsystem, mesosystem, and exosystem (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 468).	Microsystem Mesosystem Exosystem
Interpersonal communication (theory set)	Example of interpersonal communication theories: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a linguistic model of patient participation in care • a model of decision making • cognitive Model • consumerism • integrated Behavior Model (IBM) • integrative model of shared decision making • Mishel's uncertainty theory 	Interpersonal communication

Theory	Brief description	Key concepts
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • model of empathic understanding • model of relational topoi • paternalism • problematic integration theory • Roter and Hall's typology of provider-patient relationships • self-determination theory • three models of physician-patient relationships • Transtheoretical Model (TTM) / Stages of Change • uncertainty management theory • patient agency model 	
Social support and social networks related theories (theory set)	<p>“It is clear that the terms social network and social support do not connote theories per se. Rather, they are concepts that describe the structure, processes, and functions of social relationships” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 193). But some related theories have been used to explain the basic interpersonal processes, such as exchange theory (Hunter, 2015), attachment theory (Granqvist et al., 2020), and symbolic interactionism (Carter et al., 2015; Del Casino & Thien, 2009).</p>	Social support Social networks

Note. The book mentioned in the table title is *Health Behavior and Health Education* (Glanz et al., 2008). The references listed here are only from our additional search beyond this book. Please refer to the book for more comprehensive sources and richer references. To

facilitate readers in searching and reading relevant literature, some different spellings (e.g., “behavior” and “behaviour,” “organization” and “organisation”) are consistent with the original references.

Appendix C

Thematic Synthesis

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
1 Needs	Autonomy Competence Relatedness Drives (e.g., hunger) Self-determination 1 Self-integrity Self needs: identity (ownership) 1, self-determination, security, and support.	Self-determination theory (SDT; Deci & Ryan, 2002, 2010; Gaggioli et al., 2017; Ryan & Deci, 2000) PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013) Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994) Self-affirmation theory (Steele, 1988) Health behavior internalization model (HBIM; Bellg, 2003)
2 Motivation	Autonomous motivation Implicit motivation Brain: motivated brain (motivational system) Defensive motivation Protection motivation Explore & enhance the motivation Health behavior motivation Intrinsic motivation	Integrated behavior change model (Hagger & Chatzisarantis, 2014) Evo-Eco approach (Aunger & Curtis, 2014a) Extended parallel process model (EPPM; Witte, 1992) Process model for lifestyle behavior change (PMLBC; Greaves et al., 2010; Gillison et al., 2015) Information-Motivation-Behavioral Skills Model (IMB model; Fisher & Fisher, 2003; Fisher et al., 2003; Hodges et al., 2020) Cognitive evaluation theory (CET; Hoss, 1985)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Motivation	Conceptual model of psychosocial risk and protective factors for excessive gestational weight gain (Hill et al., 2013)
	Motivation	Evolved structure of human motivation (Aunger & Curtis, 2013)
	Motivation	Fogg Behavior Model (FBM; Fogg et al., 2003; Fogg, 2009a, 2009b)
	Motivation	Heuristic model for teachable moments (TM; McBride et al., 2003)
	Motivation	Rubicon model of action phases (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2007, 2008; Heckhausen, 2007)
	Motivation	Self-perception theory (Bem, 1967, 1972)
	Motivation	Supportive accountability model (Mohr et al., 2011)
	Motivation	Theory of physical activity maintenance (Nigg et al., 2008)
	Motivation	Life-span theory (Heckhausen & Schulz, 1995; Schulz & Heckhausen, 1996)
	Motivation: basic drives.	COM-B system (Michie et al., 2011)
	Motivation: choice motivation and control motivation.	Theory of action control (Kuhl, 1984)
	Motivation (e.g., autonomy and freedom)	Reactance theory (Miron & Brehm, 2006)
	Motivations	Dynamic social systems model (DSSM; Latkin et al., 2010)
	Motives (wants)	PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)
	Primary appraisal: motivational relevance	Transactional model of stress and coping

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
2.1 Volition	Protection motivation	Protection motivation theory (PMT)
	Unidirectional drive upward	Social comparison theory (Festinger, 1954)
	Social motives	Socioemotional selectivity theory (SST; Carstensen et al., 1999)
3 Psychological propensity of behavior	Human volition	Model of Human Occupation (Kielhofner, 2002)
	Volition	Rubicon model of action phases (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2007, 2008; Heckhausen, 2007)
	Volitional control	Theory of action control (Kuhl, 1984)
3.1 Intention	Behavioral intention	Health action model (HAM; Mazaheri & Heidarnia, 2015; Seaman, 2010; Tones, 1987; Vahedian-Shahroodi et al., 2019)
	Behavioral intention	Prototype willingness model (Gerrard et al., 2008)
	Behavior intention	BASNEF model (Heather, 2005; Momeni et al., 2020)
	Cognitive mediators: intention.	Environmental research framework for weight gain prevention (Kremers et al., 2006)
	Decisions/Intentions	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)
	Decision to act	Process model for lifestyle behavior change (PMLBC; Greaves et al., 2010; Gillison et al., 2015)
	Individual attributes: initial treatment readiness.	Integrative conceptual model of spiritual mechanisms underlying substance abuse behaviour change (Neff & MacMaster, 2005)
	Readiness: enhanced behavioral intention.	
	Intending	Reflective-impulsive model (Strack & Deutsch, 2004)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Intention	Health Action Process Approach (HAPA; Schwarzer, 1992, 2008, 2016b; Sniehotta et al., 2005)
	Intention	Habit and intention theory (Ouellette & Wood, 1998)
	Intention	Integrated behavior change model (Hagger & Chatzisarantis, 2014)
	Intention	Rubicon model of action phases (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2007, 2008; Heckhausen, 2007)
	Intention	Theory of interpersonal behaviour (TIB; Cheng et al., 2011; Moody & Siponen, 2013; Triandis, 1979)
	Intention Self-regulation factors: commitment (stronger than intention).	Risk, attitude, norm, ability, and self-regulation model (RANAS; Mosler, 2012)
	Intentions	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Intentions	Multiple Domain Model (MDM; Zimmerman et al., 2007)
	Intentions	Temporal self-regulation theory (Hall & Fong, 2007)
	Intentions	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)
	Intentions	Extended information processing model (Flay et al., 1980)
	Resistance	
	Intention state: precontemplation, contemplation, and preparation.	Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)
	Intention to perform the behavior	Integrated Behavior Model (IBM)
	Intention to perform the behavior	Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Mediating mechanisms individual factors: intentions to perform behavior.	Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)
	Psychological commitment (The decision to try to achieve a goal or perform a behavior and the decision to use a particular means.)	Social contextual model of health behavior change (SCM; Sorensen et al., 2003)
	Self-liberation (making a firm commitment to change)	Goal theory (Bagozzi, 1992)
3.1.1 Goal intention	Intention to perform means Moderators: goal commitment.	Transtheoretical Model (TTM) / Stages of Change
3.1.2 Implementation intention	Commitment to a plan of action (identification of specific strategies to do something)	Goal theory (Bagozzi, 1992)
	Goals: implementation intention.	Goal setting theory (Locke & Latham, 2002)
	Implementation intentions	Health promotion model (HPM; Heydari & Khorashadizadeh, 2014; Khoshnood et al., 2018)
	Plans (intentions)	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)
3.2 Willingness	Behavioral willingness	Implementation intentions (Gollwitzer, 1999; Lachman et al., 2018)
	Willingness to commit to new challenges	PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)
4 Perceived stimuli/needs	Controlling system: perceptual signal	Prototype willingness model (Gerrard et al., 2008)
	Input function (perception)	Goal setting theory (Locke & Latham, 2002)
	Perception	Perceptual Control Theory (PCT; Powers et al., 2011)
	Risk images 1 (when directly affecting the path of willingness-behavior)	Control theory (Carver & Scheier, 1982)
4.1 Perceived threat	Perceived risk	Reflective-impulsive model (Strack & Deutsch, 2004)
		Prototype willingness model (Gerrard et al., 2008)
		Heuristic model for teachable moments (TM; McBride)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Perceived susceptibility	et al., 2003) AIDS Risk Reduction Model (ARRM; Catania et al., 1990)
	Perceived threat: perceived susceptibility and perceived severity.	Health Belief Model (HBM; Kagee & Freeman, 2008)
	Perceived threat: severity/susceptibility.	Extended parallel process model (EPPM; Witte, 1992)
	Primary appraisal: perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, and causal focus.	Transactional model of stress and coping
	Representation of danger	Common-sense model of self-regulation (CSM; Leventhal et al., 2003; Leventhal et al., 2016)
	Risk factors: perceived vulnerability and perceived severity	Risk, attitude, norm, ability, and self-regulation model (RANAS; Mosler, 2012)
	Risk perception	Health Action Process Approach (HAPA; Schwarzer, 1992, 2008, 2016b; Sniehotta et al., 2005)
	Risk perceptions	Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)
	Subjective probabilities	Risk as feelings model (Loewenstein et al., 2001)
	Other factors: vividness.	
	Threat appraisal: perceived severity and perceived vulnerability.	Protection motivation theory (PMT)
5 Attitude-related	Attitudes	Cognitive consistency theory (Harmon-Jones & Mills, 2019; Miller et al., 2015; Thompson et al., 2012)
	Attitude	Self-perception theory (Bem, 1967, 1972)
	Beliefs (about the consequences of performing a behaviour and the value placed on each possible consequence)	BASNEF model (Heather, 2005; Momeni et al., 2020)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
5.1 Implicit attitude	<p>Beliefs (The formation process includes exposure, awareness and knowledge, and affects the formation of attitude.)</p> <p>Mediating mechanisms individual factors: attitudes/beliefs.</p> <p>Opinion/Belief</p> <p>Retention</p> <p>Risk factors: factual knowledge.</p> <p>User characteristics: beliefs and attitudes.</p> <p>Utility</p> <p>Preferences</p>	<p>Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)</p> <p>Social contextual model of health behavior change (SCM; Sorensen et al., 2003)</p> <p>Extended information processing model (Flay et al., 1980)</p> <p>Risk, attitude, norm, ability, and self-regulation model (RANAS; Mosler, 2012)</p> <p>Internet intervention model (Ritterband et al., 2009)</p> <p>Utility theory (Fishburn, 1968)</p>
5.1 Implicit attitude	<p>Automatic affective reactions (implicit attitude) 1</p> <p>Implicit attitudes</p>	<p>Dual process model of self-control (Friese et al., 2008; Hofmann et al., 2008)</p> <p>Integrated behavior change model (Hagger & Chatzisarantis, 2014)</p>
5.2 Explicit attitude	<p>Attitude</p> <p>Attitude (affective)</p> <p>Persistence</p> <p>Attitude: pros & cons and rational & emotional.</p> <p>Attitudes</p> <p>Attitude system</p>	<p>Vested interest theory (Crano & Prislin, 1995; Sivacek & Crano, 1982)</p> <p>Extended information processing model (Flay et al., 1980)</p> <p>Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)</p> <p>Belief systems theory (Grube et al., 1994)</p> <p>Health action model (HAM; Mazaheri & Heidarnia, 2015; Seaman, 2010; Tones, 1987; Vahedian-Shahroodi et al., 2019)</p>

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Attitudes towards targets	Integrated Behavior Model (IBM)
	Attitudes towards targets (Targets are considered to be the negative health outcomes of the behavior.)	Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)
	Behavior-related needs: preference.	Health behavior internalization model (HBIM; Bellg, 2003)
	Multi-attribute utility values	Multiattribute Utility Theory
	Probability (related to outcome)	Subjective expected utility theory (SEU; Shanteau et al., 2009)
	Value (loss and gain)	
5.2.1 Experiential attitude	Activity-related affect	Health promotion model (HPM; Heydari & Khorashadizadeh, 2014; Khoshnood et al., 2018)
	Affect toward means	Goal theory (Bagozzi, 1992)
	Attitude factors: affective beliefs.	Risk, attitude, norm, ability, and self-regulation model (RANAS; Mosler, 2012)
	Emotional costs & benefits	Health Behavior Goal Model (HBG model; Maes & Gebhardt, 2000)
	Emotional states: targeted.	PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)
	Enjoy/Pleasure 1 (related to leisure-time physical activity)	Groningen Active Living Model (GALM; Kwasnicka et al., 2016; Stevens et al., 1999)
	Experiential attitude: feelings about behavior.	Integrated Behavior Model (IBM)
	Feelings 1	Risk as feelings model (Loewenstein et al., 2001)
5.2.2 Instrumental attitude	Anticipated outcomes (including anticipated emotions)	Risk as feelings model (Loewenstein et al., 2001)
	Cognitive evaluation	

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Attitude: behavioral beliefs × evaluations of behavioral outcomes	Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)
	Attitude: beliefs about outcomes and evaluation of outcomes.	Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)
	Attitude factors: instrumental beliefs.	Theory of interpersonal behaviour (TIB; Cheng et al., 2011; Moody & Siponen, 2013; Triandis, 1979)
	Attitude (from the Theory of Planned Behavior)	Risk, attitude, norm, ability, and self-regulation model (RANAS; Mosler, 2012)
	Attitudes	Integrated behavior change model (Hagger & Chatzisarantis, 2014)
	Attitudes	BASNEF model (Heather, 2005; Momeni et al., 2020)
	Attitudes	Multiple domain model (MDM; Zimmerman et al., 2007)
	Attitudes	Prototype willingness model (Gerrard et al., 2008)
	Attitudes: evaluations × expectancies.	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Attitudes	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)
	Expectancies	
	Behavioral cost	Behavioral choice theory (Epstein, 1998; Lacey & Rachlin, 1978; Vlek, 1991)
	Behavioral factors: outcome expectations.	Social learning theory
		Social cognitive theory (SCT)
	Beliefs about consequences: beliefs, outcome expectancies, characteristics of outcome expectancies, anticipated regret, and consequents.	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Cognitive mediators: attitude.	Environmental research framework for weight gain prevention (Kremers et al., 2006)
	Connectedness beliefs (outcome expectancies)	Temporal self-regulation theory (Hall & Fong, 2007)
	Temporal valuations	
	Coping appraisal: response efficacy and response costs.	Protection motivation theory (PMT)
	Threat appraisal: intrinsic rewards and extrinsic rewards.	
	Costs and benefits: response efficacy (It refers to perceived instrumentality, which is a belief that one's actions will be effective and will have desired consequences.) and enjoyment.	AIDS Risk Reduction Model (ARRM; Catania et al., 1990)
	Decisional balance: pros and cons.	Transtheoretical Model (TTM) / Stages of Change
	Delay between choosing and receiving the alternatives (This can be regarded as an attribute of outcome expectancies.)	Behavioral choice theory (Epstein, 1998; Lacey & Rachlin, 1978; Vlek, 1991)
	Evaluations (beliefs)	PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)
	Expectancy	Rotter's social learning theory (Rotter, 1982)
	Expectancy 1 (It should not be thought of as just consciously recollected beliefs about the expected effects of drinking, but also associational structures in long-term memory.)	Alcohol expectancy theory (Christiansen et al., 1982; Davis et al., 2013; Jones et al., 2001)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Gain	Prospect theory (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979; Latimer et al., 2007)
	Loss	
	Health costs & benefits	Health Behavior Goal Model (HBG model; Maes & Gebhardt, 2000)
	Instrumental attitude: behavioral belief × evaluation.	Integrated Behavior Model (IBM)
	Instrumental beliefs	Goal theory (Bagozzi, 1992)
	Moderators: goal importance	Goal setting theory (Locke & Latham, 2002)
	Motivational appraisal: outcome expectancies.	Social action theory (Ewart, 1991)
	Outcome expectancies	Health Action Process Approach (HAPA; Schwarzer, 1992, 2008, 2016b; Sniehotta et al., 2005)
	Outcome expectancies	Heuristic model for teachable moments (TM; McBride et al., 2003)
	Outcome expectations	Theory of normative social behavior (Rimal & Real, 2005)
	Perceived benefits	Health Belief Model (HBM; Kagee & Freeman, 2008)
	Perceived benefits of action	Health promotion model (HPM; Heydari & Khorashadizadeh, 2014; Khoshnood et al., 2018)
	Personal perceptions: outcome expectancy.	Integrated Theory of Health Behavior Change (ITHBC; Ryan, 2009)
	Positive expectancies	Relapse prevention model (Hendershot et al., 2011; Marlatt & Donovan, 2005; Marlatt & George, 1984)
	Reasoned attitudes	Dual process model of self-control (Friese et al., 2008; Hofmann et al., 2008)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
6 Perceived social norm-related	Beliefs (beliefs about whether other people would wish a person to perform a behaviour and the influence of other people)	BASNEF model (Heather, 2005; Momeni et al., 2020)
	Context beliefs	Ford's motivational system theory (MST; Van Dellen, 2012)
	Mediating mechanisms societal context: social norms.	Social contextual model of health behavior change (SCM; Sorensen et al., 2003)
	Perceived norms	Dynamic social systems model (DSSM; Latkin et al., 2010)
	Program elements: norms.	Integrative conceptual model of spiritual mechanisms underlying substance abuse behaviour change (Neff & MacMaster, 2005)
	Social factors: norms and roles (sets of actions deemed appropriate for individuals occupying a given position within the group).	Theory of interpersonal behaviour (TIB; Cheng et al., 2011; Moody & Siponen, 2013; Triandis, 1979)
	Social influences: social norms and group norms.	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)
	Social normative beliefs (i.e., social norms, influences, or pressures)	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Social norms	AIDS Risk Reduction Model (ARRM; Catania et al., 1990)
	Social norms	Social norms theory (Berkowitz, 2004)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
6.1 Subjective/Injunctive norm	Cognitive mediators: subjective norm.	Environmental research framework for weight gain prevention (Kremers et al., 2006)
	Injunctive norms	Focus theory of normative conduct (Cialdini et al., 1990)
	Injunctive norms	Theory of normative social behavior (Rimal & Real, 2005)
	Motivation to comply	Integrated Behavior Model (IBM) Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)
	Motivation to comply	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)
	Perceived norms	
	Social normative beliefs	
	Normative system	Health action model (HAM; Mazaheri & Heidarnia, 2015; Seaman, 2010; Tones, 1987; Vahedian-Shahroodi et al., 2019)
	Social influences: norms.	Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)
	Subjective/Injunctive norm: normative belief (others' expectations) \times motivation to comply.	Integrated Behavior Model (IBM)
	Subjective norm	BASNEF model (Heather, 2005; Momeni et al., 2020)
	Subjective norm	Integrated behavior change model (Hagger & Chatzisarantis, 2014)
	Subjective norm: normative beliefs \times motivation to comply.	Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
6.2 Descriptive norm	Subjective norms	Prototype willingness model (Gerrard et al., 2008)
	Descriptive norm: normative belief (other's behavior).	Integrated Behavior Model (IBM)
	Descriptive norms	Focus theory of normative conduct (Cialdini et al., 1990)
	Descriptive norms	Theory of normative social behavior (Rimal & Real, 2005)
	Interpersonal matrix: perception of other's behavior.	Personality theory (Secord & Backman, 1961)
	Norm factors: descriptive norm.	Risk, attitude, norm, ability, and self-regulation model (RANAS; Mosler, 2012)
	Norms (How many of their friends used condoms when having sex.)	Multiple domain model (MDM; Zimmerman et al., 2007)
	Others' behavior & attitude	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)
	Risk image 2	Prototype willingness model (Gerrard et al., 2008)
7 Personal agency-related		
7.1 Perceived behavioral control	Cognitive mediators: perceived behavioral control.	Environmental research framework for weight gain prevention (Kremers et al., 2006)
	Intrapersonal component: perceived control.	Empowerment theory (Zimmerman, 1995)
	Perceived barriers	Health Belief Model (HBM; Kagee & Freeman, 2008)
	Perceived barriers to action	Health promotion model (HPM; Heydari & Khorashadizadeh, 2014; Khoshnood et al., 2018)
	Perceived behavioral control	Integrated behavior change model (Hagger & Chatzisarantis, 2014)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
7.2 Self-efficacy	Perceived behavioral control: control belief × perceived power.	Integrated Behavior Model (IBM)
	Perceived control: control beliefs and perceived power.	Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)
	Ability factors: self-efficacy, maintenance self-efficacy, and recovery self-efficacy.	Risk, attitude, norm, ability, and self-regulation model (RANAS; Mosler, 2012)
	Action self-efficacy	Health Action Process Approach (HAPA; Schwarzer, 1992, 2008, 2016b; Sniehotta et al., 2005)
	Coping self-efficacy	
	Recovery self-efficacy	
	Behavioral confidence	Multi-theory model (MTM; Dokun-Mowete et al., 2019; Sharma, 2015; Sharma et al., 2016)
	Beliefs about capabilities: self-confidence, perceived competence, self-efficacy, perceived behavioural control, beliefs, self-esteem, empowerment, and professional confidence.	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)
	Competence beliefs	Ford's motivational system theory (MST; Van Dellen, 2012)
	Coping appraisal: self-efficacy.	Protection motivation theory (PMT)
Health behavior skills: perceived abilities.	Information-Motivation-Behavioral Skills Model (IMB model; Fisher & Fisher, 2003; Fisher et al., 2003; Hodges et al., 2020)	
Intrapersonal component: self-efficacy and perceived competence.	Empowerment theory (Zimmerman, 1995)	

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Mediating mechanisms individual factors: self-efficacy.	Social contextual model of health behavior change (SCM; Sorensen et al., 2003)
	Moderators: self-efficacy	Goal setting theory (Locke & Latham, 2002)
	Motivational appraisal: self-efficacy.	Social action theory (Ewart, 1991)
	Perceived competence	Health Behavior Goal Model (HBG model; Maes & Gebhardt, 2000)
	Perceived efficacy	Extended parallel process model (EPPM; Witte, 1992)
	Perceived self-efficacy	Health promotion model (HPM; Heydari & Khorashadizadeh, 2014; Khoshnood et al., 2018)
	Personal factors: self-efficacy.	Social learning theory Social cognitive theory (SCT)
	Personal perceptions: self-efficacy.	Integrated Theory of Health Behavior Change (ITHBC; Ryan, 2009)
	Secondary appraisal: perceived control over outcomes, perceived control over emotions, and self-efficacy.	Transactional model of stress and coping
	Self-efficacies	Goal theory (Bagozzi, 1992)
	Self-efficacy	AIDS Risk Reduction Model (ARRM; Catania et al., 1990)
	Self-efficacy	Conceptual model of psychosocial risk and protective factors for excessive gestational weight gain (Hill et al., 2013)
	Self-efficacy	Groningen Active Living Model (GALM; Kwasnicka et al., 2016; Stevens et al., 1999)
	Self-efficacy	Health Belief Model (HBM; Kagee & Freeman, 2008)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Self-efficacy	Heuristic model for teachable moments (TM; McBride et al., 2003)
	Self-efficacy	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Self-efficacy	Multiple domain model (MDM; Zimmerman et al., 2007)
	Self-efficacy	Relapse prevention model (Hendershot et al., 2011; Marlatt & Donovan, 2005; Marlatt & George, 1984)
	Self-efficacy	Revision and persistence (Vancouver & Kendall, 2006; Vancouver et al., 2002)
	Self-efficacy	Self-efficacy theory (Bandura, 1977a)
	Self-efficacy	Theory of physical activity maintenance (Nigg et al., 2008)
	Self-efficacy	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)
	Self-efficacy: confidence and temptation. Self-efficacy: self-efficacy belief. Self-efficacy: social-, stress-, skills-, and routine self-efficacy.	Transtheoretical Model (TTM) / Stages of Change Integrated Behavior Model (IBM) Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)
8 Personal norm-related	Controlling system: reference signal. Goal conflict Goal contents Goal core	Perceptual Control Theory (PCT; Powers et al., 2011) Goal conflict model (Stroebe et al., 2007) Goal content theory (GCT; Deci & Ryan, 2000; Gunnell et al., 2014; Gill et al., 2021) Goal setting theory (Locke & Latham, 2002)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Moderators: task complexity. Goals: goals (distal/proximal), goal priority, and goals (autonomous/controlled). Lower/Higher order personal goals	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021) Health Behavior Goal Model (HBG model; Maes & Gebhardt, 2000)
	Motivational appraisal: goal structures. Norm factors: personal norm.	Social action theory (Ewart, 1991) Risk, attitude, norm, ability, and self-regulation model (RANAS; Mosler, 2012)
	Personal factors: goal.	Social learning theory Social cognitive theory (SCT)
	Personal goal	Ford's motivational system theory (MST; Van Dellen, 2012)
	Personal norms	Focus theory of normative conduct (Cialdini et al., 1990)
	Personal perceptions: goal congruence.	Integrated Theory of Health Behavior Change (ITHBC; Ryan, 2009)
	Personal rules	PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)
	Possible selves	Possible selves theory (Markus & Nurius, 1986)
	Reference value	Control theory (Carver & Scheier, 1982)
	Goal	
	Restraint standards	Dual process model of self-control (Friese et al., 2008; Hofmann et al., 2008)
9 Stimuli-related	Conditioned stimulus Controlling system: input function. Environment: input quantity, disturbance. Disturbance	Classical conditioning (Skinner, 2014) Perceptual Control Theory (PCT; Powers et al., 2011) Control theory (Carver & Scheier, 1982)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
9.1 Cues	Life stress (triggers of relapse) Message components Past experience influence: habituation/sensitisation (related with stimuli). Stimuli (from our senses and our memory) Prompt Salience of the behavior Situational stimuli (inner and outer) Stimulus control Stressor Stressors	Theory of physical activity maintenance (Nigg et al., 2008) Extended parallel process model (EPPM; Witte, 1992) PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013) Fogg Behavior Model (FBM; Fogg et al., 2003; Fogg, 2009a, 2009b) Integrated Behavior Model (IBM) Common-sense model of self-regulation (CSM; Leventhal et al., 2003; Leventhal et al., 2016) Transtheoretical Model (TTM) / Stages of Change Transactional model of stress and coping Social determinants of health and environmental health promotion model (Schulz & Northridge, 2004)
9.1 Cues	Cues to action Cues to action External motivators (cues)	Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005) Health Belief Model (HBM; Kagee & Freeman, 2008) AIDS Risk Reduction Model (ARRM; Catania et al., 1990)
10 Consciousness-dominant process	Acceptance Comprehension Consistency	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Action Control: parsimonious information processing.	Theory of action control (Kuhl, 1984)
	Adaptive response	Protection motivation theory (PMT)
	Maladaptive response	
	Brain: executive brain (executive control of behavior)	Evo-Eco approach (Aunger & Curtis, 2014a)
	Brain (process related)	Behaviour Centred Design (BCD; Aunger & Curtis, 2016; White et al., 2016)
	Central route	Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM)
	Cognitive impairments	Alcohol myopia theory (Steele & Josephs, 1990)
	Consciousness raising	Transtheoretical Model (TTM) / Stages of Change
	Episodic future thinking	Episodic future thinking (Schacter et al., 2017)
	Executive System (ES)	Context, executive, and operational systems theory (CEOS Theory; Borland, 2016)
	Exposure	Extended information processing model (Flay et al., 1980)
	Awareness	
	Information processing	Cognitive-Social Health Information-Processing Model (C-SHIP model; Mille et al., 1996; Shaw et al., 2008)
	Information processing	McGuire's information processing model (Flay et al., 1980)
	Information processing	Unimodel
	Internal environment percepts	PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)
	Internalization of new health behavior	Health behavior internalization model (HBIM; Bellg, 2003)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
10.1 Attribution	Motivation: reflective processes “Natural” cognitive reorganisation	COM-B system (Michie et al., 2011) Health-related model of behaviour change (Hunt & Martin, 1988)
	Person: awareness, involvement.	Environmental research framework for weight gain prevention (Kremers et al., 2006)
	Pointing & referring Propositional categorizaion	Reflective-impulsive model (Strack & Deutsch, 2004)
	Reasoning 1 Reasoning 2	
	Program elements: empathy, acceptance, and forgiveness.	Integrative conceptual model of spiritual mechanisms underlying substance abuse behaviour change (Neff & MacMaster, 2005)
	Reflective Social liberation: realizing that the social norms are changing in the direction of supporting the healthy behavior change.	2 × 2 behaviour change matrix (Rothman et al., 2009) Transtheoretical Model (TTM) / Stages of Change
	Systematic processing System 2: deliberate and analytical.	Heuristic Systematic Model Dual-Process Theory (Kahneman, 1973)
	Behavioral attribution	Attribution theory (Jones, 1976; Rubenstein & Thoron, 2017)
	Locus of control (beliefs about what determines whether or not they get reinforced in life)	Rotter’s social learning theory (Rotter, 1982)
	Moral disengagement	Social learning theory Social cognitive theory (SCT)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
10.2 Decision/Choice	Behavioral decision Noetic decision (e.g., factual and evaluative) Choice Choice among means Choices Decision making Decision making Decision making under risk Memory, attention and decision processes: decision making. Rational choice	Reflective-Impulsive model (Strack & Deutsch, 2004) Behavioral choice theory (Epstein, 1998; Lacey & Rachlin, 1978; Vlek, 1991) Goal theory (Bagozzi, 1992) Edwin Fisher and others' resources and skills for self-management model Habit and intention theory (Ouellette & Wood, 1998) Integrated Theory of Health Behavior Change (ITHBC; Ryan, 2009) Subjective expected utility theory (SEU; Shanteau et al., 2009) Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021) Theory of rational addiction (Becker & Murphy, 1988; Rogeberg, 2020)
10.3 Memory	Episodic memory Imagination Memory Memory, attention and decision processes: memory. Past experience influence: explicit memory Self-regulation factors: remembering	Episodic future thinking (Schacter et al., 2017) Reflective-Impulsive model (Strack & Deutsch, 2004) Extended information processing model (Flay et al., 1980) Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021) PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013) Risk, attitude, norm, ability, and self-regulation model (RANAS; Mosler, 2012)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
10.4 Reason	Reason (explicit, conscious)	Behavioural reasoning theory (Westaby, 2005)
10.5 Resources	Cognitive load	Dual process model of self-control (Friese et al., 2008; Hofmann et al., 2008)
	Ego depletion	
	Memory, attention and decision processes: cognitive overload/tiredness.	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)
	Resource	Strength model of self-control (Baumeister et al., 1998; Baumeister et al., 2000; Muraven & Baumeister, 2000)
10.6 Self-regulation		
10.6.1 General process	Control	Goal theory (Bagozzi, 1992)
	Manage setbacks	Process model for lifestyle behavior change (PMLBC; Greaves et al., 2010; Gillison et al., 2015)
	Performance control	Theory of action control (Kuhl, 1984)
	Promotion focus	Regulatory fit/focus theory (Higgins, 1997, 2005; Veazie & Qian, 2011)
	Prevention focus	
	Secondary control	Life-span theory (Heckhausen & Schulz, 1995; Schulz & Heckhausen, 1996)
	Self-affirmation	Self-affirmation theory (Steele, 1988)
	Self-control	Prototype willingness model (Gerrard et al., 2008)
	Self-regulation	Context, executive, and operational systems theory (CEOS Theory; Borland, 2016)
	Self-regulation	Self-regulation theory (Kanfer & Gaelick-Buys, 1991; Kanfer & Kanfer, 1991; Parvin, 2013)
	Self-regulatioin	Social learning theory Social cognitive theory (SCT)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Self-regulation	Strength model of self-control (Baumeister et al., 1998; Baumeister et al., 2000; Muraven & Baumeister, 2000)
	Self-regulation of new health behavior	Health behavior internalization model (HBIM; Bellg, 2003)
	Spiritual transformation process	Integrative conceptual model of spiritual mechanisms underlying substance abuse behaviour change (Neff & MacMaster, 2005)
	Trait self-control	Dual process model of self-control (Friese et al., 2008; Hofmann et al., 2008)
10.6.2 Self-monitoring	Action control: selective attention.	Theory of action control (Kuhl, 1984)
	Action self-monitor progress	Process model for lifestyle behavior change (PMLBC; Greaves et al., 2010; Gillison et al., 2015)
	Attention	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Behavioural regulation: self-monitoring. Memory, attention and decision processes: attention control and attention.	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)
	Focus of attention	Focus theory of normative conduct (Cialdini et al., 1990)
	Locus of attention	Feedback intervention theory (FIT; Kluger & DeNisi, 1996)
	Monitoring activities	Goal theory (Bagozzi, 1992)
	Self-monitoring	Integrated Theory of Health Behavior Change (ITHBC; Ryan, 2009)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Self-monitoring (action control)	Health Action Process Approach (HAPA; Schwarzer, 1992, 2008, 2016b; Sniehotta et al., 2005)
10.6.3 Judgment process	Appraisal	Common-sense model of self-regulation (CSM; Leventhal et al., 2003; Leventhal et al., 2016)
	Comparator	Control theory (Carver & Scheier, 1982)
	Controlling system: comparator and error signal.	Perceptual Control Theory (PCT; Powers et al., 2011)
	Evaluations	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)
	Review progress and motivation	Process model for lifestyle behavior change (PMLBC; Greaves et al., 2010; Gillison et al., 2015)
	Self-evaluation	Integrated Theory of Health Behavior Change (ITHBC; Ryan, 2009)
	Self-reevaluation	Transtheoretical Model (TTM) / Stages of Change
10.6.4 Self-reaction	Perceived satisfaction	Model of behaviour maintenance (Rothman, 2000, 2004; Rothman et al., 2011)
	Satisfaction with performance and rewards	Goal setting theory (Locke & Latham, 2002)
10.6.5 Self-reflective	Reflective thinking	Integrated Theory of Health Behavior Change (ITHBC; Ryan, 2009)
10.6.6 Feedback	Feedback	Feedback intervention theory (FIT; Kluger & DeNisi, 1996)
	Feedback loop	Common-sense model of self-regulation (CSM; Leventhal et al., 2003; Leventhal et al., 2016)
	Feedback loop	Control theory (Carver & Scheier, 1982)
	Moderators: feedback	Goal setting theory (Locke & Latham, 2002)
	Negative feedback system	Social learning theory

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
10.6.7 Goal guidance/setting	Goal mechanisms: choice/direction (direct attention and effort toward goal-relevant activities and away from goal-irrelevant activities).	Social cognitive theory (SCT) Goal setting theory (Locke & Latham, 2002)
	Goal setting	Integrated Theory of Health Behavior Change (ITHBC; Ryan, 2009)
	Goal-setting	Theory of physical activity maintenance (Nigg et al., 2008)
	Goals: goal/target setting.	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)
10.6.8 Planning	Guidance	Goal theory (Bagozzi, 1992)
	Action planning	Integrated behavior change model (Hagger & Chatzisarantis, 2014)
	Action planning	Coping planning (Sniehotta et al., 2005)
	Coping planning	Health Action Process Approach (HAPA; Schwarzer, 1992, 2008, 2016b; Sniehotta et al., 2005)
	Action planning	Common-sense model of self-regulation (CSM; Leventhal et al., 2003; Leventhal et al., 2016)
	Coping planning	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)
	Action plans	Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)
Behavioural regulation: action planning.	Goal: action planning.	
Implementation plans		

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
10.6.9 Plans/Strategies	Plan action	Process model for lifestyle behavior change (PMLBC; Greaves et al., 2010; Gillison et al., 2015)
	Planning	Goal theory (Bagozzi, 1992)
	Planning and plan enactment	Integrated Theory of Health Behavior Change (ITHBC; Ryan, 2009)
	Problem solving (making plan or strategies)	Social action theory (Ewart, 1991)
	Self-regulation factors: action control/planning and coping planning	Risk, attitude, norm, ability, and self-regulation model (RANAS; Mosler, 2012)
	Available alternatives	Behavioral choice theory (Epstein, 1998; Lacey & Rachlin, 1978; Vlek, 1991)
	Available behavioral alternatives	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Behavior-related needs: coping (strategies).	Health behavior internalization model (HBIM; Bellg, 2003)
	Coping efforts: emotional regulation (strategies) 2.	Transactional model of stress and coping
	Coping efforts: problem management (strategies) 1.	
10.6.10 Emotional regulation	Dispositional coping styles	
	Coping procedures	Common-sense model of self-regulation (CSM; Leventhal et al., 2003; Leventhal et al., 2016)
	Goal mechanisms: strategies	Goal setting theory (Locke & Latham, 2002)
	Action Control: emotion control. 1	Theory of action control (Kuhl, 1984)
	Coping efforts: emotional regulation 1.	Transactional model of stress and coping

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Emotional transformation 1	Multi-theory model (MTM; Dokun-Mowete et al., 2019; Sharma, 2015; Sharma et al., 2016)
	Management of emotional response	Integrated Theory of Health Behavior Change (ITHBC; Ryan, 2009)
10.6.11 Cognitive regulation	Action Control: encoding control. Self-control strategies: cognitive reframing.	Theory of action control (Kuhl, 1984) Relapse prevention model (Hendershot et al., 2011; Marlatt & Donovan, 2005; Marlatt & George, 1984)
10.6.12 Motivational regulation	Action Control: motivation control. Intrapersonal component: motivation control. Self-regulation of extrinsic motivation	Theory of action control (Kuhl, 1984) Empowerment theory (Zimmerman, 1995) Self-determination theory (SDT; Deci & Ryan, 2002, 2010; Gaggioli et al., 2017; Ryan & Deci, 2000)
10.6.13 Behavior regulation	Behavioural regulation: breaking habit.	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)
11 Objective capability	Ability	Fogg Behavior Model (FBM; Fogg et al., 2003; Fogg, 2009a, 2009b)
	Capability: psychological capability and physical capability.	COM-B system (Michie et al., 2011)
	Generative capabilities	Social action theory (Ewart, 1991)
	Performance capacity	Model of human occupation (Kielhofner, 2002)
	Self-determination 2	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)
	Self-perception (It is a product of social interaction and an individual's ability to respond differentially to his own behavior and its controlling variables.)	Self-perception theory (Bem, 1967, 1972)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
11.1 Competence	Self-regulatory capacity	Temporal self-regulation theory (Hall & Fong, 2007)
	Behavior-related needs: competence.	Health behavior internalization model (HBIM; Bellg, 2003)
	Competence	Ford's motivational system theory (MST; Van Dellen, 2012)
	Social competence	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)
11.2 Executive function	Executive function: working memory, inhibition, and shifting.	Maintain IT (identity transformation) model (Caldwell et al., 2018)
	Working memory capacity	Dual process model of self-control (Frieese et al., 2008; Hofmann et al., 2008)
11.3 Behavioral knowledge and skills	Ability factors: action knowledge.	Risk, attitude, norm, ability, and self-regulation model (RANAS; Mosler, 2012)
	Acquisition of skills	Heuristic model for teachable moments (TM; McBride et al., 2003)
	Condition specific knowledge	Integrated Theory of Health Behavior Change (ITHBC; Ryan, 2009)
	Coping skills	Conceptual model of psychosocial risk and protective factors for excessive gestational weight gain (Hill et al., 2013)
	Facilitators: skills, knowledge.	Health action model (HAM; Mazaheri & Heidarnia, 2015; Seaman, 2010; Tones, 1987; Vahedian-Shahroodi et al., 2019)
	Health behavior skills: objective ability	Information-Motivation-Behavioral Skills Model (IMB model; Fisher & Fisher, 2003; Fisher et al., 2003; Hodges et al., 2020)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Interactional component: critical awareness, understanding causal agents, skill development, skill transfer across life domains, and resource mobilization.	Empowerment theory (Zimmerman, 1995)
	Knowledge	Extended information processing model (Flay et al., 1980)
	Knowledge and skills to perform the behavior	Integrated Behavior Model (IBM)
	Knowledge	Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)
	Performance skills	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)
	Knowledge	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)
	Skills	
	Knowledge	
	Social skills Knowledge/Understanding of weight gain during pregnancy	Conceptual model of psychosocial risk and protective factors for excessive gestational weight gain (Hill et al., 2013)
	Mediating mechanisms individual factors: skills.	Social contextual model of health behavior change (SCM; Sorensen et al., 2003)
	Personal factors: knowledge.	Social learning theory Social cognitive theory (SCT)
	Prevention skills	Dynamic social systems model (DSSM; Latkin et al., 2010)
	Self-control strategies: skill-training.	Relapse prevention model (Hendershot et al., 2011; Marlatt & Donovan, 2005; Marlatt & George, 1984)
	Skills	AIDS Risk Reduction Model (ARRM; Catania et al., 1990)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Skills	Edwin Fisher and others' resources and skills for self-management model
	Understand the process	Process model for lifestyle behavior change (PMLBC; Greaves et al., 2010; Gillison et al., 2015)
	User characteristics: skills.	Internet intervention model (Ritterband et al., 2009)
12 Reinforcement	Reinforcement	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Reinforcement	Operant learning theory (Skinner, 2014)
	Reinforcement	Social learning theory
	Reinforcement management	Social cognitive theory (SCT)
	Reinforcement: rewards, incentives,	Transtheoretical Model (TTM) / Stages of Change
	punishment, consequents (related	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al.,
	reinforcement), reinforcement,	2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)
	contingencies, and sanctions.	
	Reinforcements	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Reinforcement value	Rotter's social learning theory (Rotter, 1982)
	Reinforcer	Behavioral choice theory (Epstein, 1998; Lacey & Rachlin, 1978; Vlek, 1991)
	Rewards	Cognitive evaluation theory (CET; Hoss, 1985)
	Social learning processs: social	Integrative conceptual model of spiritual mechanisms underlying substance abuse behaviour change (Neff & MacMaster, 2005)
	reinforcement.	

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
13 Subconsciousness-dominant process (It does not exclude conscious processes.)	Automatic	2 × 2 behaviour change matrix (Rothman et al., 2009)
	Brain: reactive brain (for reactions to environmental stimuli) 1	Evo-Eco approach (Aunger & Curtis, 2014a)
	Heuristic	Prototype willingness model (Gerrard et al., 2008)
	Heuristic processing	Heuristic Systematic Model
	Impulses (urges)/Inhibitions	PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)
	Motivation: automatic processes (involving emotions and impulses that arise from associative learning).	COM-B system (Michie et al., 2011)
	Operational System (OS)	Context, executive, and operational systems theory (CEOS Theory; Borland, 2016)
	Peripheral route	Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM)
Reason (implicit and subliminal)	Behavioural reasoning theory (Westaby, 2005)	
System 1: intuitive and automatic.	Dual-Process Theory (Kahneman, 1973)	
13.1 Instinct	Motivation: automatic processes (innate dispositions).	COM-B system (Michie et al., 2011)
13.2 Habit	Brain: reactive brain (for reactions to environmental stimuli) 2	Evo-Eco approach (Aunger & Curtis, 2014a)
	Habit	Context-dependent repetition (Lally & Gardner, 2013; Lally et al., 2010; Lally et al., 2011)
	Habit	Habit formation theory (HFT; Gardner et al., 2012)
	Habit	Habit theory (Verplanken, 2006; Verplanken & Aarts, 1999; Verplanken & Orbell, 2003; Verplanken et al., 2008)
	Habit	Integrated Behavior Model (IBM)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
13.3 Associative constructs	Habit	Process model for lifestyle behavior change (PMLBC; Greaves et al., 2010; Gillison et al., 2015)
	Habit	Risk, attitude, norm, ability, and self-regulation model (RANAS; Mosler, 2012)
	Habits: frequency of past behaviour.	Theory of interpersonal behaviour (TIB; Cheng et al., 2011; Moody & Siponen, 2013; Triandis, 1979)
	Habit strength	Environmental research framework for weight gain prevention (Kremers et al., 2006)
	Habitualness	Dual process model of self-control (Friese et al., 2008; Hofmann et al., 2008)
	Habituation	Model of human occupation (Kielhofner, 2002)
	Associative store	Reflective-Impulsive model (Strack & Deutsch, 2004)
	Automatic affective reactions (implicit attitude) 2	Dual process model of self-control (Friese et al., 2008; Hofmann et al., 2008)
	Automatic approach-avoidance reactions	
	Behavioral schemata	Reflective-Impulsive model (Strack & Deutsch, 2004)
14 Behavior/Response	Expectancy 2 (It should not be thought of as just consciously recollected beliefs about the expected effects of drinking, but also associational structures in long-term memory.)	Alcohol expectancy theory (Christiansen et al., 1982; Davis et al., 2013; Jones et al., 2001)
	Behavior	Risk, attitude, norm, ability, and self-regulation model (RANAS; Mosler, 2012)
	Behavior (eg. smoking cessation)	Heuristic model for teachable moments (TM; McBride et al., 2003)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
14.1 Change	Behaviors	Cognitive consistency theory (Harmon-Jones & Mills, 2019; Miller et al., 2015; Thompson et al., 2012)
	Behaviour system	Problem Behaviour Theory (PBT; Jessor, 2014; Lerner et al., 2013; Mckellar & Sillence, 2020; Tremblay & Frigon, 2004)
	Physical activity and eating behaviors	Conceptual model of psychosocial risk and protective factors for excessive gestational weight gain (Hill et al., 2013)
	Behavioral component: community involvement, organizational participation, and coping behaviors.	Empowerment theory (Zimmerman, 1995)
	Action initiation	Health Action Process Approach (HAPA; Schwarzer, 1992, 2008, 2016b; Sniehotta et al., 2005)
	Action or inhibition of action	Protection motivation theory (PMT)
	Actual health behaviour	Health Behavior Goal Model (HBG model; Maes & Gebhardt, 2000)
	Target health behaviour	
	Adaptive changes	Extended parallel process model (EPPM; Witte, 1992)
	Maladaptive changes	
Adherence	Supportive accountability model (Mohr et al., 2011)	
Behavior	Extended information processing model (Flay et al., 1980)	
Behavior	Integrated behavior change model (Hagger & Chatzisarantis, 2014)	
Behavior	Multiple domain model (MDM; Zimmerman et al., 2007)	
Behavior	Reflective-Impulsive model (Strack & Deutsch, 2004)	

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Behavior	Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) Integrated Behavior Model (IBM)
	Behavior change	BASNEF model (Heather, 2005; Momeni et al., 2020)
	Behavior change	Integrative conceptual model of spiritual mechanisms underlying substance abuse behaviour change (Neff & MacMaster, 2005)
	Behavior change	Internet intervention model (Ritterband et al., 2009)
	Behavior potential	Rotter's social learning theory (Rotter, 1982)
	Behaviour	Behaviour Centred Design (BCD; Aunger & Curtis, 2016; White et al., 2016)
	Behaviour	Theory of interpersonal behaviour (TIB; Cheng et al., 2011; Moody & Siponen, 2013; Triandis, 1979)
	Behavioural state: trial.	Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)
	Controlling system: output function.	Perceptual Control Theory (PCT; Powers et al., 2011)
	Environment: output quantity.	
	Coping efforts: problem management 2.	Transactional model of stress and coping
	Outcomes of coping (adaptation): health behaviors.	
	Coping response	Relapse prevention model (Hendershot et al., 2011; Marlatt & Donovan, 2005; Marlatt & George, 1984)
	Probability of relapse	
	Effort	Goal theory (Bagozzi, 1992)
	Energy balance-related behavior	Environmental research framework for weight gain prevention (Kremers et al., 2006)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Engagement in self-management behavior	Integrated Theory of Health Behavior Change (ITHBC; Ryan, 2009)
	Goal mechanisms: effort.	Goal setting theory (Locke & Latham, 2002)
	Health behavior	Information-Motivation-Behavioral Skills Model (IMB model; Fisher & Fisher, 2003; Fisher et al., 2003; Hodges et al., 2020)
	Health behaviors	Maintain IT (identity transformation) model (Caldwell et al., 2018)
	Health behaviors	Social determinants of health and environmental health promotion model (Schulz & Northridge, 2004)
	Health promoting behavior	Health promotion model (HPM; Heydari & Khorashadizadeh, 2014; Khoshnood et al., 2018)
	Health protective action	Social action theory (Ewart, 1991)
	Health-related behavior	Dual process model of self-control (Frieze et al., 2008; Hofmann et al., 2008)
	Healthy behavior	Health action model (HAM; Mazaheri & Heidarnia, 2015; Seaman, 2010; Tones, 1987; Vahedian-Shahroodi et al., 2019)
	HIV-related behaviors	Dynamic social systems model (DSSM; Latkin et al., 2010)
	Initiation	2×2 behaviour change matrix (Rothman et al., 2009)
	Initiation/One-time behavior change	Multi-theory model (MTM; Dokun-Mowete et al., 2019; Sharma, 2015; Sharma et al., 2016)
	Observed behavior	Temporal self-regulation theory (Hall & Fong, 2007)
	Output function (behavior)	Control theory (Carver & Scheier, 1982)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Practice for change	Multi-theory model (MTM; Dokun-Mowete et al., 2019; Sharma, 2015; Sharma et al., 2016)
	Responses 1	PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)
	Risk behavior	Prototype willingness model (Gerrard et al., 2008)
	Trial behavior	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Trial behavior	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)
14.2 Maintenance	Action maintenance	Health Action Process Approach (HAPA; Schwarzer, 1992, 2008, 2016b; Sniehotta et al., 2005)
	Behavioural state: maintenance.	Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)
	Goal mechanisms: persistence.	Goal setting theory (Locke & Latham, 2002)
	Health behavior maintenance	Health behavior internalization model (HBIM; Bellg, 2003)
	Maintenance	Extended information processing model (Flay et al., 1980)
	Maintenance	2 × 2 behaviour change matrix (Rothman et al., 2009)
	Physical activity environment	Theory of physical activity maintenance (Nigg et al., 2008)
	Repeated behavior	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Repeated behavior	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
14.3 Response	Sustenance/Long term behavior change	Multi-theory model (MTM; Dokun-Mowete et al., 2019; Sharma, 2015; Sharma et al., 2016)
	Treatment maintenance	Internet intervention model (Ritterband et al., 2009)
	Brain: reactive brain (for reactions to environmental stimuli) 3	Evo-Eco approach (Aunger & Curtis, 2014a)
	Response Responses 1	Classical conditioning (Skinner, 2014) PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)
15 Related behavior		
15.1 Antecedent behaviors	Alcohol consumption (influence consciousness process)	Dual process model of self-control (Friese et al., 2008; Hofmann et al., 2008)
	Help seeking	AIDS Risk Reduction Model (ARRM; Catania et al., 1990)
	Preparatory behaviors	Multiple domain model (MDM; Zimmerman et al., 2007)
15.2 Clustered behaviors	Clustering (co-occurrence of behaviors)	Environmental research framework for weight gain prevention (Kremers et al., 2006)
15.3 Competitive behaviors	Behavioral prepotency	Temporal self-regulation theory (Hall & Fong, 2007)
	Immediate competing demands and preferences	Health promotion model (HPM; Heydari & Khorashadizadeh, 2014; Khoshnood et al., 2018)
15.4 Same/Similar behaviors	Closely-related behavior	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)
	Past behavior	Habit and intention theory (Ouellette & Wood, 1998)
	Previous behavior	Prototype willingness model (Gerrard et al., 2008)
	Prior-related behavior	Health promotion model (HPM; Heydari & Khorashadizadeh, 2014; Khoshnood et al., 2018)
16 Behavior outcome	Cancer morbidity and cancer mortality	Social contextual model of health behavior change

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Gestational weight gain	(SCM; Sorensen et al., 2003) Conceptual model of psychosocial risk and protective factors for excessive gestational weight gain (Hill et al., 2013)
	Goal achievement	Goal theory (Bagozzi, 1992)
	Health outcomes	Social determinants of health and environmental health promotion model (Schulz & Northridge, 2004)
	Health status	Integrated Theory of Health Behavior Change (ITHBC; Ryan, 2009)
	Impact on environment 1	Control theory (Carver & Scheier, 1982)
	Interpersonal matrix: interpretation of own behavior.	Personality theory (Secord & Backman, 1961)
	Outcomes	Social action theory (Ewart, 1991)
	Outcomes (include emotions)	Risk as feelings model (Loewenstein et al., 2001)
	Outcomes of coping (adaptation): emotional well-being 1 and functional status.	Transactional model of stress and coping
	Outcome	Groningen Active Living Model (GALM; Kwasnicka et al., 2016; Stevens et al., 1999)
	Subjective fitness (after program)	
	Performance	Goal setting theory (Locke & Latham, 2002)
	Physiological reaction	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Symptom improvement	Internet intervention model (Ritterband et al., 2009)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
17.1 Direct experience	Experiences	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)
	Past experience	PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)
	Prior experience	Protection motivation theory (PMT)
17.2 Vicarious experience	Risk images 3	Prototype willingness model (Gerrard et al., 2008)
	Vicarious experiences	Social learning theory Social cognitive theory (SCT)
18 Personal state		
18.1 Psychological state	Arousal	PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)
	Arousal	Social action theory (Ewart, 1991)
	Body 1	Behaviour Centred Design (BCD; Aunger & Curtis, 2016; White et al., 2016)
	Cognitions factors	Dietary restraint theory (Polivy & Herman, 1985)
	Dissonance	Cognitive consistency theory (Harmon-Jones & Mills, 2019; Miller et al., 2015; Thompson et al., 2012)
	Maternal psychological factors	Conceptual model of psychosocial risk and protective factors for excessive gestational weight gain (Hill et al., 2013)
	Psychological well-being	Maintain IT (identity transformation) model (Caldwell et al., 2018)
	User characteristics: cognitive factors.	Internet intervention model (Ritterband et al., 2009)
	Well-being	Social determinants of health and environmental health promotion model (Schulz & Northridge, 2004)
18.1.1 Emotion	Action Control: emotion control. 2	Theory of action control (Kuhl, 1984)
	Affect: emotions.	Theory of interpersonal behaviour (TIB; Cheng et al., 2011; Moody & Siponen, 2013; Triandis, 1979)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Aversive emotional states	AIDS Risk Reduction Model (ARRM; Catania et al., 1990)
	Emotion	Heuristic model for teachable moments (TM; McBride et al., 2003)
	Emotion	Life-span theory (Heckhausen & Schulz, 1995; Schulz & Heckhausen, 1996)
	Emotion	Self-perception theory (Bem, 1967, 1972)
	Emotion	Temporal self-regulation theory (Hall & Fong, 2007)
	Emotion	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)
	Emotion	Two-factor theory of avoidance learning (Mowrer 1939; Michaella, 2010; Stasiewicz & Maisto, 1993)
	Emotional states: generalised.	PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)
	Emotional transformation 2	Multi-theory model (MTM; Dokun-Mowete et al., 2019; Sharma, 2015; Sharma et al., 2016)
	Emotions	Broaden-and-build theory of positive emotions (Fredrickson, 1998)
	Emotions	Ford's motivational system theory (MST; Van Dellen, 2012)
	Enjoy/Pleasure 2	Groningen Active Living Model (GALM; Kwasnicka et al., 2016; Stevens et al., 1999)
	Fear	Extended parallel process model (EPPM; Witte, 1992)
	Fear	Protection motivation theory (PMT)
	Feelings 2	Risk as feelings model (Loewenstein et al., 2001)
	Outcomes of coping (adaptation): emotional well-being 2.	Transactional model of stress and coping

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
18.1.2 Mood	Representation of fear	Common-sense model of self-regulation (CSM; Leventhal et al., 2003; Leventhal et al., 2016)
	Mood	Affect infusion model (AIM; Forgas, 1995, 2001)
	Mood	Dual process model of self-control (Friese et al., 2008; Hofmann et al., 2008)
	Mood	Social action theory (Ewart, 1991)
18.2 Physiological state	Dramatic relief	Transtheoretical Model (TTM) / Stages of Change
	Other factors: background mood.	Risk as feelings model (Loewenstein et al., 2001)
	Biological conditions (e.g., withdrawal symptoms)	Social action theory (Ewart, 1991)
	Body image during pregnancy	Conceptual model of psychosocial risk and protective factors for excessive gestational weight gain (Hill et al., 2013)
	Physiological factors (e.g., weight loss and hunger)	Dietary restraint theory (Polivy & Herman, 1985)
	Subjective fitness (before program)	Groningen Active Living Model (GALM; Kwasnicka et al., 2016; Stevens et al., 1999)
19 Individual difference	User characteristics: disease.	Internet intervention model (Ritterband et al., 2009)
	Demographic variables	Integrated Behavior Model (IBM)
	Other individual difference variables	
	Personality	
	Demographics variables: personality.	Health Belief Model (HBM; Kagee & Freeman, 2008)
	Demographic variables	Multiple domain model (MDM; Zimmerman et al., 2007)
	Personality/Individual difference	
Demographic variables	Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)	

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Personality traits	Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)
	Individual attributes: initial level of spirituality.	Integrative conceptual model of spiritual mechanisms underlying substance abuse behaviour change (Neff & MacMaster, 2005)
	Individual difference	Extended parallel process model (EPPM; Witte, 1992)
	Intelligence or personality	Implicit theories (Dweck, 1996, 2012; Dweck et al., 1995)
	Modifying conditions: individual level.	Social contextual model of health behavior change (SCM; Sorensen et al., 2003)
	Participants (related to demographic variables)	Groningen Active Living Model (GALM; Kwasnicka et al., 2016; Stevens et al., 1999)
	Personal characteristics (It refers to sociodemographic variables such as gender, age, and educational level, as well as various other attributes such as basic goal orientations or styles, including approach-avoidance, active-reactive, maintenance-change, or state-action orientations.)	Health Behavior Goal Model (HBG model; Maes & Gebhardt, 2000)
	Personality	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Personality	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)
	Personality variables	Protection motivation theory (PMT)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
19.1 Self-concept	Person: demographic. Person: personality. Socio-demographic characteristics	Environmental research framework for weight gain prevention (Kremers et al., 2006) Social contextual model of health behavior change (SCM; Sorensen et al., 2003)
	User characteristics: demographics and traits. Vested interest	Internet intervention model (Ritterband et al., 2009) Vested interest theory (Crano & Prislin, 1995; Sivacek & Crano, 1982)
	Centered identity: role-based identity, group-based identity, and behavior-based identity. Group identity	Maintain IT (identity transformation) model (Caldwell et al., 2018) Theory of normative social behavior (Rimal & Real, 2005)
	Identity	Life crises and the process of reinvention theory (Epiphaniou & Ogden, 2010; Ogden & Hills, 2008)
	Identity (frame of mine)	PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)
	Interpersonal matrix: self-concept.	Personality theory (Secord & Backman, 1961)
	Occupation (related to identity)	Model of human occupation (Kielhofner, 2002)
	Social factors: self-concept	Theory of interpersonal behaviour (TIB; Cheng et al., 2011; Moody & Siponen, 2013; Triandis, 1979)
	Social identity	Social identity theory (Leaper, 2011; Tajfel & Turner, 1979)
	Self concept	Health action model (HAM; Mazaheri & Heidarnia, 2015; Seaman, 2010; Tones, 1987; Vahedian-Shahroodi et al., 2019)
	Self-concept	Self-concept theory (Bracken, 1996)
	Self-conceptions	Belief systems theory (Grube et al., 1994)
	Self-concept	Heuristic model for teachable moments (TM; McBride

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Social role	et al., 2003)
	Self-image/Personality	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Self needs: identity (ownership) 2.	Health behavior internalization model (HBIM; Bellg, 2003)
	Self-schemata	Self-schemata theory (Markus, 1977)
	Sense of self (self-concept)	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)
	Social identity	Social comparison and social identity (Turner, 1975)
	Social/Professional role and identity: professional identity, professional role, social identity, identity, professional boundaries, professional confidence, group identity, leadership, and organisational commitment.	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)
19.2	Biological factors	Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)
Physiological/Biological factors	Biological factors	Dynamic social systems model (DSSM; Latkin et al., 2010)
	Biology	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)
	Body	Evo-Eco approach (Aunger & Curtis, 2014a)
	Body 2	Behaviour Centred Design (BCD; Aunger & Curtis, 2016; White et al., 2016)
	Demographics variables: age, gender.	Health Belief Model (HBM; Kagee & Freeman, 2008)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
19.3 Psychological factors	Gender	Theory of gender and power (Connell, 2013)
	Personal factor: biological	Health promotion model (HPM; Heydari & Khorashadizadeh, 2014; Khoshnood et al., 2018)
	Unrealistic optimism	Optimistic bias (Weinstein, 1980)
	User characteristics: physiological factors	Internet intervention model (Ritterband et al., 2009)
	Mental health status	Dynamic social systems model (DSSM; Latkin et al., 2010)
	Optimism	Transactional model of stress and coping
	Optimism: optimism, pessimism, unrealistic optimism, and identity.	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)
	Perceptual lens (It refers to attributional or explanatory style, implicit theory surrounding behaviour and identity change.)	Maintain IT (identity transformation) model (Caldwell et al., 2018)
	Personal factor: psychological.	Health promotion model (HPM; Heydari & Khorashadizadeh, 2014; Khoshnood et al., 2018)
	Psychological factors	Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)
Psychological situation	Rotter's social learning theory (Rotter, 1982)	
Sense of coherence	Salutogenic model (Antonovsky, 1996)	
Temperament	Prototype willingness model (Gerrard et al., 2008)	
Temperament	Social action theory (Ewart, 1991)	
19.3.1 Value	Centered Identity: personal values.	Maintain IT (identity transformation) model (Caldwell et al., 2018)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	General values	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Values	Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994)
	Values (cognitive representations of individual needs and desire)	Belief systems theory (Grube et al., 1994)
19.4 Social-cultural factors	Demographics variables: ethnicity, socioeconomics, and knowledge. Personal factor: sociocultural.	Health Belief Model (HBM; Kagee & Freeman, 2008)
	Social constructs (e.g., gender, race/ethnicity, and sexual orientation)	Health promotion model (HPM; Heydari & Khorashadizadeh, 2014; Khoshnood et al., 2018) Dynamic social systems model (DSSM; Latkin et al., 2010)
19.5 Behavioral styles	Behavioural factors (e.g., life styles)	Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)
	Moderators: dispositional coping styles. Program elements: discipline (related lifestyles).	Transactional model of stress and coping Integrative conceptual model of spiritual mechanisms underlying substance abuse behaviour change (Neff & MacMaster, 2005)
	Self-control strategies: lifestyle intervention.	Relapse prevention model (Hendershot et al., 2011; Marlatt & Donovan, 2005; Marlatt & George, 1984)
	Settings: task (routinely performed).	Social action theory (Ewart, 1991)
20 Environment	Barriers	Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)
	Behavior-related needs: context.	Health behavior internalization model (HBIM; Bellg, 2003)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Behavior settings	Roger Barker's environmental psychology
	Behaviour settings	Behaviour Centred Design (BCD; Aunger & Curtis, 2016; White et al., 2016)
	Community level	Behavioural ecological model (BEM; Dresler-Hawke & Veer, 2006; Hovell et al., 2002)
	Local level	
	Socio-cultural level	
	Context	Context-dependent repetition (Lally & Gardner, 2013; Lally et al., 2010; Lally et al., 2011)
	Context	Ford's motivational system theory (MST; Van Dellen, 2012)
	Context	Prototype willingness model (Gerrard et al., 2008)
	Contexts	Situated learning theory (Besar, 2018; O'Brien & Battista 2020)
	Contextual interconnectedness factors: social interconnectedness.	Dynamic social systems model (DSSM; Latkin et al., 2010)
	Resources: material resources and allocations, science & technology.	
	Environment	Internet intervention model (Ritterband et al., 2009)
	Environment	Kurt Lewin's ecological psychology
	Environment	Model of human occupation (Kielhofner, 2002)
	Environmental characteristics	Health Behavior Goal Model (HBG model; Maes & Gebhardt, 2000)
	Environmental constraints	Integrated Behavior Model (IBM)
	Environmental context and resources	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Environment factors: facilitating conditions.	Theory of interpersonal behaviour (TIB; Cheng et al., 2011; Moody & Siponen, 2013; Triandis, 1979)
	Environment factors: facilitation.	Social learning theory Social cognitive theory (SCT)
	Environment State-of-the-world	Behaviour Centred Design (BCD; Aunger & Curtis, 2016; White et al., 2016)
	Exosystem	Urie Bronfenbrenner's systems theory
	Mesosystem	
	Microsystem	
	External environment	PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)
	Facilitating/Inhibiting conditions	Goal theory (Bagozzi, 1992)
	Facilitators: supporting environment.	Health action model (HAM; Mazaheri & Heidarnia, 2015; Seaman, 2010; Tones, 1987; Vahedian-Shahroodi et al., 2019)
	Food availability, price, placement, promotion of foods, and nutrition information.	Karen Glanz and others' model of community food environment
	Influence & control factors (informal or formal)	Dynamic social systems model (DSSM; Latkin et al., 2010)
	Macroenvironmental sectors	Angelo (Swinburn et al., 1999)
	Microenvironmental settings	
	Physical activity maintenance	Theory of physical activity maintenance (Nigg et al., 2008)
	Resource: tangible resource.	Network-Individual-Resource (NIR) model (Johnson et al., 2010)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Situational/Contextual	Multiple domain model (MDM; Zimmerman et al., 2007)
	Social contexts	A social ecology model of behaviour change (Panter-Brick et al., 2006)
20.1 Physical environment	Availability of protective or harmful consumer products	Deborah Cohen and others' structural-ecological model
	Physical structures	
	Available materials	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Built environment	Social determinants of health and environmental health promotion model (Schulz & Northridge, 2004)
	Natural environment	
	Changes in physical environment	Multi-theory model (MTM; Dokun-Mowete et al., 2019; Sharma, 2015; Sharma et al., 2016)
	Environment: physical environment.	Evo-Eco approach (Aunger & Curtis, 2014a)
	Opportunity: physical opportunity.	COM-B system (Michie et al., 2011)
	Physical	Angelo (Swinburn et al., 1999)
	Physical environment	Edwin Fisher and others' resources and skills for self-management model
	Physical environment	Environmental research framework for weight gain prevention (Kremers et al., 2006)
	Physical environment	Temporal self-regulation theory (Hall & Fong, 2007)
	Physical environment	Thomas Glass and Matthew McAtee's ecosocial model
	Physical environments	Daniel Stokols' social ecology model for health promotion (Stokols et al., 1996)
	Physical settings	Rudolph Moos's social ecology

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Settings: physical. Website	Social action theory (Ewart, 1991) Internet intervention model (Ritterband et al., 2009)
20.2 Social environment	Changes in social environment Communications medium Community Community and group Cultural environment Social bonding Social situation Cultural factors Demography-social structure Economic Political Sociocultural Economic environment Political environment Sociocultural environmet Environment: social environment. Family influences Peer influences	Multi-theory model (MTM; Dokun-Mowete et al., 2019; Sharma, 2015; Sharma et al., 2016) Supportive accountability model (Mohr et al., 2011) Social change theory (Anderson et al., 2002) Community and group models (theory set) Theory of triadic influence (TTI; Flay & Petraitis, 1994) Cross-cultural psychology (Triandis, 1999) Problem Behaviour Theory (PBT; Jessor, 2014; Lerner et al., 2013; Mckellar & Sillence, 2020; Tremblay & Frigon, 2004) Angelo (Swinburn et al., 1999) Environmental research framework for weight gain prevention (Kremers et al., 2006) Evo-Eco approach (Aunger & Curtis, 2014a) Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Familial/Social-contextual factors	Conceptual model of psychosocial risk and protective factors for excessive gestational weight gain (Hill et al., 2013)
	Family	Family process theory (Broderick, 1993)
	Family	Family systems theory (Bowen, 1966; Johnson & Ray, 2016)
	Group-affiliations	Web of group-affiliations (Chayko, 2015)
	Helping relationships	Transtheoretical Model (TTM) / Stages of Change
	Human aggregate	Rudolph Moos's social ecology
	Organizational settings	
	Implementing organization	Groningen Active Living Model (GALM; Kwasnicka et al., 2016; Stevens et al., 1999)
	Microcontext	
	Inequalities	Social determinants of health and environmental health promotion model (Schulz & Northridge, 2004)
	Macrosocial factors	
	Social context	
	Interpersonal communication 1	Interpersonal communication (theory set)
	Interpersonal process and primary groups, institutional factors, community factors, and public policy.	Kenneth McLeroy and others' ecological model of health behavior
	Media	Prototype willingness model (Gerrard et al., 2008)
	Media and cultural messages	Deborah Cohen and others' structural-ecological model
	Policies	
	Social structures	
	Modifying conditions: interpersonal level, organizational level,	Social contextual model of health behavior change (SCM; Sorensen et al., 2003)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	neighborhood/community level, and societal level.	
	Mediating mechanisms societal context: organizational environment.	
	Policy	
	Culutre	
	Network	Network-Individual-Resource (NIR) model (Johnson et al., 2010)
	Nurse-patient relationships	Peplau's theory of interpersonal relations (Hagerty et al., 2017)
	Opportunity: social opportunity.	COM-B system (Michie et al., 2011)
	Organizational systmes	Social action theory (Ewart, 1991)
	Relationship systems	
	Settings: social.	
	Other individuals	Social impact theory (Latané, 1981)
	Policy environment	Edwin Fisher and others' resources and skills for self-management model
	Social environment	
	Relationship between caregivers and patients	Watson's model of caring (Lukose, 2011)
	Small-scale social systems	Behavior setting theory (Popov & Chompalov, 2012)
	Social and cultural factors	Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)
	Social consensus	Social consensus model of health education (Romer & Hornik, 1992)
	Social environment	Temporal self-regulation theory (Hall & Fong, 2007)
	Social environment	Thomas Glass and Matthew McAtee's ecosocial model

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Social environmental	Multiple domain model (MDM; Zimmerman et al., 2007)
	Social structural	
	Social environments	Daniel Stokols' social ecology model for health promotion (Stokols et al., 1996)
	Social integration	Social determinants of health and environmental health promotion model (Schulz & Northridge, 2004)
	Social network	Fisher's social influence theory (Fisher, 1988)
	Social networks	AIDS Risk Reduction Model (ARRM; Catania et al., 1990)
	Social networks	Social support and social networks related theories (theory set)
	Social structures	Theory of gender and power (Connell, 2013)
20.3 Biological environment	Environment: biological environment.	Evo-Eco approach (Aunger & Curtis, 2014a)
21 Processes/Mechanisms	Abstinence violation effect (a psychological response)	Relapse prevention model (Hendershot et al., 2011; Marlatt & Donovan, 2005; Marlatt & George, 1984)
	Anticipatory proactive system	Social learning theory
	Observational learning	Social cognitive theory (SCT)
	Reciprocal determinism	
	Classical conditioning	Classical conditioning (Skinner, 2014)
	Classical conditioning	Two-factor theory of avoidance learning (Mowrer 1939; Michaela, 2010; Stasiewicz & Maisto, 1993)
	Operant conditioning	
	Comparison	Social comparison theory (Festinger, 1954)
	Counterconditioning	Transtheoretical Model (TTM) / Stages of Change
	Decision-making process	Janis and Mann's theory of conflict (Janis & Mann, 1968)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Delivery mode	Groningen Active Living Model (GALM; Kwasnicka et al., 2016; Stevens et al., 1999)
	Environment: feedback function.	Perceptual Control Theory (PCT; Powers et al., 2011)
	Four types of social action	Social action theory (Weber, 2009)
	Interpersonal communication 2	Interpersonal communication (theory set)
	Interpersonal processes	Personality theory (Secord & Backman, 1961)
	Mechanisms of change	Internet intervention model (Ritterband et al., 2009)
	Observational learning	Protection motivation theory (PMT)
	Outcome-Response (O-R)	Associative-cybernetic model (de Wit & Dickinson, 2009)
	Response-Outcome (R-O)	
	Past experience influence: associative learning and imitation learning.	PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)
	Social comparison	Social comparison and social identity (Turner, 1975)
	Social interaction processes (social capabilities)	Social action theory (Ewart, 1991)
	Social interdependence	
	Social interactions	Social constructivist perspective (Burr, 2015)
	Social interactions	Web of group-affiliations (Chayko, 2015)
	Social learning process: role modeling.	Integrative conceptual model of spiritual mechanisms underlying substance abuse behaviour change (Neff & MacMaster, 2005)
21.1 Environment affects people	Access	Dynamic social systems model (DSSM; Latkin et al., 2010)
	Social influence & Control processes	
	Transfer of resources: material, information, and technology.	

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Engage socail support	Process model for lifestyle behavior change (PMLBC; Greaves et al., 2010; Gillison et al., 2015)
	Environment factors: incentive motivation.	Social learning theory Social cognitive theory (SCT)
	Facilitators: access to resource, communication.	Health action model (HAM; Mazaheri & Heidarnia, 2015; Seaman, 2010; Tones, 1987; Vahedian-Shahroodi et al., 2019)
	Family influences	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Peer influences	
	Human support	Supportive accountability model (Mohr et al., 2011)
	Interpersonal influences (e.g., family, peers, providers are norms and social support sources.)	Health promotion model (HPM; Heydari & Khorashadizadeh, 2014; Khoshnood et al., 2018)
	Situational influences	
	Interpersonal processes	Personality theory (Secord & Backman, 1961)
	Mediating mechanisms societal context: social support.	Social contextual model of health behavior change (SCM; Sorensen et al., 2003)
	Moderators: social support.	Transactional model of stress and coping
	Perceived environment system (e.g., peer pressure and parental influence)	Problem Behaviour Theory (PBT; Jessor, 2014; Lerner et al., 2013; Mckellar & Sillence, 2020; Tremblay & Frigon, 2004)
	Socialization	
	Program elements: support.	Integrative conceptual model of spiritual mechanisms underlying substance abuse behaviour change (Neff & MacMaster, 2005)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Social climate: supportiveness of a social setting for a particular behavior.	Rudolph Moos's social ecology
	Social influence	Fisher's social influence theory (Fisher, 1988) Kelman's social influence theory (Kelman, 1958, 1974)
	Social influence	Health Behavior Goal Model (HBG model; Maes & Gebhardt, 2000)
	Social influences: modelling.	Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)
	Social influences: modelling 1.	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)
	Social influences: pressure.	Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)
	Social influences: social pressure, group conformity, social comparisons, social support, power, intergroup conflict, alienation, group identity, and modelling 2.	Theoretical domains framework (TDF; Cane et al., 2012; Kaczmarczyk et al., 2021)
	Social influence	Integrated Theory of Health Behavior Change (ITHBC; Ryan, 2009)
	Social support: emotional, instrumental, and informational.	
	Social support	AIDS Risk Reduction Model (ARRM; Catania et al., 1990)
	Social support	Groningen Active Living Model (GALM; Kwasnicka et al., 2016; Stevens et al., 1999)
	Social support	Social determinants of health and environmental health promotion model (Schulz & Northridge, 2004)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
21.2 People affect the environment	Social support	Social support and social networks related theories (theory set)
	Support	Internet intervention model (Ritterband et al., 2009)
	Action control: environment control.	Theory of action control (Kuhl, 1984)
	Environmental reevaluation	Transtheoretical Model (TTM) / Stages of Change
22 Stages-related	Impact on environment 2	Control theory (Carver & Scheier, 1982)
	Labeling, commitment, enactment (three phases: information-seeking, obtaining remedies, and enacting solutions).	AIDS Risk Reduction Model (ARRM; Catania et al., 1990)
	Precontemplation stage, contemplation stage, initial behaviour change stage, and maintenance stage.	Health Behavior Goal Model (HBG model; Maes & Gebhardt, 2000)
	Predecisional phase (deliberation)	Rubicon model of action phases (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2007, 2008; Heckhausen, 2007)
	Postdecisional phase (planning)	
	Actional phase (action)	
	Postactional phase (evaluation)	Integrative conceptual model of spiritual mechanisms underlying substance abuse behaviour change (Neff & MacMaster, 2005)
	Readiness: movement through stages of chang.	
	Stage: motivation, action, and maintenance.	Process model for lifestyle behavior change (PMLBC; Greaves et al., 2010; Gillison et al., 2015)
Stages: precontemplation, contemplation, preparation, action, maintenance, and termination.	Transtheoretical Model (TTM) / Stages of Change	
Unaware of issue	Precaution Adoption Process Model (PAPM)	

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Unengaged by issue Undecided about acting Decided to act Acting Maintenance Decided not to act Unfreeze Change Refreeze	Change theory (Lewin, 1943)
23 Time	Other factors: immediacy. Perception of time	Risk as feelings model (Loewenstein et al., 2001) Socioemotional selectivity theory (SST; Carstensen et al., 1999)
Individual level	Individual level Individual Resource: mental resource. Intrapersonal factors Personal attributes Personality system: the perceived opportunity structure, the personal belief structure, the personal control structure.	Behavioural ecological model (BEM; Dresler-Hawke & Veer, 2006; Hovell et al., 2002) Network-Individual-Resource (NIR) model (Johnson et al., 2010) Kenneth McLeroy and others' ecological model of health behavior Daniel Stokols' social ecology model for health promotion (Stokols et al., 1996) Problem Behaviour Theory (PBT; Jessor, 2014; Lerner et al., 2013; Mckellar & Silence, 2020; Tremblay & Frigon, 2004)
Nonspecific	Belief	Belief systems theory (Grube et al., 1994)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
	Beliefs	Cognitive consistency theory (Harmon-Jones & Mills, 2019; Miller et al., 2015; Thompson et al., 2012)
	Beliefs	Dynamic social systems model (DSSM; Latkin et al., 2010)
	Beliefs (about the nature of human attributes)	Implicit theories (Dweck, 1996, 2012; Dweck et al., 1995)
	Belief system	Health action model (HAM; Mazaheri & Heidarnia, 2015; Seaman, 2010; Tones, 1987; Vahedian-Shahroodi et al., 2019)
	Enabling factors (e.g., skill, time, expenditure, information)	BASNEF model (Heather, 2005; Momeni et al., 2020)
	Health behavior information (e.g., specific facts, heuristics, implicit theories)	Information-Motivation-Behavioral Skills Model (IMB model; Fisher & Fisher, 2003; Fisher et al., 2003; Hodges et al., 2020)
	High-risk situation	Relapse prevention model (Hendershot et al., 2011; Marlatt & Donovan, 2005; Marlatt & George, 1984)
	Information factors: message, channel, and source.	Attitude-social influence-efficacy model / Integrated Change Model (De Vries et al., 2005)
	Information (from our senses and our memory)	PRIME theory (West & Brown, 2013)
	Information	Integrative model of health attitude and behaviour change with integrative model of factors influencing smoking (Flay et al., 1983)
	Other information	
	Knowledge (e.g., HIV Transmission, health utility, and enjoyability)	AIDS Risk Reduction Model (ARRM; Catania et al., 1990)

Theme/Sub-theme	Key concepts	Theory name and references used
Life crises	Sustaining conditions	Life crises and the process of reinvention theory (Epiphaniou & Ogden, 2010; Ogden & Hills, 2008)
Resource (e.g., things, personality traits, conditions and resources of energy)		Conservation of resources theory (COR; Hobfoll, 1989)

Note. “Individual level” and “Nonspecific” do not belong to any specific theme, so they are not numbered. To facilitate readers in searching and reading relevant literature, some different spellings (e.g., “behavior” and “behaviour,” “organization” and “organisation”) are consistent with the original references.

Appendix D

Explanation of Synthesis Themes

Theme/Sub-theme	Explanation of synthesis themes
1 Needs	<p>“A basic need, whether it be a physiological need or a psychological need, is an energizing state that, if satisfied, conduces toward health and well-being but, if not satisfied, contributes to pathology and ill-being” (Ryan & Deci, 2000, p. 74).</p> <p>Human basic needs include physiological needs, safety needs, love needs, esteem needs, self-actualization needs (Maslow, 1943), cognitive and aesthetic needs (Maslow, 1970a), and later transcendence needs (Maslow, 1970b).</p> <p>“A kind of desire involving anticipated relief from mental or physical discomfort” (West & Brown, 2013, p. 182).</p>
2 Motivation	<p>Motivation is an internal state or process that arouse, guide, and maintain behavior (Kleinginna & Kleinginna, 1981, p. 265).</p> <p>“Motivation can be defined as that which gives behavior its direction or goals, and determines the strength or energy behind that behavior” (Mohr et al., 2011, p. 5).</p> <p>“Motivation concerns energy, direction, persistence and equifinality—all aspects of activation and intention” (Ryan & Deci, 2000, p. 69).</p> <p>“This is a much broader conceptualisation than appears in many discourses, covering as it does basic drives and ‘automatic’ processes as well as choice and intention” (Michie et al., 2011, p. 4).</p> <p>“It makes sense to think of addiction as a disorder of motivation” (West & Brown, 2013, p. 4).</p> <p>“It refers to all those brain processes that energise and direct behaviour including ‘reflective’ processes of conscious thought and analysis, and ‘automatic’ processes that we share with other species involving feelings and impulses” (West & Brown, 2013, p.193).</p> <p>“Motivation = goals × emotions × personal beliefs” (Van Dellen, 2012, p. 38).</p> <p>“Classic motivation theories rely on this narrow definition of motivation, assuming the motivation to</p>

Theme/Sub-theme	Explanation of synthesis themes
2.1 Volition	<p>act to be determined by both the desirability and perceived feasibility of the aspired goal” (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2008, p. 276).</p> <p>“The common ground on variety of definitions are explaining motivation as degree which individuals want and choose to engage in certain directed activities in condition that returns from that particular activities would satisfy their needs” (Osemeke & Adegboyega, 2017, p. 161).</p> <hr/> <p>Motivation and volition are two related but different states of behavior-driven states. Volition can also be considered a particular state of motivation.</p> <p>“The first [referring to motivation] addresses the motivational process of making a decision for a particular goal and against alternative goals. Such decisions, if they are not trivial, require the careful and even-handed consideration and weighing of multiple factors, pros, and cons for each alternative. The second [referring to volition] involves the volitional processes of maintaining and enhancing the commitment to a goal that one has decided for so that it can be put into action” (Heckhausen, 2007).</p> <p>“Motivation concerns the processes and phenomena involved in goal setting, i.e., the selection of goals on the basis of their desirability and feasibility. Motivational processes dominate in the pre-decisional and post-actional phases of the Rubicon model. Volitional processes and phenomena, on the other hand, concern the translation of these goals into action. Volitional processes dominate in the pre-actional and actional phase” (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2008, p. 276).</p> <p>“Volition concerns the translation of existing goals into action and, specifically, the regulation of these processes” (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2008, p. 276).</p>
3 Psychological propensity of behavior	It includes intention and willingness.
3.1 Intention	<p>“Intentions are assumed to capture the motivational factors that influence a behavior; they are indications of how hard people are willing to try, of how much of an effort they are planning to exert, in order to perform the behavior” (Ajzen, 1991, p. 181).</p> <p>Intention is a “... person’s location on a subjective probability dimension involving a relation between himself and some action” (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975, p. 288, as cited in Westaby, 2005, p. 99).</p>

Theme/Sub-theme	Explanation of synthesis themes
3.1.1 Goal intention	<p>“The strength of a goal intention’s fiat tendency is the product of its volitional strength (i.e., the commitment to pursuing the goal state) and of the suitability of the situation for its initiation” (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2008, p. 275).</p> <p>Goal intention: a commitment to a specify goal (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2008, p. 274).</p> <p>Intention: “a self-conscious decision to undertake an action” (West & Brown, 2013, p. 182).</p> <p>Similar concepts: “to desire to do something implies a motivational commitment to do it, if we assume that a person believes he or she can do it” (Bagozzi, 1992, p. 184).</p>
3.1.2 Implement intention	<p>“Goal intentions specify a certain end point that may be either a desired performance or an outcome” (Gollwitzer, 1999, p. 494).</p> <p>“Implementation intentions concerning the initiation, execution, and termination of actions help people to overcome the difficulties that can be anticipated as they progress toward their goals” (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2008, p. 275).</p> <p>“Implementation intentions are subordinate to goal intentions and specify the when, where, and how of responses leading to goal attainment” (Gollwitzer, 1999, p. 494).</p>
3.2 Willingness	<p>“The commencement of risky behaviors, such as a teenager accepting his first cigarette, which seem to be better explained in terms of a ‘willingness’ to act rather than in terms of any plan to act” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 126).</p> <p>“Willingness to engage in a risky behavior given a risk-conducive environment” (Pomery et al., 2009, p. 895).</p>
4 Perceived stimuli/needs	The perception of stimuli or needs that will trigger the response, motivation or behavior.
4.1 Perceived threat	<p>In HBM, the perceived threat is defined as a “combination of perceived susceptibility and severity” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 153).</p>
5 Attitudes-related	This theme involves various attitudes and related beliefs.
5.1 Implicit attitude	<p>Implicit attitudes are “best characterized as automatic affective reactions resulting from the particular associations that are activated automatically when one encounters a relevant stimulus” (Gawronski &</p>

Theme/Sub-theme	Explanation of synthesis themes
5.2 Explicit attitude	<p data-bbox="696 280 1061 309">Bodenhausen, 2006, p. 693).</p> <p data-bbox="667 323 1980 437">“Attitude is determined by the individual’s beliefs about outcomes or attributes of performing the behavior (<i>behavioral beliefs</i>), weighted by evaluations of those outcomes or attributes” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 71).</p>
5.2.1 Experiential attitude	<p data-bbox="667 451 1592 480">“Overall affective evaluation of the behavior” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 74).</p> <p data-bbox="667 493 1895 564">“Experiential attitude or affect is the individual’s emotional response to the idea of performing a recommended behavior” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 78).</p>
5.2.2 Instrumental attitude	<p data-bbox="667 579 1473 608">“Overall evaluation of the behavior” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 74).</p> <p data-bbox="667 620 1883 692">“Instrumental attitude is cognitively based, determined by beliefs about outcomes of behavioral performance” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 78).</p>
6 Perceived social norm-related	Perceived social norms and related beliefs.
6.1 Subjective/Injunctive norm	<p data-bbox="667 790 1957 903">“A person’s subjective norm is determined by his or her normative beliefs, that is, whether important referent individuals approve or disapprove of performing the behavior, weighted by his or her motivation to comply with those referents” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 71).</p> <p data-bbox="667 917 1957 946">“Belief about whether most people approve or disapprove of the behavior” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 74).</p>
6.2 Descriptive norm	<p data-bbox="667 960 1957 1029">Descriptive norms are “perceptions about what others in one’s social or personal networks are doing” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 79).</p> <p data-bbox="667 1043 1742 1074">“Belief about whether most people perform the behavior” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 74).</p>
7 Personal agency-related	<p data-bbox="667 1088 1727 1117">This theme includes perceived behavioral control, self-efficacy, and related beliefs.</p> <p data-bbox="667 1131 1957 1283">“The term agency has been used by various writers to refer to the self’s exertion of volition, but this term has misleading connotations; An agent is quintessentially someone who acts on behalf of someone else, whereas the phenomenon under discussion involves the self acting autonomously on its own behalf” (Baumeister et al., 1998, p. 1252).</p>
7.1 Perceived behavioral	“Perceived control is determined by control beliefs concerning the presence or absence of facilitators

Theme/Sub-theme	Explanation of synthesis themes
control	and barriers to behavioral performance, weighted by their perceived power or the impact of each control factor to facilitate or inhibit the behavior” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 71). “Perceived behavioral control refers to people’s perception of the ease or difficulty of performing the behavior of interest” (Ajzen, 1991, p. 183), and the presence or absence of resources and opportunities (Ajzen, 1991, p. 196–197).
7.2 Self-efficacy	“Perceived self-efficacy is defined as people’s beliefs about their capabilities to produce designated levels of performance that exercise influence over events that affect their lives” (Bandura, 1994).
8 Personal norm-related	Personal norms and related beliefs, including behavior patterns, stands, and goals.
9 Stimuli-related	Stimuli come from internal or external body, which could cause human physiological and psychological perception and even trigger behavior, such as a light blow upon the patellar tendon of the knee, hungry, imaginative input.
9.1 Cues	Cues are discriminative stimuli that could trigger the behavior.
10 Consciousness-dominant process	Consciousness processes and intermediate variables.
10.1 Attribution	“An attribution is a causal explanation for an event or behavior” (Harvey & Martinko, 2009, p. 147). “Attribution is a dynamic process that is continually updated with experience” (Weiner, 1985).
10.2 Decision/Choice	“A complex process of transforming options into actions by making choices based on some metric that represents the importance of these options to an individual” (Paulus & Angela, 2012. p. 483). “People make decisions by setting goals, compiling goal-directed options, and evaluating these options” (Byrnes et al., 1999, p. 1122).
10.3 Memory	There are different kinds of memory, such as working memory and long-term memory. “Long-term memory can be separated into declarative (explicit) memory and a collection of nondeclarative (implicit) forms of memory that include habits, skills, priming, and simple forms of conditioning” (Squire & Dede, 2015, p. 1).
10.4 Reason	“Reasons are defined as the specific subjective factors people use to explain their anticipated behavior”

Theme/Sub-theme	Explanation of synthesis themes
10.5 Resources	<p>(Westaby, 2005, p. 100).</p> <p>“It is presumed in behavioral reasoning theory that ‘reasons’ often possess motivational power even when they are biased (e.g., biased reasons would motivate irrational behaviors, while unbiased reasons would motivate rational behaviors)” (Westaby et al., 2010, p. 483).</p> <hr/> <p>“Choice, active response, self-regulation, and other volition may all draw on a common inner resource” (Baumeister et al., 1998, p. 1252).</p> <p>“The resource functions to connect abstract principles, standards, and intentions to overt behavior. It has some link to physical tiredness but is not the same as it” (Baumeister et al., 1998, p. 1263).</p> <p>“There exists a resource that the self uses for a broad variety of volitional activities” (Baumeister et al., 2000, p. 131).</p> <hr/>
10.6 Self-regulation 10.6.1 General process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="667 703 1995 1359">• Perspective of function: <p>“Self-regulation, broadly speaking, is the propensity of a person to invest cognitive, emotional, and behavioural resources to achieve a desired goal or outcome” (Hagger et al., 2009, p. 2).</p> <p>“Self-regulation can be defined as a sequence of actions and/or steering processes intended to attain a personal goal. In other words, self-regulation consists of the individual’s attempt to control his or her own behavior over time and across contexts to achieve self-chosen goals” (Maes & Gebhardt, 2000, p. 344).</p> <p>“Self-regulation is the process used to adjust performance as an individual works toward identified behavioural goals within a specific context. This process occurs on two levels: complex or unfamiliar tasks use consciously directed self-regulation involving executive processing, while more automatic, familiar tasks forgo this additional dispensation” (Hunt et al., 2013, p. 919).</p> <p>“These self-regulatory systems can be viewed as interconnected cybernetic control loops operating at physiologic, cognitive, and social levels” (Ewart, 1991, p. 932).</p> <li data-bbox="667 1246 1995 1359">• Perspective of resource: <p>“Self-regulation is conceptualized as a limited resource that once depleted results in reduced capacity to further regulate the self” (Hagger et al., 2009, p. 2).</p> <hr/>

Theme/Sub-theme	Explanation of synthesis themes
10.6.2 Self-monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perspective of capacity: “Self-regulatory capacity, on the other hand, can be defined as any state- or trait-like factor that affects an individual’s capacity to effortfully regulate their own behavior (e.g., executive function, energy level)” (Hall & Fong, 2007, p. 15). • Perspective of construct: “Self-regulation appears to be an overarching construct that utilises executive functions” (Hunt et al., 2013, p. 920). Self-regulation is a central construct influenced by executive functions in rehabilitation literature (Toglia et al., 2010). • Similar concepts: “Self-control is one aspect of wider self-regulation” (West & Brown, 2013, p. 108). “Trait self-control is defined as an individual’s general capacity to override impulses, resist temptations, break habits, and overturn the ‘dominant response’” (Fujita, 2011; de Ridder et al., 2012; Tangney et al., 2004, as cited in Hagger et al., 2019, p. 4).
10.6.3 Judgment process	<hr/> <p>“Self- regulation is the process used to change health behavior and includes activities such as goal setting, self-monitoring and reflective thinking, decision making, planning for and engaging in specific behaviors, and self-evaluating and self-managing physical, emotional, and cognitive responses associated with health behavior change” (Ryan, 2009, p. 5).</p>
10.6.4 Self-reaction	
10.6.5 Self-reflective	
10.6.6 Feedback	
10.6.7 Goal guidance/setting	<p>“By ‘self-regulatory processes’ we mean the monitoring, appraisal, and coping activities that translate 1) attitudes into intentions, 2) subjective norms into intentions, and 3) intentions into actions leading to goal attainment” (Bagozzi, 1992, p. 183).</p>
10.6.8 Planning	<hr/> <p>“For all self-regulated activities, feedback is an inherent catalyst” (Butler & Winne, 1995, p. 246).</p>
10.6.9 Plans/Strategies	<hr/> <p>“Strategies function as action guides for specific situations and range from simple if-then rules used without active awareness” (Linville & Clark, 1989, as cited in Ewart, 1991, p. 935) to “carefully constructed constellations of thoughts, feelings, and actions that help an actor regulate arousal, exert control over outcomes, make choices, and persist in the face of difficult obstacles” (Dweck &</p> <hr/>

Theme/Sub-theme	Explanation of synthesis themes
10.6.10 Emotional regulation 10.6.11 Cognitive regulation 10.6.12 Motivational regulation 10.6.13 Behavior regulation	<p>Leggett, 1988; Kihlstrom, 1987; Langer, 1989, as cited in Ewart, 1991, p. 935).</p> <p>“Planning is a prospective self-regulatory strategy, a mental simulation of linking concrete responses to future situations” (Sniehotta et al., 2005, p. 566).</p> <hr/> <p>“It [self-regulation] has been defined as a complex interactive process involving not only cognitive self-regulation but also motivational self-regulation” (Boekaerts, 1997, p. 161).</p> <p>“Central to SCT [Social Cognitive Theory] is the idea that people are capable of self-regulation their thoughts, emotions, motivation, and actions” (Nabavi, 2012, p. 17).</p> <p>“The term self-regulating refers not only to the fact that the system can operate to achieve identified goals, but to the fact that what is being regulated is the physical machinery and functional resources of the self. The goals for self-regulation are the concrete, perceptual experiences, the physical sensations or symptoms, moods and emotions, and feelings of vigor and competence generated by the biological and psychological self” (Leventhal et al., 2003, p. 44).</p> <p>“Capacity of self-regulation is one of the most important factors in professional decision making and can eliminate the negative impact of anxiety on work achievement, including decision making” (Baumann et al., 2001, as cited in Halama, 2017, p. 158).</p>
11 Objective Capability	<p>The quality of being capable includes objectively owned abilities (not subjective perception), implied abilities, or abilities that have not been developed but can be learned.</p> <p>“Capability is defined as the individual’s psychological and physical capacity to engage in the activity concerned. It includes having the necessary knowledge and skills” (Michie et al., 2011, p. 4).</p>
11.1 Competence	<p>“Social competence is the product of a wide range of cognitive abilities, emotional processes, behavioral skills, social awareness, and personal and cultural values related to interpersonal relationships” (Orpinas, 2010, p. 1623).</p>
11.2 Executive function	<p>“The term ‘executive functions’ refers to a fairly broad group of neurocognitive processes that support higher level cognitive and metacognitive functions” (Bol & Garner, 2011, p. 114), such as goal setting, planning, self-regulatory processes, self-monitoring, flexibly regulate goal-directed actions, organize pieces of information, impulse control, problem solving, and decision making (Bol &</p>

Theme/Sub-theme	Explanation of synthesis themes
11.3 Behavioral knowledge and skills	<p>Garner, 2011; Levine et al., 2008).</p> <p>There are overlaps between executive function and self-regulation definitions, such as monitoring, inhibiting, and planning functions (Cicerone et al., 2006, p. 1213).</p> <p>Executive function is “the set of higher-order cognitive processes that allow control of behaviors essential to learning and carrying out tasks, and contribute to the supervision and regulation of these behaviors. Furthermore, they do not only influence the control exercised by executive function in the cognitive field, but also in socio-emotional and behavioral domains” (Miriam et al., 2018, p. 491).</p> <hr/> <p>Knowledge and skills required to complete specific behaviors.</p> <p>“The skill involved may be so specialized, so unrelated to general experience, that even though the person has learned a lot, he performs the same in this specialized area” (McClelland, 1973, p. 8).</p>
12 Reinforcement	<p>“Reinforcement is a term in operant conditioning theory and behavior analysis for process of increasing the rate or probability of behavior, in the form of response delivered shortly after performing the behavior” (Kinyanjui et al., 2015, p. 267).</p> <p>“Reinforcement is a powerful method for regulating behaviors that have already been learned, it is a relatively inefficient way of creating them” (Bandura, 1977b, p. 5).</p>
13 Subconsciousness-dominant process (It does not exclude conscious processes.)	<p>Subconsciousness-dominant processes and intermediate variables, take impulsive system as an example:</p> <p>“The impulsive system can be understood as a system of experiential primacy, in which affective and nonaffective feelings are generated quickly and without syllogistic processes of inference” (Strack & Deutsch, 2004, p. 222).</p> <p>“The impulsive system has low flexibility but is fast and needs no attentional resources” (Strack & Deutsch, 2004, p. 224).</p> <p>“The impulsive system requires little cognitive capacity and may control behavior under suboptimal conditions” (Strack & Deutsch, 2004, p. 223).</p>
13.1 Instinct	<p>Instinct is a natural or inherent behavior pre-programmed into an animal’s genes without learning. The most important difference between reflex and instinct is that “a reflex is an immediate reaction</p>

Theme/Sub-theme	Explanation of synthesis themes
13.2 Habit	<p>which does not involve awareness [cerebrum], while an instinct is an immediate reaction which does involve awareness [cerebrum]" (Menasheof, 2019, pp. 1–2).</p> <p>Reflexes do not change, while instincts change during a person’s life (Menasheof, 2019, p. 1).</p> <p>The chain reflex theory of instinct viewed instincts as complex sequences of reflexes (Brigandt, 2005).</p> <p>“Lorenz viewed instincts as innate motor patterns or what ethologists later called fixed action patterns” (Brigandt, 2005, p. 8).</p> <hr/> <p>“Behavioral schemata and their links to other contents in the impulsive system can be understood as habits” (Strack & Deutsch, 2004, p. 229).</p> <p>“Habits develop by satisfactorily repeating behaviour in stable contexts. When a person repeatedly faces the same behavioural choice in the same situation, and thus repeats his or her previous response, associations build up between the cues that define the context and this person’s response” (Verplanken, 2006, p. 640).</p> <p>“Habits are actions performed automatically with little forethought or effort, and which persist over time. Habits form through repeated performance of an action in the same setting” (Gardner & Wardle, 2012, p. 664).</p> <p>“The term ‘habit’ has been used to describe actions that, because of associative learning, have become to a large degree under the control of non-conscious forces” (West & Brown, 2013, p. 209).</p> <p>“Habits are but chains of conditioned reflexes. Pavlov says: ‘It is obvious that the different kinds of habits based on training, education, and discipline are nothing more than a long chain of condition”” (Gantt, 1932, p. 517).</p>
13.3 Associative constructs	<hr/> <p>The following are several items within this theme:</p> <p>Precursors: factors or processes that precede and trigger impulsive behavior.</p> <p>Behavioral schema:</p> <p>Behavioral schemas belong to a person’s knowledge base (Selden et al., 2010, p. 7).</p> <p>“When viewed in a large grain-size, behavioral schemas might also be regarded as habits of mind” (Selden et al., 2010, p. 7).</p> <hr/>

Theme/Sub-theme	Explanation of synthesis themes
	<p>“We regard <situation, action> pairs that occur regularly as the enactment of enduring mental structures that we call behavioral schemas” (Selden et al., 2010, p. 7).</p> <p>“Behavioral schemas are acquired (learned) through habituation. That is, to acquire such a schema a person should carry out the appropriate action correctly a number of times” (Selden et al., 2010, p. 8).</p> <p>Associative store:</p> <p>“The associative store of the impulsive system works like a simple memory system” (Johnson & Hirst, 1991, as cited in Strack & Deutsch, 2004, pp. 223–224), “which slowly forms enduring, nonpropositional representations of the typical properties of the environment over many learning trials” (McClelland et al., 1995; Smith & DeCoster, 2000, as cited in Strack & Deutsch, 2004, pp. 223–224).</p>
14 Behavior/Response	<p>This theme includes behavior change, maintenance, response, and related attributes.</p> <p>“Anything an individual does in response to internal or external events” (Kwasnicka et al., 2016, p. 280).</p>
14.1 Change	Changes in habits or behaviors.
14.2 Maintenance	Maintenance of behavior change.
14.3 Response	Response refers specifically to reflex behavior (conditioned reflex and unconditioned reflex).
15 Related behavior	<p>Based on the characteristics of time, space and function, there are four types of behaviors related to the target behavior:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Antecedent behaviors provide the necessary preparations for the target behavior (e.g., buying sneakers in advance for running). • Clustered behaviors happen at the same time. “Epidemiologists label the co-occurrence of behaviors as ‘clustering’ if a combination of behaviors is more prevalent than can be expected on the basis of the prevalence of the separate behaviors, e.g., consuming potato chips while watching TV” (Kremers et al., 2006, p. 6). • Competitive behaviors compete with target behaviors for resources to lead people to nontarget behaviors.

Theme/Sub-theme	Explanation of synthesis themes
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same/Similar behaviors are inherently same or similar behaviors, e.g. “smoking marijuana might provide experiences which affect a person’s knowledge about drug use in general, and consequently contribute to future cocaine use” (Flay & Petraitis, 1994, p. 39).
16 Behavior outcome	It is the result of behavior which includes internal changes (physical or psychological) or external changes (environmental).
17 Experience	Experience includes direct experience and vicarious experience.
17.1 Direct experience	“The experience that acquired from the behavior of directly interacting with the environment. Repeated experience will have resulted in individuals’ storing a strong mental representation or schema of the action in memory and the presentation of cues that activate the schema will lead to efficient behavioral enactment bypassing deliberative routes to action” (Hagger & Chatzisarantis, 2014, p. 66).
17.2 Vicarious experience	“A vicarious experience is an empathetic state in response to the observation of others’ sensations, emotions, and actions” (Rothen & Meier, 2013, p. 1).
	“Vicarious experiences provide information about modeled attainments of others, which influence one’s self-efficacy beliefs by demonstrating and transferring competencies (model learning) and by providing a point of reference for social comparison” (Pfitzner-Eden, 2016, p. 2).
18 Personal state	Personal short-term psychological and physiological state.
18.1 Psychological state	E.g., belief, attitude, intention, emotion, and mood. Some of them appear separately in the preceding themes because of their importance to behavior.
18.1.1 Emotion	“Emotions are an integral part of a person’s internal state” (Paulus & Angela, 2012, p. 476).
	“Emotions are intense feelings that are directed at someone or something” (Frijda, 1993, as cited in Hume, 2012, p. 260).
	“Emotion is an innate, powerful, and principally unconscious process” (Sylwester, 2000, p. 20).
18.1.2 Mood	“Moods, as compared to emotions, are thought to be less intense, of longer duration and lack specificity with regard to a particular object or behavioral response” (Weiss & Cropanzano, 1996).
18.2 Physiological state	E.g., arousal state, fatigue, and short term illness

Theme/Sub-theme	Explanation of synthesis themes
19 Individual difference	<p>Individual differences involve three major domains: “(a) knowledge, skill, and ability, including both the cognitive and physical domains; (b) personality, including integrity, emotional intelligence, stable motivational attributes (e.g., achievement motivation, core self-evaluations), and creativity; and (c) vocational interests” (Sackett et al., 2017, p. 1).</p> <p>Individual difference is generally reserved for attributes nearer the “stable” end of the continuum in which variables of individual differences are arrayed from stable to transitory (Sackett et al., 2017, p. 1).</p>
19.1 Self-concept	<p>“We are able to form mental representations of ourselves [self-concept]. These constitute our ‘identity’ or ‘self’. Like other mental representations, they come into existence when attention is drawn to them, vary over time, vary in how coherent and well defined they are, and involve evaluations, emotional states and motives” (West & Brown, 2013, p. 213).</p> <p>“Our identities (thoughts, images and feelings and feelings about ourselves) can be a powerful source of motives and involve labels (the categories we think we belong to), attributes (the features we ascribe to ourselves) and personal rules (imperatives about what we do and do not do)” (West & Brown, 2013, p. 227).</p>
19.2 Physiological/Biological factors	<p>Factors related to physical/physiological/ biological, e.g., gender, genetic predisposition (De Vries et al., 2005, p. 156), explosive strength, and cardiovascular endurance (Sackett et al., 2017, p. 4).</p>
19.3 Psychological factors	<p>Factors related to mental (cognitive, emotional) processes, e.g., personality (De Vries et al., 2005, p156), pessimistic, depressed, knowledge, and values.</p>
19.3.1 Value	<p>“Values also are more central than attitudes. Because values are relatively central, value change is postulated to lead to widespread changes in functionally related values, attitudes, and behaviors” (Grube et al., 1994, p. 155).</p> <p>A value is “an enduring belief that a specific mode of conduct or end-state of existence is personally or socially preferable to an opposite or converse mode of conduct or end-state of existence” (Rokeach, 1973, p. 5).</p>

Theme/Sub-theme	Explanation of synthesis themes
	<p>“Values are standards that guide our ongoing activities and help us to resolve conflicts and make decisions” (Greenfield, 2006, p. 175).</p> <p>“Values represent judgment of what is important to an individual or group of individuals” (McGinnis et al., 2016, p. 1418).</p>
19.4 Social-cultural factors	Factors related to social-cultural, e.g., race, ethnicity, and socioeconomics.
19.5 Behavioral styles	Factors related to behavioral Style, e.g., unhealthy life style.
20 Environment	Environment refers to the surroundings or conditions where people live, including the physical and social environment.
20.1 Behavior setting	“Behaviour settings provide a powerful tool for conceptualising how behaviour is situated in a particular environmental context—in time, in space and in society” (Aunger & Curtis, 2016, p. 7).
20.2 Physical environment	The physical environment includes natural and human environments with physical factors, e.g., weather, building, soil, and water supply.
20.3 Social environment	“Human social environments encompass the immediate physical surroundings, social relationships, and cultural milieus within which defined groups of people function and interact” (Barnett & Casper, 2001, p. 465), e.g., family, school, work settings, community, economics, culture, and political environments. “The social environment subsumes many aspects of the physical environment” (Barnett & Casper, 2001, p. 465), because human social processes partially configure them.
20.4 Biological environment	The biological environment refers to the complex web of interactions and relationships among species (Aunger & Curtis, 2014a).
21 Process/Mechanism	The processes, mechanisms and related concepts involved in behavior change and maintenance, such as social support.
21.1 Environment affects people	Processes or results of interaction between people and environment.
21.2 People affect the environment	

Theme/Sub-theme	Explanation of synthesis themes
22 Stages-related	“Behavior change is a process that unfolds over time through a sequence of stages” (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 103).
23 Time	Perception of time
Other definitions	Other definitions that do not belong to the synthesis themes, but are beneficial for understanding the themes and integrated framework.
Behavior unit	Behavior unit refers to automatic behaviors or reactions that do not need consciousness or only need subconscious guidance, including unconditioned reflex, instinct, conditioned reflex and habit.
Unconditioned response	<p>Unconditioned reflex is a response that occurs to an unconditioned stimulus, naturally, automatically and without thought.</p> <p>“The response that is elicited by the presentation of the US [unconditioned stimulus] is termed the unconditioned response (UR). The term ‘unconditioned’ is used to indicate that the response is ‘not learned’, but rather it is an innate or reflexive response to the US” (Clark, 2004, p. 279).</p>
Instinct/Fixed action pattern	<p>Fixed action pattern is “an inherited relatively complex movement pattern within instinctive behavior, which is as characteristic of the species or group as are structural features. The intensity of its discharge may vary, but its form is little, if at all, modifiable by external stimuli” (Thorpe, 1951, as cited in Schleidt, 1974, pp. 184–185).</p> <p>“Fixed action patterns depended on the linkage of unconditioned reflexes” (Lorenz, 1981, p. 6).</p> <p>Also see 4.2</p>
Conditioned response	<p>“The theory of classical conditioning aims to account for the way in which reflex behavior may become associated with a new stimulus that does not naturally activate that behavior. It emphasizes the importance of stimulus conditions and the associations formed in the learning process” (Lemma, 2005, p. 85).</p> <p>“According to this model of learning, a neutral stimulus (NS), a stimulus that has no particular value or meaning to the learner is paired with a naturally occurring unconditioned or unlearned stimulus (UCS) and unconditioned response” (UCR; Lemma, 2005, p. 85).</p> <p>“The term ‘conditioned’ is used to indicate that the response is ‘learned’” (Clark, 2004, p. 279).</p>

Appendix E

Studies Excluded From the Selection

Study	Exclusion criterion
Acceptance Commitment Model/Therapy (ACM; ACT; Hayes, 2004, 2005; Hayes et al., 2006, 2012; Pearson, 2006)	b
Action model of consumption (Bagozzi, 2000)	a
Adaptive decision-making framework (Zhang et al., 2021)	c
Adherence Improving Management Strategy (AIMS; Bruin et al., 2005)	b
Adult learning approach (Vella, 1995)	a
Advance care planning (ACP; Sudore et al. 2008)	b
Affect influence habits (Weyland et al., 2020)	c
Affective Events Theory (AET; Weiss, 1996)	a
Alcohol Behavioral Couple Therapy (ABCT; McCrady et al., 2019).	b
Authoritative parenting model (APM; Brukienė & Aleksejūnienė, 2012)	b
Avoiding Diabetes Thru Action Plan Targeting (ADAPT) program (Lin & Mann, 2012)	b
Behavioral activation treatment (Jacobson et al., 2001)	b
Behavioral decision theory (Edwards, 1961; Slovic et al., 1977)	a
Behavioral economics (Hursh, 1984; Thaler, 2016)	a
Behavioral substitution (Garnett et al., 2018)	b
Behavior-Image Model (BIM; Werch, 2007)	b
Behavioural-ecological model of adolescent sexual development (Hovell et al., 1994)	c
Biobehavioral family model (BFM; Wood & Miller, 2002)	b
Biological control theory (Murdoch et al., 1985)	a
Bounded rationality (Simon, 1957)	a
Carey communication model (Carey, 2008)	a

Study	Exclusion criterion
Causal modelling approach (Hardeman, 2005)	b
Chronic care management framework (Wagner et al., 1998)	b
Chronic care model (Hartmann et al., 2007; Van Gaalen et al., 2013)	b
Chronic disease self-management model (Lorig, 1996)	b
Clinical staging model (Gonnella et al., 1984; Scott & Henry, 2017)	b
Cognitive adaptation theory (Taylor, 1983)	a
Cognitive behavioral therapy (Freeman & Ronen, 2006; Gaudiano, 2008; Hofmann et al., 2012)	b
Cognitive-experiential self-theory (CEST; Epstein, 2003)	a
Communication accommodation theory (CAT; Dragojevic et al., 2015)	a
Comprehensive Children's Aid Society Carrera Model (CCM; Philliber et al., 2001)	b
Comprehensive intervention model using the mobile health system (CIMmH; Cheng et al., 2020)	b
Comprehensive Messaging Strategy for Sustained Behavior Change (CMSSBC; Pope et al., 2018)	b
Comprehensive Model of Addiction (CMA, including vulnerability model and maintenance/craving model; Gori et al., 2021, 2023)	c
Conceptual model for dietary behaviour change (Daivadanam et al., 2014)	b
Conceptual model to underpin intervention development (Combes et al., 2019)	b
Conscious competence model (Keeley, 2021)	a
Consumer information processing (Rudd, 1990)	a
Consumption of social practices (Spaargaren & Van Vliet, 2000)	a
Containment theory (Reckless, 1961)	a
Contemplation-action-maintenance model (Yue et al., 2021)	c
Contextual model of (domestic) consumption (Spaargaren & Van Vliet, 2000)	a
Contraceptive behavior change model (Chung-Park, 2008)	b
Decisional balance (Aloia et al., 2001)	b
Decision-Theoretic Model of behavior change (DTM, Matsumori et al., 2019)	c
Demand-control model (job strain model; Karasek, 1979)	a

Study	Exclusion criterion
Deterrent theory (Schneider & Ervin, 1990)	a
Diabetes prevention program (Diabetes Prevention Program Research Group, 2002)	b
Differential association theory (Sutherland et al., 1992)	a
Disconnected values model (Anshel, 2008)	b
Dual process model of alcohol-behavior link (Moss & Albery, 2009)	c
Early intensive behavioral intervention (EIBI; Lovaas, 1987)	b
Eden Decision Model (Gerhardt & Holmes, 1994)	a
Effort-reward imbalance (Siegrist, 1996)	a
eHealth behavior management model (Bensley et al., 2004)	b
Empowerment programs (Arnold et al., 1995)	b
Family empowerment model (Koren et al., 1992)	b
Family resilience approach (Walsh, 2016)	b
Fast and frugal way (Gigerenzer & Goldstein, 1996)	a
Fear and recommendation on attitudes and behavior (Leventhal et al., 1965)	c
Field theory (Lewin, 1935)	c
Five A's model (Sherson et al., 2014)	b
Fluid vulnerability theory (Rudd, 2006)	a
Gender equality continuum (Interagency Gender Working Group, 2017)	a
Gender transformative programming (Ruane-McAteer et al., 2020)	b
General theory of crime (Gottfredson & Hirschi, 1990)	a
General theory of deviant behavior (Kaplan, 1982)	a
Gestalt counseling model (nutritional education; Campos et al., 2009)	b
Goal framing theory (Lindenberg & Steg, 2007)	a
Graphic model (Kelly, 2014)	c
Group lifestyle balance (Kramer et al., 2009; Ross et al., 2019)	b
Group motivational interviewing for teens (GMIT; Moreno et al., 2022)	b

Study	Exclusion criterion
Habit reversal training (Azrin & Nunn, 1973; Bate et al., 2011; Piacentini & Chang, 2006)	b
Health behaviour change competency framework (HBCCF; Dixon & Johnston, 2020)	b
Health capital theory (Grossman, 1972)	a
Health coaching / motivational Interviewing (Huffman, 2007; Miller & Rollnick, 2012; Miller & Rose, 2009)	b
Health information avoidance change model (HIACM; Sun et al., 2022)	c
Healthy weight for living (HWL; Das et al., 2021)	b
Hierarchy of effects (HOE model; McGuire, 1984)	c
Incentive-Sensitization Theory (Robinson & Berridge, 1993)	a
Information-Motivation-Strategy (IMS) model (DiMatteo et al., 2012)	b
Instructional theory (Shegog et al., 2006)	a
Integrated theoretical model for alcohol and drug prevention (Gonzalez, 1989)	c
Integrated theory of drinking behaviour (Wagenaar & Perry, 1994)	c
Integration of Freire and protection motivation theory (Wallerstein & Sanchez-Merki, 1994)	b
Integrative model of coach behavior (Behrendt et al., 2016)	a
Integrative model of the determinants of the effectiveness of organizational implementation (Klein & Sorra, 1996)	a
Intentional social action framework (Bagozzi, 2000)	a
Intersectoral Health and Environment Research for InnovaTion (INHERIT) Model (Van der Vliet et al., 2018)	a
Intervention mapping (Bartholomew et al., 1998; Shegog et al., 2001)	b
Kaufman HIV behavior change model (Kaufman et al., 2014)	c
Learning theory perspective on lapse, relapse, and the maintenance of behavior change (Bouton, 2000)	c
Life skills theory/training (Jackson et al., 2012; MacArthur et al., 2018; Underhill et al., 2008)	b
Media advocacy (Wallack, 1990)	b
Medical Research Council (MRC) framework (Craig et al., 2008)	b
Medication adherence model (Johnson, 2002)	c
Model of engagement in medical rehabilitation (Lequerica & Kortte, 2010)	c
Model of motivational design (Keller, 1979, 1983)	b

Study	Exclusion criterion
Model of proactive and reactive control (Amodio & Swencionis, 2018)	a
Model of pro-environmental behaviour (Kollmuss & Agyeman, 2002)	a
Modified diabetes prevention program (Durán et al., 2021; Geria & Beitz, 2018)	b
Motivational enhancement therapy (Miller, 1992)	b
Motivational interviewing (Miller, 1983)	b
Motivation-Opportunities-Abilities (MOA) model (Ölander & Thøgersen, 1995)	a
Motivation-Volition (MoVo) process model (Fuchs et al., 2011)	c
Multi-level/multi-media model of social change (Dresler-Hawke & Veer, 2006)	c
Multi-process action control approach (Rhodes, 2017)	c
Multisystemic therapy (MST; Henggeler et al., 2009)	b
Needs-opportunities-abilities model (Gatersleben & Vlek, 1998)	a
Needs acquisition and behavior change model (Caplan, 2008)	b
Net-present value economic theory (Wight et al., 1998)	a
Network diffusion model (Broadhead et al., 1998; Kelly et al., 1992; Latkin et al., 2003; Weeks et al., 2009)	a
Norm activation model (Schwartz, 1977)	c
Norma engaging multimedia design (NEMD; Wyatt et al., 2013)	a
Normalisation process theory (May & Finch, 2009; May et al., 2009)	a
Nurturing Care Groups Model (NCG model; Forbes et al., 2023)	b
Operant theory of acculturation (Landrine & Klonoff, 2004)	a
Operation of the basal ganglia (Graybiel, 1995, 2005)	a
Organizational change theory (Cummings & Worley, 2014)	a
Parent Behavior Change Intervention (PBC-I; Dong et al., 2020)	b
Patient navigator model (Rahm et al., 2007)	b
Pavlovian instrumental transfer (Corbit & Balleine, 2005)	c
Personalised normative feedback (Kilwein et al., 2017; Neighbors et al., 2015)	b
Person-situation contingency model (Fiedler, 1971)	c

Study	Exclusion criterion
Persuasive systems design model (Oinas-Kukkonen & Harjuma, 2009)	b
Population-based health promotion model (McKinlay, 1995)	b
PRECEDE-PROCEED Model (Green & Kreuter, 2005)	b
Pressure system model (Katz, 2001)	b
Process model of lifestyle behavior change (Greaves et al., 2010)	c
Rational-emotive behavior therapy (Sherin & Caiger, 2004)	b
RE-AIM framework (Glasgow et al., 1999)	b
Reflective practice approach (Anderson et al., 2004)	a
Reinforcement learning (RL) theory (Sutton & Barto, 1998)	a
Relational ethics (Downing et al., 2011)	a
Relative deprivation (Stouffer et al., 1949)	a
Risk Communication Framework (Brown et al., 2011)	a
Role playing (Boies, 1972)	b
Screening and brief interventions (SBI; Rosário et al., 2022)	b
Selection, optimisation and compensation model (Baltes, 1997)	a
Self-confrontation method (Greenstein, 1976; Lyddon et al., 2006)	b
Self-regulatory theories (Boekaerts, 1997)	a
Shared decision-making (SDM; Edwards et al., 2004; Shay & Lafata, 2015)	b
Six staged model of communication effects (Vaughan & Rogers, 2000)	c
Social change theory (Thompson & Kinne, 1990)	a
Social change theory of dialogue and praxis (Papa et al., 2006)	a
Social control theory / social bond theory (German, 2009)	a
Social development model (Hawkins & Weis, 1985)	a
Social ecological model of walking (Alfonzo, 2005)	c
Social influence model of consumer participation (Dholakia et al., 2004)	a
Social inoculation theory (Evans & Neighbors, 2014)	b

Study	Exclusion criterion
Social judgment theory (Sherif et al., 1965)	a
Social marketing (Storey et al., 2008)	b
Social theory (Giddens, 1979)	a
Socioeconomic model (Hellmich, 2015)	a
Structural model of health behavior (Cohen et al., 2000)	c
Systems model of health behaviour change (Kersell & Milsum, 1985)	c
Tailoring (Joseph et al., 2010)	b
Technology acceptance model 1 (Davis, 1989)	a
Technology acceptance model 2 (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000)	a
Technology acceptance model 3 (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008)	a
Terror management health model (Goldenberg et al., 2008)	c
Terror management theory (TMT; Greenberg et al., 1986)	a
Theoretical framework for behavior change (Burnet et al., 2002)	c
Theory of group-mediated social control (Heckathorn, 1990)	a
Theory of psychotherapy, of personality, and of interpersonal relationships (Rogers, 1957)	b
Three-factor model (Barnes & Mongrain, 2015)	a
Transcontextual model of motivation (Hagger et al., 2003)	c
Transformative gender justice framework (Keddie, 2005)	a
Transmission Reduction Intervention Project (TRIP; Friedman, 2013)	b
Trust and confidence model (Siegrist et al., 2003)	a
Two-factor avoidance theory (Stasiewicz & Maisto, 1993)	c
Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (Venkatesh et al., 2003)	a
Unintentional behaviour change (Aunger & Curtis, 2014b)	b
Value-belief-norm (VBN) theory (Stern et al., 1999)	a
Voluntary counseling and testing (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2001)	b
Voluntary family planning programs (Rodriguez et al., 2013)	b

Study	Exclusion criterion
Wahls Behavior Change Model (WBCM; Elliott-Wherry et al., 2022)	c
Wellness-group (WG) model (Axten et al., 2017)	b
Young's early maladaptive schemas theory (Jesinoski, 2010)	a

Note. The letters “a,” “b,” and “c” in the second column indicate the reasons for exclusion. The “a” stands for the studies about non-human, non-health-related behaviors, or non-specific theories; the “b” stands for the strategies, technologies, treatments, or approaches for a specific program or scene; the “c” stands for the immature or variant theories. To facilitate readers in searching and reading relevant literature, some different spellings (e.g., “behavior” and “behaviour,” “organization” and “organisation”) are consistent with the original references.

Appendix F

Detailed Overview of the Framework

Model 1: Temporal Model of Reciprocal Determinism (Figure 3)

Reciprocal Causation Relationship

In Figure 3, paths 1, 3, and 5 represent the interaction between people and behavior. People influence behavior, as articulated by Bandura (1989), who states that “what people think, believe, and feel, affects how they behave” (p. 3). This interaction is closely linked to an individual’s physiological and psychological attributes. Considering physiological properties, for example, Bandura (1989) notes that “physical structure and sensory and neural systems affect behavior and impose constraints on capabilities” (p. 3). Conversely, sensory systems and brain structures can be modified through behavioral experiences (Greenough et al., 1987). Regarding psychological properties, such as attitudes, self-efficacy, and emotions, they serve not only as factors promoting behavior but also as outcomes of behavior. In other words, behavior also contributes to shaping individuals. As Ronen (2007) aptly puts it, “People make their own realities by constructing, reconstructing, and construing their life events and by attributing personal meanings to their experiences” (p. 14).

Paths 2, 4, and 6 illustrate the “two-way influence between behavior and the environment” (Bandura, 1989, p. 4). As Bandura

(1989) explains, “In the transactions of everyday life, behavior alters environmental conditions and is, in turn, altered by the very conditions it creates” (p. 4).

Path 7 delves into the interactive relationship between individuals and their surroundings. According to Bandura (1986, as cited in Bandura, 1989), “Human expectations, beliefs, emotional bents and cognitive competencies are developed and modified by social influences that convey information and activate emotional reactions through modeling, instruction and social persuasion” (p. 3). In turn, individuals “activate different social reactions depending on their socially conferred roles and status” (Bandura, 1989, p. 3), thereby influencing their social environment. Similarly, the physical environment serves not only as the physical setting for human existence but is also continuously shaped by human activities. In summary, “people are both products and producers of their environment” (Bandura, 1989, p. 4).

Paths 3, 4, and 7 depict the ongoing interactive process. The proximal factors influencing behavior include an individual's current state and the context in which the behavior occurs, often referred to as the *behavior setting* (Barker, 1968). Distal factors, such as individual differences and the broader environment (not the immediate behavior setting), indirectly impact behavior through these proximal factors. The concept of behavior setting situates behavior within a specific environmental context, encompassing elements of time, space, and

society (Barker, 1968). Over time and across various activity scenarios, behavior settings dynamically change, exerting varying influence on behavior.

Behavior Trajectory

As illustrated in Figure 3, time (indicated by arrow A) serves as the horizontal axis, whereas the spectrum of activities within the environment (denoted by double arrow B) constitutes the vertical dimension. The dynamic interplay between individuals and their ever-changing behavior setting (depicted as circle C) occurs through the medium of behavior. This intricate process gives rise to an interaction trajectory (represented by the curved line D with an arrow) within the coordinate system, which is defined as the *behavior trajectory*. Each individual possesses a unique behavior trajectory that actively shapes both their environment and personal attributes, moving from the past to the present (Path 8) and toward the future (Path 9).

Model 2: Behavior Unit Model (Figure 4)

Stimuli

BU are triggered by stimuli, which can originate from various sources: the external environment (e.g., food aroma; Path 1), the internal organism (e.g., hunger disrupts the balance or homeostasis and triggers people's perception of food needs; represented as the

Perceived Stimuli/Needs box), subconscious mental representation (Path 7), or conscious process (e.g., imagination; forward Path 10).

Stimuli exceeding a certain threshold are perceived and produce physiological or psychological changes or trigger unbalanced states. The perception of these stimuli can vary among individuals, encompassing short-term personal conditions and long-term individual disparities.

Instinct

Paths 1–2 correspond to the unconditioned response. Paths 1, 3, 6, 8, 9, and 12 (enclosed in a dashed box) are indicative of classically conditioned responses (Stimulus-Response: S-R), impulsive system, and habit. Paths 1, 3, 4, and 5 depict instinctive behaviors, wherein perceived stimuli and needs give rise to instinctive motivations (forward Path 3), motivations drive behaviors (Paths 4–5), and behaviors are executed according to fixed action patterns (Path 5; Schleidt, 1974). These instinctive motivations and fixed action patterns are “pre-programmed” within the subconscious. The trend of behavior varies according to the strength of motivation; for instance, the trend of eating is robust when experiencing hunger but diminishes when satiated.

Associative Store

Through interaction with the environment, guided by cognitive functions, particularly reflective processes, an initial instinctive motivation can evolve into a multitude of more specific and superficial motivations. For example, consider the transition from a general

motivation to drink water to the specific desire to have an alcoholic beverage at a bar. Moreover, the repetition of such experiences, encompassing emotions, tastes, feelings, and perceptions, along with contextual factors like music, lighting, and others' behaviors, forms mental representation links within the human brain. As Strack and Deutsch (2004) elucidate, “The resulting links reflect correlations between aspects of the environment and cognitive [including perceived stimuli/needs], affective, or motor reactions, without representing the causes of such multimodal correlations” (p. 223). This collection of formed links is termed the *associative store*, which operates in the subconscious state and serves as the foundation of the impulsive system. The associative store can also be thought of as long-term memory (Strack & Deutsch, 2004, p. 225), wherein certain linked <situation, action> pairs might be regarded as *behavioral schemas* from a first-person, internal, or psychological perspective. Simultaneously, they can be seen as *habits of mind* from a third-person, large grain-size, or external perspective, especially for a complex behavior consisting of several smaller actions (each stemming from its own behavioral schema; Selden et al., 2010, pp. 6–7). These habits of mind become associated with body movements, giving rise to physical habits. When dealing with complex behaviors (as previously described), these physical habits can be perceived as chains of conditioned responses (Gantt, 1932, p. 517). Furthermore, sequenced patterns of habitual behaviors that people perform regularly in their daily lives integrate into *routines* (Aunger & Curtis, 2014).

Impulsive System

Bidirectionality is a defining characteristic of the impulsive system (Strack & Deutsch, 2004, p. 235). Perceived stimuli/needs, associative store, and behavioral schema are activated by directionless spreading (Path 6). That means perceived stimuli/needs could activate the associative store (forward Path 6); in turn, the activation of the associative store can modulate the perception of the situation (reverse Path 6; Strack & Deutsch, 2004, p. 240). Similarly, the conceptual content within the associative store and behavioral schema are bidirectionally linked (Path 6; Strack & Deutsch, 2004, p. 229). In other words, the associative store can activate behavioral schema (forward Path 6), and in turn, “people [mental processing] are influenced by what they are doing even if the meaning of an action is not recognized” (reverse Path 6; Strack & Deutsch, 2004, p. 232).

Bidirectionality is also evident in the mediating role of motivational orientations, be it approach or avoidance. As elucidated, “The motivational orientation functions by selectively lowering the threshold for the processing of evaluatively compatible information and for the execution of functionally compatible behaviors” (forward Paths 8–9; Strack & Deutsch, 2004, p. 232). “In turn, a motivational orientation may be elicited by the valence of the processed information” (reverse Path 8; Strack & Deutsch, 2004, p. 232) or “the orientation of a behavior” (reverse Path 9; Strack & Deutsch, 2004, p. 232). Motivation also exerts an influence on perceived stimuli

(reverse Path 3). For example, McClelland and Atkinson (1948) demonstrated that a hungry individual was more likely than a satiated one to identify ambiguous stimuli as being food-related. In the absence of external forced intervention, the impulsive system will execute behavior in accordance with the behavioral schema (forward Path 12).

The impulsive system is dominated by the subconscious, as indicated by the shaded area in Figure 4. This subconscious dominance requires little or no cognitive effort (the ideal state; Strack & Deutsch, 2004, p. 223). In contrast, the reflective system demands more consciousness resources. However, these two systems are not isolated, and presumably interact in the process of behavior formation (Path 10). In this regard, intermediate information from both systems may be captured and entered into each other's processes. For example, "in the reflective system, a behavioral decision is linked to behavioral schemata by the process of intending [i.e., intention]" (Path 11; Strack & Deutsch, 2004, p. 230). In another case, information from consciousness enters the subconsciousness (Path 10) and may induce subconscious behavior through Path 6 (bidirectional) or Path 7. Conversely, subconscious information can also enter the conscious process. For instance, "intending [also belonging to the consciousness] monitors the impulsive system for information that enables the behavioral implementation of the decision" (reverse Path 10; Strack & Deutsch, 2004, p.230). Path 12 (forward) serves as a "final common pathway to overt behavior in the impulsive system that may be activated by input from the reflective and the impulsive system" (Strack & Deutsch,

2004, p. 229).

Past Behaviors

Past behaviors influence multiple constructs and processes within BUM through reverse Path 12. This influence encompasses various aspects, including the perceptions of original stimuli/needs, the deactivation of motivations, the updating of mental representations, the regulation of emotions, and the strengthening of links within the associative store and behavioral schemas.

Model 3: General Behavior Model (Figure 5)

Serial-Form Behavior

The final associated shape of the consciousness stream line with rectangles represents a kind of *serial-form behavior*. Given that only one conscious process occurs at one time (Prost, 2019, p. 389), the consciousness line can only connect to one rectangle at a particular time point. However, different rectangles can overlap because people can perform multiple behaviors simultaneously. Rectangles and arrow lines, with varying quantities and content, and their sequential order symbolize distinct behaviors.

To facilitate analysis, standard behaviors are conceptualized with the following characteristics: (a) the ability to connect BUs of appropriate quality and quantity under various factors to ensure the completion of behavior (a complete consciousness stream line); (b) the

entire behavioral process remains continuously controlled without interruptions (no broken line); and (c) the absence of irrelevant conscious processes (no line deviating from the straight-line direction). As shown in Figure 5, line AH represents the consciousness stream line, commencing at S1 (a stimulus denoted by an oblique arrow), followed by AB (consciousness line) initiating BU1, BE initiating BU2, EF initiating BU3, FG (the ellipsis above FG represents multiple consciousness line and BUs), and subsequent multiple BUs, concluding at BU_n (the last behavior unit) and GH. The ultimate arrangement of AH in conjunction with the rectangles symbolizes standard behavior. The length of EF being shorter than BE suggests that BU2 and BU3 possess a stronger habit association and require fewer conscious resources than BU1 and BU2. When the length of EF is reduced to zero, BU3 can be executed automatically following BU2, without the involvement of consciousness. This indicates that BU2 and BU3 have been integrated into a new BU. Additionally, the overlapping segment of BU2 and BU3 signifies concurrent behaviors, such as humming while riding a bike. Towards the conclusion of the behavior, an evaluation may be performed with consciousness (GH), leading to feedback (Path b) that can influence future behaviors. For example, it may enhance the habit strength of the behavior or its behavioral prepotency (Hall & Fong, 2007), ultimately resulting in a shorter consciousness stream line (see the Conscious-Associated Behavior Model section for details).

Compared to standard behaviors, in reality, people are vulnerable to various disturbances and deviations. Varao-Sousa et al. (2018)

noted that the “shifts of attention can be either inward, toward one’s own thoughts (i.e., mind wandering), or outward, toward an external event (i.e., a distraction)” (p. 1). For example, following stimulation by S2 at point C (time point), the consciousness workflow may move along CI, possibly influenced by a selection mechanism (Ocasio & Wohlgezogen, 2010, p. 192). CI indicates that people detach their attention from AH and even perform irrelevant behavior (e.g., BU4), whereas ID implies that people redirect their attention back to the standard consciousness stream line (AH). In this regard, attention regulation (Ocasio & Wohlgezogen, 2010) is a possible explanation. In the aforementioned process, consciousness requires attention as the precursor, although some experiments have demonstrated the existence of consciousness in the near absence of attention (Koch & Tsuchiya, 2007, p. 18). Some theories of mind wandering (Pachai et al., 2016) offer further explanations. Additionally, it is important to recognize that consciousness, in reality, possesses both continuous and discrete attributes (Herzog et al., 2020). Consequently, CID is represented by dashed lines, with solid segments denoting consciousness and dashed segments representing subconsciousness.

From this, it can be inferred that even for behaviors that appear similar outwardly, the content of consciousness stream lines may vary significantly, and the extent of differentiation depends on the research criteria. However, in behavioral research, standards often allow for a variety of consciousness workflows (consciousness stream lines), such as smoking cessation based on differing attitudes or levels of

self-efficacy. Therefore, it is more reasonable to conceive of the consciousness stream line as a thick line with the width symbolizing the set of consciousness workflows that meet the established criteria.

Parallel-Form Behavior

Relative to the conscious process, the cortex performs many subconscious processes simultaneously (Prost, 2019, p.389), which are related to subliminal stimuli (S3, S4; Dijksterhuis et al., 2005; Warren, 2009, p. 191) and potentially involve the activation of more than one behavioral schema at a time (Strack & Deutsch, 2004, p. 229). These concurrent processes result in the emergence of multiple BUs, which can be executed in parallel or further combined with a serial-form behavior. For example, activities like breathing, blinking, answering the phone, and driving can be performed simultaneously, illustrating a *parallel-form behavior* composed of BU1, BU5, and BU6. When parallel-form behaviors are repetitively enacted to the extent that unidirectional, bidirectional, or multidirectional cue effects are established among them, phenomena such as “consuming potato chips while watching TV” (Kremers et al., 2006, p. 6) emerge. The co-occurrence of behaviors is termed “clustering” (Kremers et al., 2006, p. 6).

In terms of the interaction between conscious and subconscious processes, Prost (2019) posits that “all subconscious processes send signals to the STN [subthalamic nucleus]. When a given subconscious process reaches a certain signal threshold the current conscious

process is interrupted” (p. 385). “It is also possible that the STN switches from the previously conscious process to a previously subconscious process and thus makes the latter the new conscious process” (Prost, 2019, p. 385). Path a (represented by a dashed line with double arrows) denotes the switching channel between the two processes, consistent with Paths 10–11 in BUM. Furthermore, “which behavioral schema [of the two processes] wins out over the other will depend on the relative strength of activation for competing schemas” (Hofmann et al., 2008).

Model 4: Conscious-Associated Behavior Model (Figure 6)

Phases

Based on the distinct roles of consciousness in the process of behavior formation and development, the model is divided into four phases: (a) decision phase, wherein the behaviors are deliberated by assessing desirability (weighing pros and cons of expected outcomes, which can also be reflected in attitude) and feasibility (involving personal agency and beliefs about the likelihood of the expected outcome, e.g., condoms can effectively prevent virus infection) to decide whether to act and what to do; (b) planning phase, in which “the implementation of the chosen goal is planned by deciding on when, where, and how one wants to act toward the goal” (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2007, p. 769); (c) action phase, in which “one progresses toward the goal by initiating goal-directed behaviors and bringing

them to a successful ending” (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2007, p. 769); and (d) evaluation phase, wherein people “compare what has been achieved (outcomes) and obtained (consequences) with what was originally expected or intended” (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2008, p. 278), and gain experiences for future behavior. CABM is an idealized model, implying that each phase unfolds in a sequential manner. However, in reality, consciousness may “wander” among different phases. For instance, state-oriented people with low self-regulatory capacity tend to engage in extensive planning and deliberation before acting (maybe in the decision phase; Bagozzi, 1992, p. 198). Conversely, action-oriented individuals with high self-regulatory capacity tend to act automatically or with minimal deliberation when executing plans (Bagozzi, 1992, p. 198), while potentially regulating the plan during the action phase. Moreover, partial evaluation may be conducted in the action phase, future behavior might be planned during the evaluation phase, or individuals may reconsider the desirability of behavior in the planning or action phases. Hence, the process advances with twists and turns, and may even be abandoned midway.

This process is closely related to individual, behavioral, and environmental factors. Therefore, for behaviors characterized by gradual change (e.g., quitting smoking), individuals' predominant conscious contents and behavior progress (such as being more entangled in decision-making or more focused on implementation details) may vary across different periods (which differs from the phase concept of an idealized single behavior as depicted in Figure 6). Regarding the precompensation state, where people have not yet considered whether

to execute the behavior, some theories regard it as a stage, such as the transtheoretical model (TTM), the precaution adoption process model (PAPM), and the health behavior goal model (HBG model; Maes & Gebhardt, 2000), which falls outside the scope of CABM. Nevertheless, the predominant content or task (“decision,” “plan,” or “action”) of consciousness in a certain period still serves as a valuable reference for segmenting behavior stages in certain theories, such as TTM, PAPM, HBG, and the integrated change model (De Vries et al., 2005).

Evaluation provides essential regulatory guidance for future behavior following the action phase. A negative evaluation diminishes the likelihood of behavior recurrence. Conversely, a positive evaluation would encourage the behavior to recur and may even lead to entry into the maintenance stage (as observed in models like TTM, PAPM, and HBG), until individuals no longer experience the temptation to relapse (the termination stage of TTM) or until a habit is formed. Simultaneously, the consciousness resources invested in each phase gradually diminish, the distinctions between phases diminish, and behavior tends to become automated.

It should be noted that unless a specific BU can provide some independent utility, the consciousness content in each phase is oriented toward conscious-associated behavior capable of achieving the complete goal (or a part of it), rather than focusing on a single BU.

Stimuli

The fundamental driving force behind behavior arises from motivation and its precursor, needs, which are activated by stimuli. The discussion regarding the sources of stimuli in the behavior unit model section is applicable to CABM. Stimuli can originate from the external environment (Path 1), the internal organism (the Perceived Stimuli/Needs Box), conscious mental representation (Path 2), or the subconscious (Path 3). In cases involving multiple stimuli, the more salient the environmental cues are, the stronger the behavioral prepotencies (Hall & Fong, 2007, p. 15), making the corresponding behaviors more readily triggered. However, even identical perceived stimuli/needs can give rise to multiple motivations (as indicated by multiple forward Paths 6; see Motivation, Intention, and Willingness section for details).

Perceived stimuli/needs trigger people to perform specific behavior patterns (belonging to personal norms), which “can be acquired through direct experience or by observing the behavior of others” (observational learning; Bandura, 1977, p. 3). Observational learning relies on modeling stimuli (others’ behavior) that are considered special and influential (Paths 4–5). Modeling influences also exert potent motivational effects based on the outcomes resulting from others’ actions (forward Path 6). “Observed desired effects can create outcome expectancies that serve as positive incentives, whereas observed punishing effects can instill negative outcome expectancies that function as disincentives for similar behavior” (Bandura, 2008, p. 2). Perceived stimuli/needs are likewise influenced by motivation in the reverse

direction (reverse Path 6). For example, motivating operations affect stimulus control (Lotfizadeh et al., 2012). In cases where individuals lack predefined personal norms and do not know how to respond to stimuli, they must acquire new behavior patterns through the above two learning methods, wherein the stimuli prompt exploratory behavior arising from cognitive needs (Saeednia, 2009, p. 4).

Motivation, Intention, and Willingness

“Individuals possess several, often competing, needs that serve to motivate behavior when activated” (multiple forward Paths 6; Shafi et al., 2016, p. 3). For example, individuals may have the goal of deriving enjoyment from eating while also striving for weight control (Stroebe et al., 2013, p. 110). This can be seen as approach-avoidance conflict (Ehrlich & Fasbender, 2017) and, in cases involving multiple goals, double/multiple approach-avoidance conflicts. Additional types of conflicts include approach-approach and avoidance-avoidance conflicts (Ehrlich & Fasbender, 2017).

Conflict resolution is the process of selecting from multiple motivations, which depends on the magnitude of valence (related to attitude), state of tension (related to motivation), individual differences, and psychological distance and individual experiences (related to experience) in relation to the conflict in question (Ehrlich & Fasbender, 2017, pp. 2–3). Finally, the behavior with the strongest behavioral prepotency (Hall & Fong, 2007, p. 15) will be performed. When there is no best option, conflicts may engender a certain degree of stress

(De Heredia et al., 2004, p. 110) and promote exploratory behavior.

Needs are states of felt deprivation marked by the necessity of having to be satisfied, whereas motivations focus on behavior (what and how). It is possible for people to have a need without having a corresponding motivation. For example, a thirsty newborn baby has a need for certain substances (e.g., water) to regulate the homeostasis in their body (quench thirst); however, they have no motivation to find a cup to pour water into because they have not yet learned this behavior. In comparison, an adult can generate specific behavior motivations based on the context and personal preferences, such as picking up a bottle of water or purchasing a lemon soda.

The development of motivation is a process. After a specific stimulus (e.g., the perception of being overweight) triggers a vague motivation to exercise, consciousness begins to compare and select several familiar exercise methods in the decision phase. The motivation at this time can be regarded as choice motivation (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2008, p. 276), which focuses on the “motivational processes involved in goal setting” (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2008, p. 276), wherein people weigh the expected value and realizability of different goals (Gollwitzer, 1990). When the goal of swimming is determined, motivation has produced a concrete goal, described as crossing the Rubicon (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2008). Then, volition comes into play (Path 7), which can also be regarded as control motivation (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2008, p. 276). “Volition concerns the translation of existing goals into action and, specifically, the regulation of

these processes” (Achtziger & Gollwitzer, 2008, p. 276). Volition drives people to make a plan in the planning phase (Path 21). For example, to save time and obtain social support, one may finally decide to join the community interest group and go swimming in the nearby pool every Sunday. In the action phase, volition continues to drive behavior monitoring and maintenance. The development process of motivation involves not only the selection of multiple motivations but also the concretization of behavior. This view is consistent with the temporal construal theory, “which asserts that decisions about action are based initially on abstract construals of the options but become more focused on concrete event details when the actual choice comes near” (Glanz et al., 2008, pp. 130–131). With the gradual presentation of behavior outcomes (none, partial, or all), mainly in the evaluation phase, motivation will be regulated (enhancement, reduction, or even deactivation; Path 8).

In the development of motivation, “intentions are assumed to capture the motivational factors that have an impact on behavior” (Ajzen, 1991, p. 181) and “can range from not contemplating behavioural change to contemplating to change the behaviour very rapidly” (De Vries et al., 2005, p. 155). Michie et al. (2011) included intention in their motivation concept (p. 4). In CABM, intention is considered the externalization of motivation (Path 9), implying that the level of motivation can be measured by intention. When choosing from multiple motivations, goal intention gradually forms; when motivation develops into the volition state, the goal intention also develops into

the implementation intention (Path 10); when motivation is regulated, intention also follows the regulation (enhancement, reduction, or even deactivation; Path 11).

Compared with the intention-behavior route, which is based more on deliberative and systematic reasoning, the willingness-behavior route relies more on heuristics, affect, and experiential processing. Nevertheless, “according to the prototype model, willingness and intentions share some antecedents” (Gerrard et al., 2008, p. 41), such as perceived social norms and attitudes. Both routes operate simultaneously, sometimes competitively, and “consideration of consequences mediates the relation between planfulness [intention] and willingness” (Gerrard et al., 2008, p. 43); at times, they can “switch from one mode to the other depending on factors such as context, the task, and their mood” (Gerrard et al., 2008, p. 54). In short, unlike the formation of intention, which represents a rational processing style, the formation of willingness is less deliberative and more heuristic when the situations or opportunities are unfamiliar. These heuristic processes are “efficient cognitive processes, conscious or unconscious [refers to subconscious], that ignore part of the information” (Gigerenzer & Gaissmaier, 2011, p. 451). However, both intention and willingness are externalized forms of motivation.

Perceived Social Norm/Modeling, Attitude and Agency

Attitudes, personal agency, perceived social norms, and others’ behaviors influence the motivation to change behavior. Many

theories have discussed how these factors affect intention (such as TPB, TRA, IBM: Integrated Behavior Model; Paths 12–13). CABM views motivation and intention as the relationship between essence and externalization. The transition from motivation to intention is a developmental process involving dynamic interactions among various factors, including attitudes, personal agency, perceived social norms, planning, and other constructs.

Additionally, motivation has a reverse impact on attitude and personal agency (reverse Path 12 and reverse Path 13; Hagger et al., 2003, p. 786). This occurs because the intrinsic causality of motivation serves as a source of information in shaping attitudes, perceived behavioral control (Chatzisarantis et al., 2002), and self-efficacy. For instance, when motivation is strong, individuals may overestimate their self-efficacy, a phenomenon potentially linked to heightened arousal or emotion. Within this relationship, attitudes and agency mutually influence each other in a bidirectional manner (Path 14), with motivation serving as a mediating factor.

The more one is convinced that he or she is able to perform a specific behavior and maintain it at a certain level, for example, on the basis of previous experience, the more one is likely to expect that the perceived benefits of the new behavior will occur. (Maes & Gebhardt, 2000, p. 360)

Conversely, Witkiewitz and Marlatt (2004) observed that in high-risk contexts, the drop in self-efficacy may affect attitudes,

leading to negative affect and expectancies. Li (2012) also identified that “attitude and self-efficacy are related to each other” (p. 178).

Sparks (1992) postulated “that attitude variability is negatively related to perceived control” (p. 55).

Unlike TPB, TRA, and IBM, CABM posits that perceived social norms, as environmental factors relative to the target individual, do not directly influence intention or motivation. Instead, they indirectly impact attitudes and agency by providing information. Modeling learning also plays a pivotal role, as both concepts involve the guiding function of other people's behaviors on one's own behaviors (Path 18). Researchers have even suggested that the “importance of modeling is now also referred to as descriptive norms” (Rivis & Sheeran, 2003, as cited in De Vries, 2017, p. 2), and social norms can also be seen as focal points for observational learning (Young, 1996).

However, the emphases of the two are different. The former focuses on acceptable behavior norms from the perspective of social groups, whereas the latter emphasizes the modeling effects of others' behaviors. In CABM, the following five functions are highlighted.

Patterns of Behavior (Path 18). Triggered by modeling stimuli (Path 5), “in abstract, observers extract the rules and principles embodied in the specific judgments or actions exhibited by others” (Bandura, 2008, p. 2) and “organize component responses into new patterns of behavior” (Bandura, 1977, p. 10). These new patterns of behavior can be considered as personal norms, serving as a foundation for the formation of attitudes and agency related to personal behaviors (Paths 15–16). Similarly, descriptive norms also provide information

about the personal norm, guiding individuals' behaviors (Legros & Cislighi, 2020, p. 68). This implies that the effects of perceived social norms and modeling on attitudes and agency are indirectly realized through personal norms.

Attitudes Toward Personal-Related Behavior (Path 15). People not only learn the behavior patterns of others but also observe the detriments and benefits experienced them (Bandura, 2008, p. 1), which can be described as vicarious experiences. The observed consequences provide reference information, known as vicarious reinforcement (Bandura, 1977), influencing attitudes toward personal norms.

Another way attitudes may be influenced is through heuristics. For example, in the case of descriptive norms, which refer to perceptions of significant others' attitudes and behaviors in a particular domain, “the opinions and actions of significant others provide information that people may use in deciding what to do themselves” (Rivis & Sheeran, 2003, p. 220). In simpler terms, it can be expressed as “if everyone is doing it, then it must be a sensible thing to do” (Cialdini et al., 1991, p. 203). Moreover, persuasion from an influential person (referred to as instrumental attitude) may also make people feel that a behavior is meaningful.

Furthermore, others' behaviors could serve as cues to bolster existing beliefs and attitudes (Rimal, 2008, p. 105). For example, college students perceive that drinking alcohol can lead to increased affective expression, feelings of happiness, emotional moderation,

stress reduction (Baum-Baicker, 1985), and protection against heart disease (Dufour, 1996). “These beliefs are likely to be strengthened by perceptions that many others engage in the behaviors, which in turn can lead to greater behavioral intentions” (Rimal, 2008, p. 105).

Agency Toward Personal-Related Behavior (Path 16). Personal agency encompasses self-efficacy and perceived behavioral control. Bandura (1989) proposed four sources of self-efficacy: mastery experiences, vicarious experiences, verbal persuasion, and physiological states (p. 60). “The second source of increasing self-efficacy is vicarious experiences that are the acquiring and the use of self-efficacy in comparison to the others’ performances in the social context” (Piran, 2014, p. 59). Similarly, since vicarious experiences provide reference and comparison information, they could also influence perceived behavioral control. Verbal persuasion can serve as an injunctive norm and has a more active role in affecting agency compared to vicarious experiences.

Attitudes From Social Pressure (Path 17). The same behavior can be driven by multiple needs and motivations. In addition to influencing the relevant constructs (attitude and agency) of behavior driven by nonsocial needs (e.g., health), perceived social norms can also affect attitudes by exerting social pressure. For descriptive norms or, if applicable, the norm attribute of modeling, “perceptions about the wide prevalence of a behavior would lead individuals to perceive strong pressures to comply with the group behavior, which in turn would enhance their own behavioral intentions” (Rimal, 2008, p. 104). “It is natural to believe that one, too, has to do likewise to

demonstrate solidarity with the group” (Rimal, 2008, p. 104) or “to express membership [identity] in a group” (Legros & Cislighi, 2020, p. 68). Regarding subjective norms, “the person’s potential to gain approval or suffer sanctions from significant others for engaging in a behavior” (Rivis & Sheeran, 2003, p. 219) would result in perceived social pressure. This pressure can be regarded as the motivation derived from belongingness or esteem needs.

In turn, people’s attitudes and agency affect their perceptions of social norms and modeling (reverse Path 17). As proposed by Rimal (2008):

Individuals with positive outcome expectations [attitude] are likely to interpret strong descriptive norms to mean that many others are also deriving benefits from consumption, and thus, in order not to deprive themselves of those benefits, their own behavioral intentions are likely to be strong. (p. 105)

Objective Capability (Paths 19–20). “Observational learning [as illustrated in the dashed box labeled ‘Observational Learning’] plays a key role in the acquisition of knowledge, cognitive skills, and new styles of behavior” (Bandura, 2008, p. 2). This capability encompasses both psychological and physical attributes, and is internalized as specific personal attributes based on personal norms (forward Path 19). In turn, it also influences the development of agency and other consciousness processes, including self-regulation (with

the capability attribute). Therefore, multiple arrows (reverse Paths 19) from the “Objective Capability” box indicate this overall effect.

During the action phase, objective capability can directly affect behavior (Path 20). For instance, “if someone wants to live on a diet, he or she has to know how to prepare low-calory dishes” (De Vries et al., 1988, p. 381).

Reason

Attitudes, personal agency, and perceived social norms are determined by beliefs (Glanz et al., 2008, pp. 71, 77). Conversely, Westaby (2005) introduced a more abstract and general concept, *reasons*, which “serve as important linkages between beliefs, global motives (e.g., attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived control), intentions, and behavior” (p. 97). As an intermediate process within consciousness, reasons may not always be fully activated in certain situations, such as in cases involving heuristic motives or a personal preference for simplified information processing (Westaby, 2005, p. 102).

Reasons can be powerful drivers of intention [through global motives] because people feel more comfortable with themselves when they have reasons that justify and defend their anticipated actions, even if their global motives are not perfectly aligned with their intentions. (Westaby, 2005, p. 101)

From this perspective, although the reason concept is not embodied in CABM, reason, attitude, agency, and perceived social norm

are all intermediate variables in the formation of intention within the model.

Planning

The plan comprised the identification of a cue in the environment that would be linked to the initiation of the behavior (e.g., “If my alarm clock chimes at 12 noon, I will collect my gym bag and go for a workout at my local fitness center”). (Hagger & Chatzisarantis, 2014, p. 65)

With the development of motivation-intention, plans formation (Path 21) occurs in the volition state (Heckhausen & Gollwitzer, 1987). Planning is an important ability that comprises “plans to implement intentions by specific actions to reach the goal behavior and actual skills” (De Vries, 2003, p. 613). Plans also possess an intention attribute, defined by West and Brown (2013) as “a self-conscious intention to perform an act in the future” (p. 183). Intentions are more likely to be translated into behaviors when people formulate detailed coping plans to manage possible scenarios, barriers, and opportunities (Schwarzer, 2016a). In general, planning realizes the concretization of behavior at the mental representation level, refines the behavior forms of the personal norm, and subsequently, influences the development of motivation and intention through attitudes and agency. That is the first updating route or mechanism of CABM. In this route, motivation and intention act as moderators through which attitudes and agency impact the formulation of plans. As posited by Ewart

(1991), “self-efficacy appraisals guide the selection of action strategies” (p. 936). In summary, planning plays a positive role in promoting health behavior, a conclusion supported by numerous studies, such as in breast self-examination (Gollwitzer & Oettingen, 1998), cervical cancer screening (Sheeran & Orbell, 2000), and vitamin supplement use (Sheeran & Orbell, 1999).

Reinforcement and Experience

Once the decision and planning phase is complete, the process transitions into the action phase, during which the BUs are consciously associated (see General Behavior Model section for details). In this phase, people remain susceptible to other stimuli (Path 22), and their behavior may either persist, deviate, or be interrupted. This phase necessitates self-regulation, as outlined in the Self-regulation section.

Following the completion of a behavior, whether active or passive, reinforcements of various forms (direct reinforcement and self-reinforcement) and intensities are generated, constituting response-outcome (R-O) associations (Path 23). Subsequently, outcome-response (O-R) associations (Path 24) are “formed as a consequence of experience with the consequent R-O contingency” (de Wit & Dickinson, 2009, p. 473). Moreover, knowledge regarding the connection between actions and outcomes is an essential prerequisite for future goal-directed behavior (de Wit & Dickinson, 2009, p. 468). The formation of these associations and knowledge relies on the involvement of

consciousness (the shaded area encompassing self-regulation) and behavior internalization (the mental representation of R-O, O-R, and experiences) during the evaluation phase, thereby shaping a mechanism (operant conditioning [R-Sr] or instrumental learning) capable of guiding future behavior. This internalization process, coupled with physiological and psychological experiences, broadly affects various constructs within CABM (Path 25), including attitude, perceived subjective norm, perceived behavioral control, behavioral schema (Hagger & Chatzisarantis, 2014, p. 64), self-efficacy (West & Brown, 2013, p. 100; Pfitzner-Eden, 2016, p.1; Parkinson et al., 2017, p. 415; Vancouver et al., 2002, p. 507), emotional and psychological consequences (Flay & Petraitis, 1994, pp. 38–39; Haselhuhn et al., 2012, p. 6), motivation (West & Brown, 2013, p. 200), mental representation (West & Brown, 2013, p. 208), personal norm, perceived descriptive norm, and objective capability. In this way, the entire CABM system is updated, representing the second updating route (a mechanism) of CABM.

Self-Regulation

Within CABM, self-regulation, represented by the dashed box in the shadow labeled “Self-Regulation,” runs through the entire process. The regulation content varies according to the internal organism, external environment, and behavior phases. Simultaneously, self-regulation encompasses numerous components, such as motivation, emotions, attitude, agency, personal norms, and behavior, as well as

various processes including self-monitoring, self-judgment, planning, and the first and second updating routes, all of which are integral to CABM (see Table 1 for details).

General Constructs***Related Behavior***

Based on characteristics in terms of time, space, and function, four types of behaviors influence the target behavior:

- Antecedent behaviors provide the necessary preparations for the target behavior (e.g., buying sneakers in advance for running).
- Collaborative behaviors, also recognized in epidemiology as clustered behaviors, provide stimuli or associative constructs to the target behavior.
- Competitive behaviors compete with the target behaviors for resources and may lead individuals to engage in non-target behaviors.
- Same/Similar behaviors provide direct or referential experiences for the future target behavior.

The effects of these related behaviors on target behavior, mediated through constructs of CABM or BUM, are indirect and wide-ranging. Therefore, they are not presented independently in Figure 4 and Figure 6.

Personal State

Personal state is a general term encompassing individuals' short-term physiological and psychological state, especially factors with

global effects such as emotion, arousal, and physiological state. Personal state can change on account of various factors such as life events, medications, or alcohol consumption. Emotion, in particular, is a pervasive factor with connections to numerous other aspects, including:

- Need (Gu et al., 2019, p. 4)
- Motivation (West & Brown, 2013, p. 8, 200; Van Dellen, 2012, p. 38; Maes & Gebhardt, 2000, p. 356; Bodenhausen, 1993, p. 21; Strack & Deutsch, p. 236)
- Intention (Ajzen, 2011, p. 1116)
- Perceived stimulus (West & Brown, 2013, p. 199), belief (Frijda et al., 2000, p. 1),
- Attitude (West & Brown, 2013, p. 69; Hall & Fong, 2007, pp. 32–33)
- Self-efficacy (Stasiewicz & Maisto, 1993, p. 338)
- Perceived social norm (Bastian et al., 2017, p. 7)
- Attitude-intention relationship (Bagozzi, 1992, p. 186)
- Subjective norms-intention relationship (Bagozzi, 1992, p. 178)
- Arousal state (West & Brown, 2013, p. 199; Sylwester, 2000, p. 21)

- Self-regulation (Bagozzi, 1992; West & Brown, 2013, p. 204; Leventhal et al., 2003; Hofmann et al., 2008, p. 113)
- Decision making (Watanabe & Haruno, 2015, p. 1)
- Memory (Bodenhausen, 1993, p. 21; Watanabe & Haruno, 2015, p. 1)
- Cognitive capacity (Bodenhausen, 1993, p. 16; Halama, 2017, p. 158)
- Problem-solving capabilities (Ewart, 1991, p. 940)
- Association learning (Watanabe & Haruno, 2015, p. 1)
- Instinct behavior (Ginsberg, 1926)
- Subconscious process (Watanabe & Haruno, 2015)
- Other consciousness processes (Van Dellen, 2012, p. 40; Bodenhausen, 1993, p. 21, p. 7)

Moreover, emotion itself exhibits attributes of various other factors, such as stimulus (Stasiewicz & Maisto, 1993, p. 339), attitude (Hunt & Martin, 1988, p. 210), social norm (Legros & Cislighi, 2020, p. 66), goal (Watanabe & Haruno, 2015, p. 1), subconsciousness process (Sylwester, 2000, p. 20), instinct behavior (Gu et al., 2019, p. 4; Ginsberg, 1926, p. 42), and personality (Corr & Matthews, 2020).

Individual Difference

Individual differences, categorized as distal variables (Glanz et al., 2008, p. 81), exert indirect and extensive influence on various constructs. For instance, temperament influences individuals' emotions, activities, social interactions, cognition, arousal states, motivations, attitudes, perceived stimuli, abilities, and experiences (Goldsmith et al., 1987, as cited in Ewart, 1991, p. 940; Kagan et al., 1988, as cited in Ewart, 1991, p. 940).

Environment

The environment can be categorized in various ways, such as microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem (Bronfenbrenner, 1979, as cited in Glanz et al., 2008, p. 468), or macro, meso, and micro levels (Latkin et al., 2010, p. 222). The environment can directly or indirectly impact behavior development. For example, external stimuli directly trigger behaviors, whereas social groups promote or restrict behaviors by indirectly affecting perceived social norms. As a broad concept, the environment exerts widespread influences on many constructs. For a specific behavior, the role of the environment should be analyzed concretely.

Time

“Temporal factors influence behavior at several levels” (Hall & Fong, 2007, p. 23). In cases of time constraints, BUM is more likely to occur; in CABM, “the value a person places on results that he/she will not see for days, weeks, or years is a temporal valuation for that

behavior” (Ballay, 2017, pp. 33–34). “It is common for people to prematurely respond to the immediate benefits of some activities rather than placing value in the long-term benefits of other activities” (Ballay, 2017, p. 47). Time is an essential consideration in the decision-making (not only in the decision phase) and plays a critical role in reinforcement (Wang, 2020, p. 65). “The reinforcement which develops skill must be immediate. Otherwise, the precision of the differential effect is lost” (Skinner, 2014).

Appendix G

Cross-Appendix References

Appendix G contains the complete shared references used across all appendices (A-F). For references cited exclusively within the main text, see the References chapter.

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